

COVID-19 infection and medicines in pregnancy – a multinational electronic health records/registry-based study

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7 November 2023

Title	COVID-19 infection and medicines in pregnancy – a multinational registry based study
Version identifier	0.3
Date of last version	November 7, 2023
EU PAS register number	EU PAS 39438
Active substance	NA
Medicinal product	NA
Product reference	NA
Procedure number	EMA/2017/09/PE/11 (Lot 4). Study on impact of COVID-19 infection and medicines in pregnancy.
Marketing authorisation holder(s)	None
Research question and objectives	<p>This study is based on electronic health care registry data from 7 health care databases in 6 European countries between 2018 and 2021. The primary objectives are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) To estimate the prevalence of medicines used, by trimester of pregnancy and compare this between pregnant women with COVID-19, pregnant women without COVID-19 and non-pregnant women of reproductive age with COVID-19. 2) To describe severity and clinical outcomes of COVID-19 in pregnant and non-pregnant women. 3) To compare the rates of adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes in pregnant women with and without COVID-19, using different medicines.
Country(-ies) of study	<p>Participating electronic health care databases among CONSIGN partners:</p> <p>Denmark – nationwide registries France – nationwide registries Italy – regional registry (Tuscany) Norway – nationwide registries Spain – regional registries (Valencia and Aragon) UK – national registry (Wales)</p>

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1 List of abbreviations

ACOG	American College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists
ARS	Agenzia Regionale di Sanita' della Toscana
ATC	Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical
BMI	Body Mass Index
BPE	Bordeaux PharmacoEpi
CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
CDM	Common Data Model
CI	Confidence interval
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease
DAP	Data Access Provider
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EMR	Electronic Medical Records
ENCePP	European Network of Centres for Pharmacoepidemiology and Pharmacovigilance
ETL	Extract, Transform, and Load
EU PAS	The European Union electronic Register of Post-Authorisation Studies
FICF	Catalan Institute of Pharmacology Foundation (FICF)
FISABIO	-Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencia Region -
HSRU	Health Services Research Unit
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GP	General Practitioner
IACS	Instituto Aragonés de Ciencias de la Salud
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
LMP	Last menstrual period
NHS	National Health Service
SAIL	Secure Anonymised Information Linkage
SAP	Statistical Analysis Plan
SARS-CoV-2	Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2
SNDS	Système National des Données de Santé
SWANSEA	Swansea University
UiO	University of Oslo
VID	Valencia Integrated Database

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4 Deliverables

Deliverable	Date
D2a. Protocol submitted to the EMA	16 October 2020
D3. Interim report, objective 1	16 July 2021
D4. Final report of study results	17 November 2022 / updated November 2023

Milestone	Planned date
Protocol submitted to the EMA	16 October 2020
Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL) design finalized	February 2020
Statistical analysis plan finalized	March 2021
Data extraction & ETL	March/ April 2021
Running quality & first analysis	April 2021
Interim report, objective 1	16 July 2021
Data extraction, objective 2 and 3	March 2022
Submission of study report	November 2022
Submission of updated study report	November 2023

DISCLAIMER: We call pregnant persons women, as the majority of pregnant persons would identify with this.

5 Rationale and background

SARS-CoV-2 leaves pregnant women, health care providers and authorities with numerous unanswered questions, but with little data to guide them. Although several case series, small cohort studies and meta-analyses of COVID-19 and pregnancies are appearing,¹⁻¹⁵ we still do not know the full consequences of COVID-19 infection and treatment on maternal and neonatal health and early infant development. Foregoing clinical care, in accordance with constraints imposed by the pandemic, may also impact pregnancy outcomes. It is not fully clear how the pandemic impacted fertility, pregnancy outcomes, breastfeeding, child development and pregnancy termination.

At the launch of the study in 2020 very little data existed on the fetal safety of SARS-CoV-2 medicines, and what we do know is gleaned from the use of these drugs for other indications. Management of COVID-19 during pregnancy is currently based on clinical “best guess” and includes aggressive infection control procedures, testing for SARS-CoV-2 and coinfection, antibiotics (for secondary bacterial infection risk) and fetal monitoring.¹⁶ Advice on delivery mode was lacking in the early part of the pandemic.¹⁷ WHO considered that COVID-19 infection alone is not an indication for caesarean section.¹⁸

The CONSIGN project was funded by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) (specific contract 04 Implementing framework contract No EMA//28/PE, Lot 4) to address questions regarding utilization of medications among pregnant women with COVID-19, and its impact on the unborn child.. The project has led to the establishment of a new collaboration of over thirty researchers, harnessing data from eight electronic health care registries in seven European countries (Denmark (DK), France (FR), Italy (IT), Norway (NO), Spain (ES), Sweden (SE), United Kingdom (UK)). Data sources include general practice/primary care databases (e.g. UK, ES), claims databases (FR) and record linkage of demographic data, registers and dispensing data (SE, NO, DK, IT, ES).

6 Research questions and objectives

Objective 1. Medication utilisation

The specific objectives are:

- a. To estimate the prevalence of medicines use in pregnant women with COVID-19
- b. To compare prevalence of medicines use between pregnant women with COVID-19 with those for pregnant women without COVID-19
- c. To compare prevalence of medicines use between pregnant women with COVID-19 and non-pregnant women of reproductive age with COVID-19.

Objective 2. Severity of COVID-19 in pregnant and non-pregnant women

The specific objective is:

- a. To describe the severity of COVID-19 disease among pregnant and non-pregnant women with COVID-19.

Objective 3. Adverse maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes

The specific objectives are:

- a. To describe the rates of adverse maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes in pregnant women with and without COVID-19
- b. To assess the impact of COVID-19 on pregnancy-related adverse outcomes
- c. To describe the rate of adverse outcomes in pregnant women with COVID-19 according to medication use in pregnancy among non-hospitalized women with COVID-19 in pregnancy.

Medication use refers to outpatient or primary care prescribed/dispensed medicines as recorded in the electronic health care registries participating in the project in the 30-day window pre- and post-COVID-19 infection.

The medications that are captured by each DAP represent primary care dispensing/prescriptions. WP2 and WP3 of the CONSIGN project covers inpatient drug utilization. Results should be interpreted bearing this in mind.

7 Research methods

7.1 Study design

The study was a multi-database cohort study, conducted during the years 2018 to 2021, including a period of SARS-CoV-2 circulation in Europe until the date of last data availability for each data source.

The source population included women of reproductive age (12-55 years), pregnant women and their children observed in any one of the participating data banks for at least one day during the study period (01.01.18 – 31.12.20/last data availability).

Studying the outcomes of pregnancy and identifying pregnancies is subjected to left and right censoring. Figure 1 shows how left and right censoring operate. Left censoring is caused by the study start date, 1/1/2018. To avoid left censoring bias for pregnancy analyses we only included pregnancies that coincide with the pandemic (C, D), and a historical (background) group (B).

Right censoring of pregnancies was considered a more important concern, any data cut that does not capture full information up until 1 October 2021 for pregnancies starting in 2020, will suffer from right censoring. Since some data sources identify pregnancies based on pregnancy end, shorter follow-ups would bias towards the inclusion of preterm births, as they are more likely to have ended by a certain censoring date.

To negate the selection risk of pregnancies with early terminations and to ensure three months of follow up post birth to examine for a diagnosis of congenital anomalies, the inclusion of pregnancies was limited to those for which the latest start date of pregnancy was set at a full 12 months before the end date of data availability.

Figure 1 Schematic illustration of pregnancy cohorts considering SARS-COV-2 circulation. In brown: the group of non-pregnant women with COVID-19. For the analyses we will include women in group C and D (pregnant women), as well as non-pregnant women of childbearing age (contemporaneous) and the historical comparator group (B).

7.2 Sources and study population

The CONSIGN project included data from 8 data sources in 7 European countries. The Data Access Providers (DAPs) participating in the study are listed in Table 1, along with the data sources they have access to (Table 2). Further details of these DAPs and the data sources they have access to are provided in Annex 2.

For this report, eight Data Access providers (DAPS) in seven countries were eligible to participate. The end date of data available differed by DAP. Most DAPS had data available until 31.12.2021, and therefore pregnancies completed by 30.09.2021 were included, to facilitate a three month follow up to identify recording of congenital anomalies. This was operationalized by restricting to those pregnancies that had started by 1.1.2021 to give each pregnancy a full 9 months duration plus the necessary 3 month of follow up, rather than restrict on end date. In BPE, the end date of data available was one year earlier (31.12.2020) and therefore only pregnancies that started by 1.1.2020 were included, again to facilitate a three month follow up after delivery.

Table 1 Overview of data sources and end date of data available

Data source	Country	DAP	Estimated births per year	Total population	Type of data source	End date of data available
ARS database (ARS)	Italy – Tuscany	ARS	25 000	3.6 million	Record linkage	2021-12-31
Valencia Integrated Database (VID)	Spain – Valencia	FISABIO-HSRU	32 000	5 million	Record linkage	2021-12-31
SAIL database (SAIL)	UK – Wales	SWANSEA	29 000	3 million	Record linkage	2021-12-31
PRECOVID Study and EpiChron Cohort (PRECOVID)	Spain – Aragon	IACS	10 000	1.3 million	Cohort	2021-12-31
Linked national registries (Norway)	Norway	UiO	60 000	5.3 million	Record linkage	2021-12-31
Linked national registries (Denmark)	Denmark	Aarhus University	60 000	5.8 million	Record linkage	2018-12-31
Système National des Données de Santé (SNDS) ¹	France	BPE	700 000 (70 000 in the 1/10th sample extracted)	67 million (6.7 million in the 1/10th sample extracted)	Health insurance	2020-12-31

Notes:

¹Given the very broad inclusion criteria, a representative 1/10th sample of the full SNDS will be used.

Abbreviations: ARS = Agenzia Regionale di Sanita' della Toscana; BPE = Bordeaux PharmacoEpi platform; FISABIO-HSRU = Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencia Region - Health Services Research Unit; IACS = Instituto Aragonés de Ciencias de la Salud; SAIL = Secure Anonymised Information Linkage; SNDS = Système National des Données de Santé; SWANSEA = Swansea University; UiO = University of Oslo; VID = Valencia Integrated Database.

Please note that the medications that are captured by each DAP represent primary care dispensing/prescriptions. WP2 and WP3 of the CONSIGN project covers inpatient drug utilization. Results should be interpreted bearing this in mind.

Table 2 Information on data sources and data banks available for CONSIGN study

Data source	Country	Diagnoses recordings	Medicines (Care level)	Medical birth registry
ARS database (ARS)	Italy – Tuscany	Hospital ¹	Dispensings in community pharmacies (primary care)	Yes
Valencia Integrated Database (VID)	Spain – Valencia	GP, specialist, Hospital	Dispensing and prescriptions (linked) (primary care)	Yes
SAIL database (SAIL)	UK – Wales	GP, Hospital	Primary care prescribing for ~80% population ² (primary care)	Yes
PRECOVID Study and EpiChron Cohort	Spain – Aragon	GP, Hospital	Dispensings in community pharmacies (primary care)	No
Linked national registries (Norway)	Norway	GP, specialists, Hospital	Dispensings in community pharmacies (primary care)	Yes
Linked national registries (Denmark)	Denmark	Hospital	Dispensings in community pharmacies (primary care)	Yes

Data source	Country	Diagnoses recordings	Medicines (Care level)	Medical birth registry
Système National des Données de Santé (SNDS) ³	France	Hospital	Dispensings in community pharmacies or hospital pharmacies for outpatient use + expensive drugs dispensed in hospital (inpatient data) (primary and secondary care)	No

Notes:

¹ Also emergency admissions, exemptions from copayment for chronic conditions, access to mental healthcare. ² In Wales, ~80% primary care providers voluntarily supply medicines data to the databank. Any selection bias is due to healthcare providers, not subjects. ³ Given the very broad inclusion criteria, a representative 1/10th sample of the full SNDS will be used. Birth related outcomes are available through hospital discharge summary database, but there is not specific birth registry.

Abbreviations: ARS = Agenzia Regionale di Sanita' della Toscana; BPE = Bordeaux PharmacoEpi platform; FISABIO-HSRU = Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencia Region - Health Services Research Unit; GP = General Practitioner; IACS = Instituto Aragonés de Ciencias de la Salud; SAIL = Secure Anonymised Information Linkage; SNDS = Système National des Données de Santé; SWANSEA = Swansea University; UiO = University of Oslo; VID = Valencia Integrated Database.

7.3 Study population

The study cohort consisted of two pandemic populations and one pre-pandemic cohort:

1. Pregnant women whose pregnancy duration overlapped the COVID-19 pandemic (i.e. were pregnant on or after 01.03.2020 or whose pregnancy started by 01.01.2021*)
2. Non-pregnant women of childbearing age with COVID-19 during the COVID-19 pandemic period (i.e. women who were not pregnant on or after 01.03.2020 until end of data)
3. Pre-pandemic pregnancy cohort: Pregnant women whose pregnancy was completed prior to 31/12/2019

*01.01.2020 in BPE

1. Pregnant women whose pregnancy overlapped the COVID-19 pandemic

This cohort included women who were 12-55 years of age and pregnant on the start date of the pandemic, defined as 01.03.2020, or their pregnancy started after this date (i.e. were pregnant on or after 01.03.2020 or whose pregnancy started by 01.01.2021, except for BPE as mentioned above), and whose pregnancy prompted a recording in the data sources by the time of most recent update.

Further exclusions to this pregnancy cohort which overlapped the pandemic were:

1. Pregnancies that started before June 1, 2019 (and therefore would end before the start of the pandemic in Europe (defined as 01.03.2020))
2. Pregnancies in women with less than one year of continuous prescription data prior to the start of pregnancy.
3. Pregnancies without recorded end or start date (red quality, see section 7.4.1)

A woman could contribute data on more than one pregnancy, as pregnancy was the unit of analysis.

2. Non-pregnant women of childbearing age with COVID-19

For each pregnancy identified in the pregnant cohort among people with COVID-19, three non-pregnant persons with COVID-19 (among women aged 12-55 years), were selected to compare medical product use, as well as baseline characteristics during a defined period for which such woman did not have a pregnancy. Details of the matching process are provided in Section 7.5.1.

3. Pre-pandemic group: Pregnant women whose pregnancy was completed prior to the COVID-19 pandemic

This included women who were 12-55 years of age and whose pregnancy commenced from 01.01.2018 and was completed prior to 01.01.2020, and whose pregnancy prompted a recording in the data sources by the time of most recent update with a green, yellow, or blue classification by the pregnancy algorithm (see above).

7.4 Study variables

7.4.1 Pregnancy start and end dates

The start of pregnancy was defined as the estimated first day of the last menstrual period (LMP); end of pregnancy was the date of delivery or abortion (elective/spontaneous). Pregnancy start and end dates were assessed based on the data banks used to detect the pregnancy:

- medical birth registers
 - LMP: The first day of the LMP is estimated by subtracting the gestational age at delivery, as recorded in the register, from the pregnancy end date; if gestational age is estimated both by ultrasound and the woman's recall of LMP, the former is preferred.
- records of diagnostic codes (e.g. hospitalizations):
 - gestational age at the record date is estimated using the algorithm of Matcho et al,¹⁹
- records of procedure codes:
 - gestational age at the record date is estimated using the algorithm of Matcho et al,¹⁹ possibly adjusted per data source-specific predicted gestational age
- primary care medical records or hospitalization records
 - date of the pregnancy delivery or date of abortion are retrieved as recorded

Novel methods to identify pregnancies using diagnostic codes, procedure codes and primary care records were developed as part of ConcePTION. Details of how individual DAPs identify pregnancy start and end date are provided in Annex 3.

The IMI-ConcePTION pregnancy algorithm which allows for several streams of information to detect pregnancies in databanks, together with their start or end date was used to extract pregnancies from each of the data sources.

Pregnancies identified using this algorithm have the following classification system:

- quality is green if both pregnancy_start_date and pregnancy_end_date are recorded;
- quality is classified yellow if pregnancy_end_date is recorded and pregnancy_start_date is imputed;
- quality is blue if pregnancy_start_date is recorded and pregnancy_end_date is imputed;
- quality is red if both pregnancy_start_date and pregnancy_end_date are imputed.

Only green (based on registers), yellow and blue pregnancies were included in the primary analyses; women with red pregnancies were excluded from the study (*exception ARS).

7.4.2 *Trimester of pregnancy*

The period of pregnancy was divided into trimesters. The American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG, 2017) definition of timing in pregnancy was used:²⁰

- Trimester 1: from Last Menstrual Period (LMP) to day < 98 after LMP; or end of pregnancy, whichever earlier
- Trimester 2: from day 98 after LMP to day <196 after LMP; or end of pregnancy, whichever earlier
- Trimester 3: from day 196 after LMP onwards until end of pregnancy

7.4.3 *Maternal age*

Age at start of pregnancy was categorised as follows:

- 12-24 years of age
- 25-39 years of age
- 40-55 years of age

7.4.4 *Maternal vaccination status*

Influenza vaccination status during the pregnancy of interest was examined.

7.4.5 *SARS-CoV-2 infection and severity of COVID-19 disease*

7.4.5.1 *COVID-19 case definition*

SARS-CoV-2 infections and COVID-19 were identified by records in surveillance systems, or diagnostic codes in health care records and/or laboratory results.

See Annex 3 for details of DAP specific means of identifying COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis in their data banks. In all data sources - with the exception of BPE using SNDS data in France - a COVID-19 surveillance registry was available which allowed the identification of a confirmed diagnosis. BPE had access to inpatient data (PMSI) with ICD10 codes of COVID-diagnoses only. No positive test results were available.

7.4.5.2 Severity of COVID-19 disease: hospitalization

COVID-19 disease severity was categorized as hospitalized or not hospitalized depending on whether or not the woman was admitted to hospital with a COVID-19 diagnosis. Since information on ICU admission or respiratory support was not known in each of the data sources, no further categorization of severity level was possible.

Non-hospitalized COVID-19

Recording of a positive COVID-19 test (PCR or antigen test) or COVID-19 diagnosis (but not identified from a hospital admission) with no subsequent hospital admission with a recording (primary or secondary) of COVID-19 within a 4-week period.

Hospitalized COVID-19

Any recording of a positive COVID-19 test (PCR or antigen test) or COVID-19 diagnosis in any of the diagnostic fields in hospital records (not just the principal diagnosis.), within 4 weeks of initial COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis.

Note 1: If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were classified separately as “COVID-19 at delivery”. They were included in the analysis undertaken on the total cohort of those that tested positive for COVID-19 during their pregnancy, but were not included in the sub-category classified as ‘hospitalized’; they were quarantined in those analyses. This is why the sum of non-hospitalized and hospitalized will not add up to the total.

Note 2: As BPE only had access to inpatient data with ICD10 codes of COVID-diagnoses only, all episodes of COVID-19 identified in their data were classed as hospitalized COVID-19 infection, with the caveat that those diagnoses within 2 days of delivery were not included in this classification, in a similar manner to other DAPS.

7.4.6 Medical conditions increasing the risk to be hospitalized for COVID-19

Medical conditions increasing the risk for hospitalization due to COVID-19 were defined based on scientific evidence available from the US Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC website, July 2020, and updates).²¹

Table 3 lists the medical conditions increasing the risk, diagnostic codes and proxies, identified in line with the ACCESS project.²² A composite variable of pre-disposing risk factors was created to indicate the presence of any one of these conditions. Multi-morbidity was not considered; subjects could belong to more than one at-risk group. A one-year look back time-period prior to the start of pregnancy - to assess relevant diagnostic codes or ATC codes - was applied.

Table 3 Co-morbid conditions with evidence of increased COVID-19 severity

At-risk medical conditions (diagnostic codes) ¹	Medicinal product proxy(ies) (ATC code)
Cardiovascular incl. blood	
Cardiovascular disease/ Serious heart conditions including: heart failure, coronary artery disease, cardiac myopathies hypertension	Antiarrhythmics, class I and III (C01B) Cardiac stimulants excl. Cardiac glycosides (C01C) Vasodilators used in cardiac diseases (C01D) Other cardiac preparations (C01E) Antithrombotic agents (B01A) Antihypertensives (C03, C07, C08, C09)
Sickle Cell Disease	Hydroxyurea (L01XX05) Other hematological agents (B06AX)
Respiratory	
Chronic lung disease including COPD, cystic fibrosis, severe asthma, interstitial lung disease, pulmonary hypertension, bronchiectasis	Drugs for obstructive airway diseases (R03) Lung surfactants (R07AA) Respiratory stimulants (R07AB)
Endocrine and metabolic	
Type 1 & 2 Diabetes	Insulin and analogues (A10A) Blood glucose lowering drugs (A10B)
Obesity diagnosis or having a BMI ≥ 30 kg/m ²	Peripherally acting antiobesity products (A08AB) Centrally acting antiobesity products (A08AA)
Renal	
Chronic kidney disease	Erythropoietin (B03XA01)
Liver	
Chronic liver disease diagnosis (cirrhosis, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, alcoholic liver disease, autoimmune hepatitis)	Antiviral agents for the treatment of HCV infections (J05AP)
Immunological	
HIV	Protease inhibitors (J05AE) Combinations to treat HIV (J05AR) NRTI (J05AF) NNRTI (J05AG)
Immunosuppression & solid organ transplants	Immunosuppressants (L04A) Corticosteroids (H02)
Cancer	Alkylating agents (L01A) Antimetabolites (L01B) Plant alkaloids and other natural products (L01C) Cytotoxic antibiotics and related substances (L01D)

At-risk medical conditions (diagnostic codes) ¹	Medicinal product proxy(ies) (ATC code)
	Other antineoplastic agents (L01X) Hormones and related agents (L02A) Hormone antagonists and related agents (L02B) Immunostimulants (L03) Immunosuppressants (L04)
Mental health disease NA	Antipsychotics N05A, Anxiolytics N05B Antidepressants N06A

Notes:

1. Codelists developed as part of VAC4EU were utilized. See Additional document: 20221017_CODELIST_CONSIGN_NARROW

7.4.7 *Risk Conditions for Obstetric Complications*

The following maternal obstetric conditions were examined in the two year period prior to the start of pregnancy:

- history of gestational diabetes
- history of preeclampsia
- stillbirth or spontaneous abortion

The data banks used by each DAP used to identify the presence of medical conditions that increase the risk of hospitalization for COVID-19 or risk of obstetric complications are provided in Annex 3.

7.4.8 *Medications*

Medicines are exposures of interest as they may impact pregnancy outcomes, be used to treat symptoms of COVID-19 infections, or be proxies for maternal medical conditions (risk factors for adverse outcomes). Timing of medicine use relative to COVID-19 as well as timing of medicine use in pregnancy (trimester), is relevant to understand drug utilisation patterns (objective 1) as well as for maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes (objective 3)

Information on medicines was retrieved from outpatient or primary care prescription/dispensing records. For each prescription/dispensing record we used the prescription/dispensing date to reflect timing of actual medicine availability. The prevalence of medicine use of special relevance for COVID-19 was examined in the 30-day till -1 window pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis (day 0-30). Medication was analyzed at ATC-2, ATC-3 level and where clinically relevant (Maisonneuve E in submission) to substance level (ATC-level 5). See

Table 4 and Annex 4.

Table 4

Table 4 ATC-levels 2 medicines of special relevance to COVID-19

Drug class	ATC code
Drugs used in diabetes	A10
Antithrombotic agents	B01
Antihypertensives	C02, C03 C04 C07, C08, C09
Corticosteroids for systemic use	H02
Antibacterials for systemic use	J01
Antimycotics	J02
Antimycobacterials	J04
Antivirals for systemic use	J05
Immune sera and globulins	J06
Vaccinations	J07
Antineoplastic agents	L01
Immunostimulants	L03
Immunosuppressants	L04
Anti-inflammatory drugs	M01
Antigout preparations	M04
Analgesics	N02
Psycholeptics	N05
Psychoanaleptics	N06
Antiprotozoals	P01
Anthelmintics	P02
Nasal preparations	R01
Medicines for obstructive airway disease	R03
Cough and cold preparations	R05

7.4.9 Maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes

The maternal pregnancy and neonatal, outcomes evaluated are presented in **Error! Not a valid bookmark self-reference..**

Table 5 Definitions of maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes¹

OUTCOMES	Definition
Maternal death	Maternal death or maternal mortality is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as "the death of a woman while pregnant or within 42 days of termination of pregnancy, irrespective of the duration and site of the pregnancy, from any cause related to or aggravated by the pregnancy or its management but not from accidental or incidental causes.
Gestational diabetes (GDM)	GDM is as glucose intolerance with onset or first recognition in pregnancy.
Preeclampsia	Pre-eclampsia is defined as new onset hypertension (>140 mm Hg systolic or >90 mm Hg diastolic) after 20 weeks of pregnancy and the coexistence of one or both of the following new-onset conditions: Proteinuria (urine protein: creatinine ratio \geq 30 mg/mmol, Albumin/creatinine ratio \geq 8 mg/mmol, or \geq 1 g/L [2+] on dipstick)

OUTCOMES	Definition
Spontaneous abortion	Pregnancy ending spontaneously before 22 weeks of gestation (i.e. up to and including 21 6/7 weeks of gestation). ¹
Caesarean section	
Pre-term birth	Birth at less than 37 completed weeks (less than 259 days) of gestation
Stillbirth	Late fetal death, after 22 completed weeks of gestation. ¹
Neonatal death	Neonatal mortality refers to death of a live-born baby within the first 28 days of life. Early neonatal mortality refers to the death of a live-born baby within the first seven days of life, while late neonatal mortality refers to death after 7 days until before 28 days.
Low birth weight	Body weight of the newborn at birth of less than 2,500 grams (up to and including 2,499 g).
Small-for-gestational age (SGA)/ Intrauterine growth restriction	Defined as an observed weight of a live born infant or size of a foetus lower than expected, usually below the 10th percentile, on the basis of gestational age and sex
Low Apgar score (5-minute)	A 5-minute Apgar score of 7–10 is classified as normal, a score of 4–6 as moderately abnormal, and a score of 0–3 as low in the term infant.
Major congenital anomalies	Morphological, functional and/or biochemical developmental disturbance in the embryo or foetus whether detected at birth or not. The term congenital anomaly is broad and includes congenital abnormalities, foetopathies, genetic diseases with early onset, developmental delay.
Microcephaly	Congenital anomaly

¹ Some DAPS, following the approach taken locally, classify fetal deaths up to week 24 as spontaneous abortion. 2. Codelists developed as part of VAC4EU were utilised. See Additional document: 20221017_CODELIST_CONSIGN_NARROW.

7.5 Analysis

7.5.1 Description of the prevalence of medication use

Obj 1a. Prevalence of medication use in the cohort of pregnant women with COVID-19

Population: Study population included all pregnant women (aged 12-55 years) whose pregnancy overlapped the pandemic and had a diagnosis of/positive test results for COVID-19 during pregnancy.

Exposure: COVID-19 in pregnancy (overall, hospitalized, and non-hospitalized), stratified by trimester of pregnancy when the infection occurred.

Analyses: Prevalence of medication use in the 30 days prior to the date of COVID-19 infection and in the 30 days after the index date of COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis (including the date of test/diagnosis) was computed.

The numerator was the count of women having one or more dispensing/prescription (date of prescription/dispensing) of the specific medication within the 30- day window pre/post COVID-19 positive test or diagnosis. The denominator was the number of women contributing person-time to that trimester.

Obj 1b. Prevalence of medication use in a matched cohort of pregnant women with and without COVID-19

Population: Study population included all pregnant women (aged 12-55 years) whose pregnancy overlapped the pandemic and had a diagnosis of COVID-19 during pregnancy.

Matching: Pregnant women with COVID-19 in pregnancy during the pandemic were matched (1:3 without replacement) to pregnant women without COVID-19 in pregnancy during the pandemic. Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 had estimated pregnancy start within +/- 14 days from pregnancy start for pregnant women with COVID-19 and had same age category. Pregnant women without COVID-19 were assigned the date of their matched partner's COVID-19 positive test or diagnosis. For the referent pregnant cohort without COVID-19, additional exclusion criteria was applied requiring no COVID-19 diagnosis observed during any trimester (i.e. for the entire pregnancy period).

Exposure: COVID-19 in pregnancy (overall, hospitalized, and non- hospitalized), stratified by trimester of pregnancy when the infection occurred.

Analyses: Baseline characteristics of the matched groups were described using counts and proportions (where appropriate). Comparisons of baseline characteristics between hospitalized, and non-hospitalized COVID cases were conducted using standardized differences.

Prevalence of medication use was described as per Obj 1a above.

Obj 1c. Prevalence of medication use in a matched cohort of pregnant and non-pregnant women with COVID-19

Population: Study population included all pregnant women (aged 12-55 years) whose pregnancy overlapped the pandemic and had a diagnosis of COVID-19 during pregnancy.

Matching: Pregnant women with COVID-19 in pregnancy during the pandemic were matched (1:3 without replacement) to non-pregnant women with COVID-19 on age group and timing of COVID-19 diagnosis (+/- 7 days of each other). Non-pregnant women were assigned the start date of pregnancy of their matched pregnant partner (to facilitate the creation of a pseudo trimester of pregnancy when infection occurred).

Exposure: COVID-19 in pregnant women vs. COVID-19 in non-pregnant women (overall, hospitalized, and non-hospitalized), stratified by trimester of pregnancy when COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis occurred for the pregnant women.

Analyses: Baseline characteristics of the matched groups were described using counts and proportions (where appropriate). Comparisons of baseline characteristics (at start of pregnancy) between hospitalized and non-hospitalized COVID cases were conducted using standardized differences.

Prevalence of medication use was undertaken as per Obj 1a above.

7.5.2 Description of the severity of COVID-19 disease in pregnant and non-pregnant women

In the Study protocol, the aim of Objective 2 was to compare the association between medication use and the severity of COVID-19. However, since other studies undertaken by partners in the CONSIGN consortium found that both the type and number of medicines used was so highly correlated with severity of COVID-19, this analysis was considered inaccurate. Instead, for all analyses, the results of prevalence of medication use were presented stratified by disease severity (non-hospitalized COVID-19 and hospitalized COVID-19).

7.5.3 Adverse maternal and pregnancy outcomes

Obj 3a. Prevalence of adverse maternal and pregnancy outcomes in pregnant women in the pre-pandemic era

Population: Pregnant women who were 12-55 years of age and whose pregnancies commenced from 01.01.2018 and were completed prior to 01.01.2020.

Analysis: The prevalence of each pregnancy-related outcome was computed as the number of events divided by the number of pregnancies in the cohort. The count of pregnancies in the denominator differed depending on the outcome of interest, as per Table 6.

Table 6 Pregnancies included in the analyses of adverse maternal and pregnancy outcomes

Outcome	Pregnancies included
Gestational diabetes	Pregnancies that reached at least 20 weeks of gestational age
Pre-eclampsia (including eclampsia & HELLP)	Pregnancies that reached at least 20 weeks of gestational age
Maternal death	All pregnancies
Spontaneous abortion	All pregnancies
Caesarean section	All pregnancies
Pre-term birth	Live births only
Stillbirth	Pregnancies that reached at least 22 weeks of gestational age ¹
Neonatal death	Live births only
Low birth weight	Live births only
Small for gestational age/intrauterine growth restriction	Live births only
Low Apgar score (5-minute)	Live births only
Major congenital anomalies	Live births only
Microcephaly	Live birth only

Notes: 1. 24 weeks in UK

Obj 3b: Prevalence of adverse maternal and pregnancy outcomes in a matched cohort of pregnant with and without COVID-19

Population: The study population for this analysis were the matched pregnant study cohorts with and without COVID-19 as used in objective 1b.

Exposure: COVID-19 in pregnancy stratified by trimester and severity of COVID-19 disease.

Analysis: Adverse pregnancy and neonatal outcomes in pregnant women with COVID-19 were described by presenting the prevalence overall, by trimester of pregnancy at COVID-19 diagnosis, and by COVID-19 severity. The prevalence of each pregnancy-related outcome was computed as the number of events divided by the number of pregnancies in the cohort stratified by trimester of COVID-19 infection. Outcome-specific risk windows (i.e. exposure to COVID-19), were defined for each of the outcome. See **Table 7**.

Table 7 Outcome-specific exposure window for inclusion of pregnant women in the corresponding analysis

Outcome	Exposure window	Comment
Gestational diabetes	First trimester exposure only	Because the operational definition of gestational diabetes is any outcome occurrence from start of second trimester, only exposure in the first trimester time window is investigated.
Pre-eclampsia (including eclampsia & HELLP)	First trimester exposure only	Because the operational definition of pre-eclampsia is any outcome occurrence from start of second trimester, only exposure in the first trimester time window is investigated.
Maternal death	From LMP to end of pregnancy	

Outcome	Exposure window	Comment
Spontaneous abortion	From LMP to before week 22 of gestation (21 weeks and 6/7 days)	Because the outcome occurs before week 22, only exposure up to end of gestational week 21 is investigated
Caesarean section	From LMP to end of pregnancy	
Pre-term birth	From LMP to before week 37 of gestation (36 weeks and 6/7 days)	Because the outcome occurs before week 37, only exposure up to end of gestational week 36 is investigated.
Stillbirth	From LMP to end of pregnancy	
Neonatal death	From LMP to end of pregnancy	
Low birth weight	From LMP to end of pregnancy	
SGA/ Intrauterine growth restriction	From LMP to end of pregnancy	
Low Apgar score (5-minute)	From LMP to end of pregnancy	
Major congenital anomalies	First trimester exposure only	
Microcephaly	First trimester exposure only	

Effect estimates were calculated as relative risks with 95% CIs using a modified Poisson model with robust estimate of the variance, while adjusting for co-variates. Modified Poisson regression, which combines a log Poisson regression model with robust variance estimation, is a useful alternative to log binomial regression for estimating relative risks. Unlike log binomial regression, modified Poisson regression is not prone to convergence problems. To avoid immortal time bias when studying effect of COVID-19 infection on risk of non-live birth outcome (i.e. spontaneous abortion, stillbirth), exposure was modelled as time-dependent within the Cox proportional hazard framework. In each model, adjustments were made adjusted for age (by the matching design), calendar week (by the matching design) and for factors for hospitalized COVID-19 (composite variable, binary) and obstetric risk factors (composite variable, binary).

Objective 3c: Prevalence of adverse maternal and pregnancy outcomes according to medicines use in pregnancy among women with COVID-19 but not hospitalized for COVID-19

Population: Pregnant women with COVID-19 without a hospital admission for COVID-19. The cohort of pregnant women with COVID-19 was restricted to women categorized as having non-hospitalized COVID-19 to avoid misclassification of medicines exposure during hospitalisation, as DAPs did not have access to information on exposures to medication in hospitals.

Exposure: Medication exposure was defined at three levels:

- Exposed to medication in the 30 days pre COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis
- Not-exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis
- Exposed to medication in the 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis

Analysis: The prevalence of individual outcomes was presented per level of medication exposure, stratified by trimester of pregnancy.

8 Results

8.1 Description of the pregnancy cohort which overlapped the pandemic

The pregnancy cohort included women who were 12-55 years of age and pregnant on the start date of the pandemic, defined as 01.03.2020, or their pregnancy started after this date, and whose pregnancy prompted a recording in the data sources by the time of most recent update. The latest start date of pregnancy was set at 1.1.2021 to allow for a full nine months of pregnancy and a three-month follow-up post-delivery to examine for a diagnosis of congenital anomalies.

Table 8 describes the pandemic pregnancy cohort (2020/2021). This cohort included 294,126 pregnant women; 8,943 (3.0%) of whom tested positive for, or were diagnosed with COVID-19, during their pregnancy (Table 8). The proportion of pregnant women who tested positive for or were diagnosed with COVID-19 during pregnancy ranged from 1.2% (UIO, Norway) to 5.6% (IACS, Spain). Just under half of COVID-19 cases (47.7%) occurred during the third trimester of pregnancy.

The patterns among BPE (France) were inconsistent with other DAPS as BPE had access to inpatient data (PMSI) with ICD10 codes of COVID-diagnoses only. Furthermore, the time period covered was pregnancies completed between 1. March 2020 and 1. October 2020 (latest start date of pregnancy was set at 1.1.2020), hence the vast majority of cases were trimester 3 infections.

Table 8 Description of the pregnancy cohort which overlapped the pandemic (before matching)

	Total Pregnancies	COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis in pregnancy	Diagnosis in Trimester 1	Diagnosis in Trimester 2	Diagnosis in Trimester 3	Median gestational week of infection
	N	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	Weeks
ARS, Italy	41,415	992 (2.4%)	207 (20.9%)	277 (27.9%)	508 (51.2%)	29
BPE, France	45,125	1069 (2.4%)	7 (0.7%)	92 (8.6%)	970 (90.7%)	40
FISABIO-HSRU, Spain	58,379	2978 (5.1%)	941 (31.6%)	856 (28.7%)	1181 (39.7%)	23
IACS, Spain	15,847	892 (5.6%)	190 (21.3%)	266 (29.8%)	436 (48.9%)	27
SWANSEA, Wales	46,322	1941 (4.2%)	576 (29.7%)	638 (32.9%)	727 (37.5%)	22
UIO, Norway	87,038	1071 (1.2%)	230 (21.5%)	398 (37.2%)	443 (41.4%)	25
Total	294,126	8943 (3.0%)	2151 (24.1%)	2527 (28.3%)	4265 (47.7%)	

Abbreviations: ARS = Agenzia Regionale di Sanita' della Toscana; BPE = Bordeaux PharmacoEpi = FISABIO-HSRU = Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencia Region - Health Services Research Unit; IACS = Instituto Aragonés de Ciencias de la Salud; UiO = University of Oslo.

8.1.1 Timing of COVID-19 infection in the pregnancy cohort

Figure 2 presents calendar time of COVID-19 positive test or disease by month from March 2020 to September 2021 for the cohort of pregnant women who had a positive test or diagnosis for COVID-19 during their pregnancy. Most COVID-19 diagnoses/positive tests occurred between 09/2020 and 03/2021.

Figure 2 Timing of COVID-19 infection in the pregnancy cohort

Notes: Includes pregnancies which overlapped the pandemic (1.3.2020) with latest start date of pregnancy set at 1.1.2021

Abbreviations: ARS = Agenzia Regionale di Sanita' della Toscana; BPE = FISABIO-HSRU = Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencia Region - Health Services Research Unit; IACS = Instituto Aragonés de Ciencias de la Salud; UiO = University of Oslo.

8.2 Prevalence of medication use in pregnant women with COVID-19 in pregnancy

The prevalence of medication use among pregnant women with a positive test/diagnosis for COVID-19 during pregnancy are presented in the Annex 6. These tables represent **all included pregnancies** with a COVID-19 positive /diagnosis after applying in-and exclusion criteria. Section 8.2 and Section 8.3 present similar tables, but among the matched cohorts.

Tables are provided separately for each DAP, and for each level of severity of COVID-19 infection. Within each table, prevalence estimates are stratified by the trimester of pregnancy when the COVID-19 infection took place. Estimates are presented separately for the 30-day window pre- and the 30-day window post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis. Results are presented at the ATC-

2 level, results at the ATC-3, ATC-4 and ATC-5 level are available as additional files. In the interest of making the tables more interpretable, results have been suppressed to present only those rows with a minimum prevalence of 2% in any of the cells in that row. The full tables are also provided as Additional file 1.

Of note, the wide confidence interval of the prevalence estimates is due to small sample size and indicate a low level of precision of the results. This is especially noticeable among hospitalized COVID-19 cases, where counts are considerably smaller. Details of the hospitalization of COVID-19 cases in the matched cohort of pregnancy women with and without COVID-19 (per DAP) can be found in Table 22.

8.2.1 Antithrombotic medicines (B01)

The increase in use of antithrombotic medicines in the 30-day window after COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis was the most notable result of the analyses. The magnitude of this increase varied by the trimester of pregnancy when infection occurred, as well as the DAP providing results.

Among total cases of COVID-19 in ARS (Italy), rates of antithrombotic medicines use in the 30-day window before infection were broadly similar across trimesters of pregnancy (3.9%, 4.3% and 3.7% respectively). In trimesters 1 and 2, following COVID-19 test/diagnosis, the prevalence of use as compared to the pre-COVID-19 test/diagnosis increased by a magnitude of approximately 4-fold. In trimester 3 however, there was approximately an 8-fold increase in prevalence from 3.7% (2.4-5.8) during the 30 days prior to the positive test/diagnosis to 29.5% (25.7-33.6) in the 30 days following the positive test/diagnosis. In FISABIO-HSRU (Spain), there was a 10-15-fold increase in the prevalence of antithrombotic medicines use after COVID-19 test/diagnosis, which was seen across all trimesters of pregnancy, including trimester 1. For example, antithrombotic use in trimester 2 increased from 4.4% (3.3-6.0) in the 30 days prior to positive test/diagnosis to 50.7% (47.4-54.0), and from 3.8% (2.9-5.1) to 61.9% (59.1-64.6) in trimester 3 of pregnancy. In IACS, use of antithrombotic medicines in the 30-day window pre-COVID-19 test/diagnosis was considerably higher than that seen in other DAPS. For example, among total cases, in trimester 2, 17.9% were dispensed an antithrombotic in the 30 days pre-test/diagnosis; as were 14.7% of trimester 3 cases¹. Prevalence of use increased to 37.5% and 44.7% post-test/diagnosis.

In UIO (Norway), baseline rates of antithrombotic use in pre-COVID-19 window were lower (of the order of 1-2%), and the use after COVID-19 test/diagnosis was considerably lower than that seen elsewhere. The use of antithrombotic medicines increased 6.6-fold after COVID-19 infection in trimester 3 corresponding to an increase on an absolute scale from 0.9% (0.4-2.3) to 5.9% (4-

¹ It is probable that this anomaly is caused by a delay of 1-2 days in the registering of a positive COVID-19 test result in the surveillance system.

8.5). SWANSEA (Wales) did not see an increase in prescribing of antithrombotic medicines in the 30-day window post COVID-19 diagnosis.

Among the hospitalized COVID-19 cases (Table 10), the increase in use of antithrombotic medicines was even more pronounced between pre-COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis and after. In UIO (Norway), the prevalence of medication use increased from 2.6% (0.5-13.2) to 17.9% (9-32.7) following COVID-19 in pregnancy trimester 2 infections and from 2.9% (1-8.1) to 15.4% (9.7-23.5) among pregnancies with a COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis in trimester 3.

In BPE (France) prevalence increased from 3.1% (1.5-6.3) to 25.9% (20.6-32.0) among pregnancies with a COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis in trimester 3. Antithrombotic medicines in ARS, IACS and FISABIO post trimester 2 infection among the hospitalized COVID-19 cases was considerably higher than that observed in UIO and BPE: 47.1% (26.2-69.0), 66.7% (43.7-83.7) and 74.4% (64-82.6).

Among the non-hospitalized COVID-19 cases (Table 11) UIO was an exception, with no increase seen in the prevalence of antithrombotic use after COVID-19 infection. All other DAPS had substantial increases in the use of this class of medicine following non-hospitalized COVID-19 disease as compared to the 30 days prior. Stricter data privacy regulations in Wales prohibit the release of prevalence estimates at the level of stratification undertaken here.

From examination of the use antithrombotic medicines at the ATC 3rd, 4th, 5th level among pregnancies with trimester 3 infections, the majority of use was driven by enoxaparin (B01AB05). There was no use of unfractionated heparin (B01AB01) (Table 12-14).

Table 9 Prevalence of antithrombotic medicines (B01) prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (total cases)

DAP	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	0-30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)
IT-ARS	3.9 (2-7.4)	12.6 (8.7-17.8)	4.3 (2.5-7.4)	16.6 (12.7-21.4)	3.7 (2.4-5.8)	29.5 (25.7-33.6)
FR-BPE	0 (0-35.4)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	3.3 (1.1-9.2)	6.5 (3-13.5)	1.9 (1.2-2.9)	22.8 (20.3-25.5)
ES-FISABIO	2.3 (1.5-3.5)	31 (28.2-34.1)	4.4 (3.3-6)	50.7 (47.4-54)	3.8 (2.9-5.1)	61.9 (59.1-64.6)
ES-IACS	5.2 (2.9-9.1)	20.8 (15.8-26.7)	17.9 (13.9-22.8)	37.5 (32.1-43.3)	14.7 (11.8-18.2)	44.7 (40.2-49.3)
WA-SWANSEA	1.2 (0.6-2.5)	1.7 (0.9-3.2)	2.2 (1.3-3.6)	2.5 (1.5-4)	1.4 (0.7-2.5)	1.2 (0.7-2.3)
NO-UIO	1.7 (0.7-4.4)	1.7 (0.7-4.4)	1.3 (0.5-2.9)	2.5 (1.4-4.6)	0.9 (0.4-2.3)	5.9 (4-8.5)

Table 10 Prevalence of antithrombotic medicines (B01) prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (hospitalized COVID-19 hospitalized cases)

DAP	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)
IT-ARS	0 (0-29.9)	66.7 (35.4-87.9)	5.9 (1-27)	47.1 (26.2-69)	7.5 (3.9-14.2)	50 (40.6-59.4)
FR-BPE	0 (0-35.4)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	3.3 (1.1-9.2)	6.5 (3-13.5)	3.1 (1.5-6.3)	25.9 (20.6-32)
ES-FISABIO	0 (0-39)	50 (18.8-81.2)	7.7 (1.4-33.3)	61.5 (35.5-82.3)	2.4 (0.7-8.5)	74.4 (64-82.6)
ES-IACS	0 (0-24.2)	41.7 (19.3-68)	16.7 (5.8-39.2)	66.7 (43.7-83.7)	24.3 (16-35.2)	83.8 (73.8-90.5)
WA-SWANSEA	*	*	*	1.8 (1-3.2)	*	*
NO-UIO	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	2.6 (0.5-13.2)	17.9 (9-32.7)	2.9 (1-8.1)	15.4 (9.7-23.5)

* Wales cannot release numbers between 1 and 4 either directly or in a call that would disclose a number 1-4 elsewhere in the report.

Table 11 Prevalence of antithrombotic medicines (B01) prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (non-hospitalized COVID-19 cases)

DAP	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)
IT-ARS	4.4 (2.3-8.5)	10.5 (6.8-15.8)	4.2 (2.4-7.4)	14.6 (10.8-19.4)	2.7 (1.4-5.2)	21.3 (17-26.3)
FR-BPE1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
ES-FISABIO	2.3 (1.5-3.5)	31.3 (28.3-34.3)	4.3 (3.1-5.9)	50.4 (47-53.8)	4.5 (3.2-6.2)	61.8 (58.3-65.2)
ES-IACS	5.6 (3.2-9.8)	19.5 (14.5-25.6)	18 (13.8-23)	35.6 (30.1-41.5)	18.5 (13.9-24.1)	33.3 (27.5-39.8)
WA-SWANSEA	*	*	*	13.9 (6.1-28.7)	*	*
NO-UIO	1.8 (0.7-4.6)	1.8 (0.7-4.6)	1.1 (0.4-2.8)	0.8 (0.3-2.4)	0.3 (0.1-1.9)	2.3 (1.1-4.7)

Notes: ¹In BPE COVID-19 cases were identified based on admission to hospital with a COVID-19 diagnosis. Hence there are no cases classed as non-hospitalized. * Wales cannot release numbers between 1 and 4 either directly or in a call that would disclose a number 1-4 elsewhere in the report.

Table 12 Prevalence of antithrombotic medicine at the ATC-3, 4, 5 level, in the 30-day window after COVID-19: pregnancy trimester 3 positive test/diagnosis, total cases

ATC –level name (code)	Antithrombotic medicines (B01A)	Heparin group (B01AB)	Heparin (Unfractionated) (B01AB01))	Enoxaparin (B01AB05)	Acetylsalicylic acid (B01AC06)
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
IT-ARS	29.5 (25.7-33.6)	29.1 (25.4-33.2)	0 (0-0.8)	22.6 (19.2-26.5)	0.6 (0.2-1.7)
FR-BPE	22.8 (20.3-25.5)	22.6 (20.1-25.3)	0 (0-0.4)	20 (17.6-22.6)	0.5 (0.2-1.2)
ES-FISABIO	61.9 (59.1-64.6)	61.6 (58.8-64.3)	0 (0-0.3)	48.7 (45.8-51.5)	1.4 (0.9-2.3)
ES-IACS	44.7 (40.2-49.3)	43.2 (38.8-47.7)	0 (0-0.8)	42.1 (37.7-46.7)	1.5 (0.7-3.1)
NO-UIO	5.9 (4-8.5)	5.4 (3.7-7.9)	0 (0-0.9)	2.5 (1.4-4.4)	0.5 (0.1-1.6)

Table 13. Prevalence of antithrombotic medicine use at the ATC-3, 4, 5 level, in the 30-day window after COVID-19: pregnancy trimester 3 positive test/diagnosis, hospitalized cases

ATC –level name (code)	Antithrombotic medicines (B01A)	Heparin group (B01AB)	Heparin (Unfractionated) (B01AB01)	Enoxaparin (B01AB05)	Acetylsalicylic acid (B01AC06)
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
IT-ARS	50 (40.6-59.4)	50 (40.6-59.4)	0 (0-3.5)	44.3 (35.2-53.8)	0.9 (0.2-5.2)
FR-BPE	25.9 (20.6-32)	25.4 (20.2-31.5)	0 (0-1.7)	22.8 (17.8-28.7)	1.3 (0.5-3.9)
ES-FISABIO	74.4 (64-82.6)	73.2 (62.7-81.6)	0 (0-4.5)	58.5 (47.7-68.6)	2.4 (0.7-8.5)
ES-IACS	83.8 (73.8-90.5)	83.8 (73.8-90.5)	0 (0-4.9)	77.0 (66.3-85.1)	2.7 (0.7-9.3)
NO-UIO	15.4 (9.7-23.5)	15.4 (9.7-23.5)	0 (0-3.6)	7.7 (3.9-14.4)	0 (0-3.6)

Table 14. Prevalence of antithrombotic medicine use at the ATC-3, 4, 5th level, in the 30-day window after COVID-19: pregnancy trimester 3 positive test/diagnosis, non-hospitalized cases

ATC –level name (code)	Antithrombotic agents (B01A)	Heparin group (B01AB)	Heparin (Unfractionated) (B01AB01))	Enoxaparin (B01AB05)	Acetylsalicylic acid (B01AC06)
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
IT-ARS	21.3 (17-26.3)	20.6 (16.4-25.6)	0 (0-1.3)	14.9 (11.3-19.4)	0.7 (0.2-2.4)
FR-BPE	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
ES-FISABIO	61.8 (58.3-65.2)	61.4 (57.9-64.8)	0 (0-0.5)	49.9 (46.3-53.4)	1.9 (1.1-3.1)
ES-IACS	33.3 (27.5-39.8)	31.5 (25.8-37.9)	0 (0-1.7)	31.5 (25.8-37.9)	2.3 (1-5.2)
NO-UIO	2.3 (1.1-4.7)	1.7 (0.7-3.8)	0 (0-1.3)	0.7 (0.2-2.4)	0.7 (0.2-2.4)

8.2.2 Antibacterial medicines (J01)

Overall, the prevalence of use of antibacterial medicines (J01) was not influenced by COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, with the exception of France where among those with trimester 3 infections, prevalence of use increased from 6.6% (5.2-8.3) prior positive test/diagnosis to 17.8% (15.6-20.4) after the positive test/diagnosis.² Patterns of use in other countries show little change

² In BPE total COVID-19 cases were identified based on admission to hospital with a COVID-19 diagnosis. Severe cases were a subset of these cases, where the admission did not take place within +/- 2 days of delivery.

in antibacterial medicines before vs after COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, based on overlap of confidence intervals, with some minor increases observed in trimester 3 (Table 15).

Table 15 Prevalence of antibacterial medicines (J01) prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (total cases)

DAP	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
IT-ARS	6.8 (4.1-11)	12.1 (8.3-17.2)	5.8 (3.6-9.2)	6.9 (4.4-10.5)	5.3 (3.7-7.6)	8.9 (6.7-11.6)
FR-BPE	42.9 (15.8-75)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	19.6 (12.7-28.8)	34.8 (25.8-44.9)	6.6 (5.2-8.3)	17.8 (15.6-20.4)
ES-FISABIO	3.3 (2.3-4.6)	4.3 (3.1-5.7)	3.5 (2.5-5)	5.3 (4-7)	4.5 (3.4-5.8)	5.3 (4.2-6.8)
ES-IACS	5.7 (3.3-9.6)	7.5 (4.7-11.9)	5.6 (3.5-8.9)	5.3 (3.2-8.5)	5.2 (3.5-7.6)	8.4 (6.2-11.3)
WA-SWANSEA	4.9 (3.4-6.9)	6.4 (4.7-8.7)	6.0 (4.4-8.1)	6.1 (4.5-8.2)	3.4 (2.3-5)	8.1 (6.3-10.3)
NO-UIO	2.6 (1.2-5.6)	4.3 (2.4-7.8)	4.3 (2.7-6.7)	4 (2.5-6.4)	3.4 (2.1-5.5)	7.2 (5.2-10)

8.2.2.1 Azithromycin (J01FA10)

The use of antibacterial medicines at the substance level was investigated further. We present in the main report only the results for the use of azithromycin. Other medicines are listed in the annexes. Table 16 Table 17 Among all pregnancies with COVID--19 positive test/diagnosis there was minimal use of azithromycin and minimal change between pre- and post-positive test/diagnosis, with the exception of ARS.

Table 16 Prevalence of azithromycin prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (total cases)

DAP	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
IT-ARS	2.4 (1-5.5)	5.8 (3.3-9.9)	1.1 (0.4-3.1)	1.8 (0.8-4.2)	0.8 (0.3-2)	1.8 (0.9-3.3)
FR-BPE	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-4)	3.3 (1.1-9.2)	0 (0-0.4)	0.8 (0.4-1.6)
ES-FISABIO	0.2 (0.1-0.8)	1 (0.5-1.8)	0.1 (0-0.7)	0.2 (0.1-0.8)	0 (0-0.3)	0.1 (0-0.5)
ES-IACS	0.5 (0.1-2.6)	0 (0-1.8)	0 (0-1.3)	0.4 (0.1-2)	0.4 (0.1-1.6)	0.2 (0-1.2)
NO-UIO	0 (0-1.6)	0 (0-1.6)	0 (0-1)	0 (0-1)	0 (0-0.9)	0 (0-0.9)

Table 17 Prevalence of azithromycin prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (hospitalized cases)

DAP	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)
IT-ARS	0 (0-29.9)	22.2 (6.3-54.7)	0 (0-18.4)	0 (0-18.4)	0 (0-3.5)	1.9 (0.5-6.6)
FR-BPE	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-4)	3.3 (1.1-9.2)	0 (0-1.7)	0.4 (0.1-2.5)
ES-FISABIO	0 (0-39)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-4.5)	0 (0-4.5)
ES_IACS	0 (0-24.2)	0 (0-24.2)	0 (0-17.6)	0 (0-17.6)	1.4 (0.2-7.3)	0 (0-4.9)
NO-UIO	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-9)	0 (0-9)	0 (0-3.6)	0 (0-3.6)

8.2.3 Corticosteroids for systemic use (H02)

Use of systemic corticosteroids was low (less than 2% prevalence in most DAPS), and therefore not presented in all tables. Across all DAPS, increases in prevalence estimates were accompanied by overlapping confidence intervals. The increase seen in ARS after COVID-19 infection in the first trimester was from 2.4% (1-5.5) to 8.2% (5.2-12.8) in all cases and from 11.1% (2-43.5) to 33.3% (12.1-64.6) in those classed as hospitalized (Annex 6).

8.2.3.1 Glucocorticoids (H02AB)

The use of systemic glucocorticoids was investigated at the ATC- 4 level. Results for total cases are presented in Table 18 and in Table 19 for those classed as hospitalized.

Table 18 Prevalence of glucocorticoids prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (total cases)

DAP	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)
IT-ARS	2.4 (1-5.5)	8.2 (5.2-12.8)	1.4 (0.6-3.7)	5.4 (3.3-8.7)	2.8 (1.6-4.6)	3.9 (2.6-6)
FR-BPE	0 (0-35.4)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	5.4 (2.3-12.1)	4.3 (1.7-10.7)	2.1 (1.3-3.2)	1.3 (0.8-2.3)
ES-FISABIO	0.7 (0.4-1.5)	0.5 (0.2-1.2)	0 (0-0.4)	0.5 (0.2-1.2)	0.3 (0.1-0.7)	0.6 (0.3-1.2)
ES_IACS	0 (0-1.8)	2.4 (1-5.4)	0.4 (0.1-2)	0.7 (0.2-2.5)	0.9 (0.3-2.2)	1.9 (1-3.7)
NO-UIO	0.9 (0.2-3.1)	0.4 (0.1-2.4)	0 (0-1)	0 (0-1)	0.5 (0.1-1.6)	0 (0-0.9)

Table 19 Prevalence of glucocorticoids prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (hospitalized cases)

DAP	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)
IT-ARS	11.1 (2-43.5)	33.3 (12.1-64.6)	0 (0-18.4)	23.5 (9.6-47.3)	2.8 (1-8)	9.4 (5.2-16.5)
FR-BPE	0 (0-35.4)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	5.4 (2.3-12.1)	4.3 (1.7-10.7)	3.6 (1.8-6.9)	3.1 (1.5-6.3)
ES-FISABIO	0 (0-39)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-4.5)	1.2 (0.2-6.6)
ES_IACS	0 (0-24.2)	16.7 (4.7-44.8)	0 (0-17.6)	5.6 (1-25.8)	0 (0-4.9)	9.5 (4.7-18.3)
NO-UIO	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-9)	0 (0-9)	0 (0-3.6)	0 (0-3.6)

8.2.4 Antiviral medicines (J05)

There was minimal use of antivirals (J05) in the pregnancy cohort with COVID-19 (less than 2% in most DAPS, and therefore not presented in these tables).

Examination at the substance level (see Additional files) showed almost zero prevalence of the use of remdesivir, lopinavir-ritonavir, oseltamivir, ribavirin and favipiravir, either before or after COVID-19 infection.

8.2.5 Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)

Use of medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03) was low in all DAPS. Any increases seen following COVID-19 infection were small and did not exceed xx% across all trimesters and all DAPS, except for FISABIO-HSRU, where there was a slight increase of the order of 1-2% following COVID-19 infection (in all trimesters).

8.2.6 Hydroxychloroquine (P01BA02)

There was almost no usage of hydroxychloroquine observed in the pregnant cohort. See Table 20 and Table 21.

Table 20 Prevalence of hydroxychloroquine (P01BA02) prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (all cases)

	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-i	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
DAP	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
IT-ARS	0 (0-1.8)	0.5 (0.1-2.7)	0 (0-1.4)	0.4 (0.1-2)	0 (0-0.8)	0 (0-0.8)
FR-BPE	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-4)	0 (0-4)	0 (0-0.4)	0 (0-0.4)
ES-FISABIO	0 (0-0.4)	0.1 (0-0.6)	0 (0-0.4)	0 (0-0.4)	0 (0-0.3)	0 (0-0.3)
ES_IACS	0 (0-1.8)	0 (0-1.8)	0 (0-1.3)	0 (0-1.3)	0.2 (0-1.2)	0.2 (0-1.2)
NO-UIO	0 (0-1.6)	0 (0-1.6)	0 (0-1)	0 (0-1)	0.2 (0-1.3)	0.2 (0-1.3)

Table 21 Prevalence of hydroxychloroquine (P01BA02) prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (hospitalized cases)

	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
DAP	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
IT-ARS	0 (0-29.9)	0 (0-29.9)	0 (0-18.4)	0 (0-18.4)	0 (0-3.5)	0 (0-3.5)
FR-BPE	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-4)	0 (0-4)	0 (0-1.7)	0 (0-1.7)
ES-FISABIO	0 (0-39)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-4.5)	0 (0-4.5)
ES_IACS	0 (0-24.2)	0 (0-24.2)	0 (0-17.6)	0 (0-17.6)	1.4 (0.2-7.3)	1.4 (0.2-7.3)
NO-UIO	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-9)	0 (0-9)	0 (0-3.6)	0 (0-3.6)

8.3 Prevalence of medication use in the matched cohorts of pregnant women with and without COVID-19 in pregnancy

8.3.1 Description of the baseline characteristics

The baseline characteristics of the matched cohorts are presented in Annex 7. Tables are provided separately for each DAP, and for the trimester of pregnancy when COVID-19 was diagnosed. The characteristics of the cohort of pregnant women with COVID-19 are stratified by level of severity. Within the cohort of COVID-19 positive pregnant people, baseline risk factors for COVID-19 hospitalization and obstetric risk are compared between hospitalized and non-hospitalized pregnant cases using standardized differences, allowing to inspect whether baseline characteristics impact on COVID-19 disease severity (objective 2). There was no evidence to show that women who were hospitalized with COVID-19 (defined as hospitalized by definition) had a higher prevalence of co-morbidities those without an admission).

Table 22 presents the severity of COVID-19 among pregnant women in the matched cohort. The majority of cases in pregnancy trimester 1 and trimester 2 were non-hospitalized (80-90%). In trimester 3, cases were more likely to be ‘quarantined’ i.e. classified as hospitalized if a COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis occurred within 2 days of delivery. For example, among those with a pregnancy trimester 3 COVID-19 episode in ARS, 21% had their positive test/ diagnosis recorded within 2 days of delivery; the corresponding figure in FISABIO-HSRU was 29.0%. As BPE did not have access to COVID-19 positive test results, its cohort of pregnant women with COVID-19 was identified based on admission to hospital with a COVID-19 diagnosis, this was mostly in trimester 3 and 76.5% was quarantined since COVID-19 was detected within 2 days of delivery. Hence the patterns differ from those seen with other DAPS.

Table 22 Details of the severity of COVID-19 disease among pregnant women in the matched cohort

	Total cases		Hospitalized cases		Non-hospitalized cases		Quarantined cases ¹	
	N		N	%	N	%	N	%
IT-ARS								
Trimester 1	201		<10	3.5%	177	88.1%	17	8.5%
Trimester 2	273		17	6.2%	256	93.8%	0	0.0%
Trimester 3	508		106	20.9%	296	58.3%	106	20.9%
FR-BPE								
Trimester 1	<10		<10	100.0%	no records	no records	0	0.0%
Trimester 2	85		85	100.0%	no records	no records	0	0.0%
Trimester 3	926		218	23.5%	no records	no records	708	76.5%
ES-FISABIO								
Trimester 1	940		<10	0.6%	914	97.2%	20	2.1%
Trimester 2	856		13	1.5%	839	98.0%	<10	0.5%
Trimester 3	1181		82	6.9%	756	64.0%	343	29.0%
ES-IACS								
Trimester 1	182		<10	3.3%	171	94.0%	<10	2.7%
Trimester 2	261		16	6.1%	245	93.9%	0	0.0%
Trimester 3	431		68	15.8%	197	45.7%	166	38.5%
WA-SWANSEA								
Trimester 1	567		21	3.7%	546	96.3%	0	0.0%
Trimester 2	626		35	5.6%	590	94.2%	<10	<1.0%
Trimester 3	726		142	19.6%	487	67.1%	97	13.4%
NO-UIO								
Trimester 1	230		13	5.7%	217	94.3%	0	0.0%
Trimester 2	398		39	9.8%	359	90.2%	0	0.0%
Trimester 3	443		104	23.5%	301	67.9%	38	8.6%

Notes:

¹ Cases in which the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date hospitalized did not contribute to analyses by hospitalization. They did however contribute to the analyses undertaken on ‘total cases’.

8.3.2 Prevalence of medication use

The results of the analyses of prevalence of medication use in the matched cohort are presented in Annex 8. As with Section 8.2, in the interest of making the tables more interpretable, results have

been suppressed to present only those rows with a minimum prevalence of 2% in any of the cells in that row. The full tables are provided as Additional file 2.

Tables are provided separately for each DAP, and for each trimester of pregnancy when the infection occurred. Within each table, prevalence estimates of the cohort of pregnant women with COVID-19 are stratified by level of COVID-19 severity. Estimates are presented for the 30 days before the COVID-19 date, and for the 30 days after this date. Results are presented at the ATC-2 level.

While the tables are similar to those in Section 8.2 (all pregnancies with a COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis in pregnancy), there are important differences to enable further interpretation of the findings. Results are presented in separate tables for the trimester of pregnancy when the positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis occurred. Within each table the prevalence estimate among total cases, hospitalized cases and non-hospitalized cases can then be compared with the estimate among matched comparator group.

8.3.2.1 Medicines use in pregnancy trimester 1

Antithrombotic medicines (B01)

In the matched comparator cohort of pregnant women without COVID-19, rates of antithrombotic use during a 30 days period were of the order of 2 - 4% across all DAPS. These values were consistent with the prevalence in the pre-COVID-19 window of total cases and those cases classed as non-hospitalized. The numbers of cases in trimester 1 classed as hospitalized were too low to provide accurate rate of antithrombotic use in the pre-COVID-19 window.

Across the majority of DAPS, there was a substantial increase in use of antithrombotic medicines after COVID-19 diagnosis/test in the first trimester. For example, in ARS (Italy) the 30-day prevalence rate (among all cases) increased from 3.9% (2-7.4) to 12.6% (8.7-17.8), while in FISABIO-HSRU (Spain) it increased from 2.3% (1.5-3.5) to 31% (28.2-34.1). In contrast there was no increase seen in the use of antithrombotic medicines in UIO, with prevalence estimate remaining unchanged at 1.7% (0.7-4.4). Among COVID-19 disease classed as hospitalized, prevalence estimates were more unstable given the small numbers and increases in prevalence after COVID-19 diagnosis though large, should be interpreted with caution.

Antibacterial medicines (J01)

In the matched comparator of pregnant women without COVID-19, the 30- days prevalence rate of antibacterial use were of the order of 2 - 3% across all DAPS. Within DAPS, prevalence estimates among total cases were marginally higher in the in the 30-day window prior to COVID-19 window than that observed among matched controls. Increases in the 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis were small in magnitude.

Corticosteroids for systemic use (H02)

The 30-day prevalence of use of systemic corticosteroids was low in the matched comparator group of pregnant women without COVID-19; less than 2% in all DAPs. Similar prevalence estimates were seen in the pre-COVID-19 window in the cases. Across DAPS, increases in 30-day prevalence of corticosteroid use after COVID-19 infection were inconsistent and more likely to be observed among hospitalized cases, where estimates were based on a small number of subjects.

8.3.2.2 Medicines use in pregnancy trimester 2

Antithrombotic medicines (B01)

In the matched comparator cohort of pregnant women without COVID-19, 30-day prevalence rates of antithrombotic use were of the order of 2 - 4%, which were consistent with the prevalence in the pre-COVID-19 window of total cases (and those classed as non-hospitalized). A clear exception to this was IACS (Spain) where among pregnancy trimester 2 infections, prevalence of antithrombotic use in the 30 days pre-COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis was considerably greater than that observed in the matched comparator group.³

There was a substantial increase in use of antithrombotic medicines in the 30-day window following COVID-19 positive test /diagnosis. This was most pronounced in FISABIO-HSRU (Spain) where prevalence among all cases increased from 4.4% (3.3-6) in the 30 days prior to COVID-diagnosis/test to 50.7% (47.4-54) in the 30 days after and from 7.7% (1.4-33.3) to 61.5% (35.5-82.3) in those classed as hospitalized COVID cases. Similarly, in ARS (Italy), there was an increase in the 30-days prevalence from 4.3% (2.5-7.4) to 16.6% (12.7-21.4) in total cases (pre-post) and from 5.9% (1-27) to 47.1% (26.2-69) in those classed as hospitalized. Among total cases in IACS (Spain) prevalence of use of antithrombotic medicines in the second semester increased from 17.9% to 37.5%.

In UIO (Norway) there was no increase in the 30-day prevalence of antithrombotic use following COVID-19 diagnosis/positive test in the 2nd trimester. Among pregnancies with hospitalized COVID-19 in the second trimester of pregnancy, the 30-day prevalence of antithrombotic use before vs after COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis was 2.6% (0.5-13.2) vs 17.9% (9-32.7), respectively, suggesting a 6.9-fold increase. However, the estimates were based on small number of individuals using antithrombotic medicines.

³ It is probable that this anomaly is caused by a delay of 1-2 days in the registering of a positive COVID-19 test result in the surveillance system.

Antibacterial medicines (J01)

In the matched comparator group of pregnant women without coCOVID-19, the 30-day prevalence rates of antibacterial medicines use were of the order of 3-5% across all DAPs. Prevalence estimates among total cases were marginally higher than this in the 30 days prior to COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, but these differences were small in magnitude. In BPE (France) which did not have a matched comparator group since COVID-19 could only be identified upon hospitalization, the rates of antibacterial use in the 30 days prior to COVID-19 diagnosis were considerably higher (19.6% (12.7-28.8)) than that observed in other DAPS. Across DAPS, there was no increase in the 30-day prevalence of use of antibacterial medicines following COVID-19 diagnosis /test as compared to the 30 days prior.

Corticosteroids for systemic use (H02)

Use of systemic corticosteroids was low in the matched comparator group of pregnant women without COVID-19; less than 2% in all DAPS. Similar prevalence estimates were seen in the pre-COVID-19 30-day window in the cases. Across all DAPS, there was increase in prevalence of corticosteroid use after COVID-19 infection in the 2nd trimester were inconsistent and more likely to be observed among hospitalized cases; similar to that seen in trimester 1.

8.3.2.3 Medicines use in pregnancy trimester 3

Antithrombotic medicines (B01)

In the matched comparator cohort of pregnant women without COVID-19, 30-day prevalence rates of antithrombotic medicines use were marginally higher than seen in trimester 2 (approx. 2-6%). These figures were consistent with the 30-day prevalence estimates in the pre-COVID-19 window of total cases (as well as those classed as non-hospitalized). Again, a clear exception to this was IACS where prevalence of use among the cases in the 30 days preceding COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis was considerably greater than in the matched group.

Similar to patterns seen in the other trimester's infection, there was an increase in the use of antithrombotic medicines in the 30-day window following COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis. This was seen in all DAPS, including UIO which did not see an increase in the use of antithrombotic medicines in trimester 1 or trimester 2 infections. The increase seen among hospitalized COVID-19 cases was remarkable across DAPS. The increase was most pronounced in FISABIO-HSRU (Spain) and ARS (Italy). In FISABIO-HSRU (Spain), 61% of total cases and 74% of COVID-19 cases of in the 3rd pregnancy trimesters classed as hospitalized had a record of dispensed antithrombotic medicines in the 30 days post COVID-19 infection.

Antibacterial medicines (J01)

In the majority of DAPS there was no increase in the use of antibacterial medicines in the 30-day window after COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis as compared to the 30-day pre diagnosis period. In contrast, in BPE (France), 30-day prevalence increased from 6.6% (5.2-8.3) to 17.8% (15.6-

20.4) among total cases and from 7.6% (4.8-11.8) to 23.7% (18.6-29.6) in those classed as hospitalized. It is important to reiterate that the cohort of pregnant women with COVID-19 in BPE consisted of women who had an admission to hospital with a COVID-19 diagnosis as this DAP did not have access to COVID-19 test results in the community.

Corticosteroids for systemic use (H02)

As with earlier pregnancy trimesters, use of systemic corticosteroids was low in the matched comparator group of pregnant women without COVID-19; less than 2% in all DAPS. Similar prevalence estimates were seen in the pre-COVID-19 window in the COVID-19 positive pregnant cases. Across all DAPS, there was no consistent increase in prevalence of medication use after COVID-19 infection, and increases were observed among hospitalized cases, similar to the results seen among infections in other trimesters.

8.4 Prevalence of medication use in the matched cohort of pregnant women with COVID-19 and non-pregnant women with COVID-19

8.4.1 Description of the baseline characteristics

The baseline characteristics of the two cohorts are presented in Annex 9. Tables are provided separately for each DAP, and for the trimester of pregnancy when the diagnosis occurred. Within each table, the characteristics of the two cohorts are presented side by side to facilitate comparison. The characteristics are stratified by level of severity. Furthermore, the baseline risk factors for hospitalized COVID-19 and obstetric risk are compared between hospitalized and non-hospitalized cases using standardized differences.

In contrast with the cohort of pregnant women who had a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis during pregnancy, there were clear difference in the baseline characteristics of hospitalized and non-hospitalized non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis. Those classed as hospitalized (i.e. had a hospital diagnosis for COVID-19), had considerably greater prevalence of co-morbidities associated with severe COVID-19 disease, that in those in the non-hospitalized group. In the pregnant cohort, baseline risk of hospitalized COVID-19 was similar between the two groups.

8.4.2 Prevalence of medication use

The results of the analyses of prevalence of medication use in the matched cohort are presented in Additional file 3. Again, tables are provided separately for each DAP, and for each trimester of pregnancy when the diagnosis/positive test occurred. To make the tables more interpretable they are split by severity of COVID-19 disease; total COVID-19 cases in the first table; hospitalized

and non-hospitalized cases in the second. Estimates are presented separately for the 30-day window pre- and the 30-day window post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis.

Across total COVID-19 cases in the non-pregnant matched cohort of women of childbearing age, few medicines experienced an increase in use in the 30-day window following COVID-19 infection. However, interesting patterns emerge when one looks at the comparison between hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases of COVID-19 infection.

Antithrombotic medicines (B02)

Prevalence of antithrombotic medicines use in the matched non-pregnant comparator cohort with a COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis was low, and considerably lower than in the matched cohort of pregnant with COVID-19. Across the majority of DAPS there was no increase seen in the use of antithrombotic medicines in contrast with large increases in prevalence rates in the pregnant cohort with COVID-19 disease. However, among non-pregnant comparators classed as having hospitalized cases of COVID-19, there was an increase in the use of this drug class, though again prevalence estimates, and the increases seen were considerably lower than that seen in the pregnant cases. For example, in ARS (Italy) among the pregnancy trimester 3 matched non-pregnant COVID-19 positive comparator group, 30-day prevalence of antithrombotic use increased from 0.9% (0.5-1.5) to 3.7% (2.9-4.8) compared with 4.9% (3.4-7.2) to 29.5% (25.7-33.6) among pregnant cases. Among those classed as hospitalized, the 30-day prevalence changed from 3.0% (1-17) to 28.0% (15-46) compared with changes of the order 11.3% (6.6-18.8) to 50% (40.6-59.4) among cases.

Antibacterials (J01)

There were mixed patterns among this drug class, in terms of the 30-day prevalence of its use in the pre-COVID-19 window, changes seen after COVID-19 diagnosis, and how these compared with the patterns seen in the pregnant cases. Overall, there was a slightly higher use of this drug class in the matched COVID-19 positive non-pregnant control cohort than in the pregnant cases, and more examples of increased use after COVID-19 diagnosis, in contrast with the pregnant cases where use of this class did not markedly increase.

8.5 Adverse pregnancy and maternal outcomes

8.5.1 Prevalence of adverse maternal and pregnancy outcomes in pregnant women in the pre-pandemic era

The prevalence of adverse maternal and pregnancy outcomes was examined in a pre-pandemic group of women who were 12-55 years of age at their start of pregnancy and whose pregnancy commenced from 01.01.2018 and was completed prior to 01.01.2020.

Pregnancies included in the denominator of each prevalence estimate differed by outcome: maternal death, spontaneous abortion, and caesarean section were reported as a prevalence of all pregnancies; pre-term birth, neonatal death, low birth weight, low APGAR score, major congenital anomalies and microcephaly for live births; gestational diabetes, pre-eclampsia (including eclampsia & HELLP) for pregnancies that reached at least 20 gestational weeks; and stillbirth for pregnancies that reached at least 22 gestational weeks.

The prevalence estimates across all Data Access Providers are presented in Table 23.

Not all DAPS provided date for each outcome. This was influenced by local governance restrictions, as well as access to data required to estimate these.

Table 23 Prevalence rates of adverse pregnancy and neonatal outcomes among pregnant women in the pre-pandemic period (2018-2019)

	Aarhus	ARS (Italy)	BPE (France)	IACS (Spain)	FISABIO-HSRU (Spain)*	SWANSEA (Wales)	UiO (Norway)
Outcome		% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Total pregnancies, n	78,201	42,834	133,967	14,633	67,415	39,640	66,286
Maternal death	NA	0.007 (0.002-0.022)	0.001 (0-0.005)	0 (0-0.033)	0.001 (0-0.01)	0 (0-0.012)	NA
Gestational diabetes	4.4 (4.2-4.5)	8.3 (8.0-8.6)	13.2 (13.0-13.4)	11.1 (10.5-11.7)	7.8 (7.5-8.0)	4.2 (4.0-4.4)	5.2 (5.0-5.4)
Pre-eclampsia	2.7(2.6-2.9)	2.9(2.7-3.1)	2.9 (2.8-3.1)	3.2 (2.9-3.5)	1.7 (1.6-1.8)	1.2 (1.1-1.3)	2.7 (2.6-2.8)
Spontaneous abortion	8.7 (8.5-8.9)	14.2(13.9-14.5)	8.8 (8.6-8.9)	10.5 (10.0-11.0)	16.8 (16.5-17.0)	NA	NA
Caesarean section	15.0 (14.8-15.3)	17.2 (16.9-17.6)	15.3 (15.1-15.5)	NA	9.6 (9.4-9.8)	NA	NA
Pre-term birth	5.4 (5.2-5.6)	7.0 (6.7-7.3)	11.0 (10.8-11.2)	6.2 (5.8-6.6)	6.5 (6.3-6.8)	7.8 (7.5-8.1)	5.9 (5.7-6.0)
Stillbirth	0.3 (0.3-0.4)	0.3 (0.3-0.4)	NA	0.4 (0.3-0.6)	0.5 (0.4-0.5)	0.5 (0.4-0.6)	0.3 (0.3-0.4)
Neonatal death	0.275 (0.236-0.321)	0 (0-0.018)	NA	0.07 (0.03-0.14)	0.04 (0.02-0.06)	NA	NA
Low birth weight	NA	8.7 (8.3-9.0)	NA	6.4 (6-6.9)	7.7 (7.5-7.9)	NA	4.8 (4.6-5.0)
SGA/IUGR	7.9 (7.7-8.1)	4.1 (3.9-4.4)	NA	1.7 (1.5-1.9)	NA	NA	8.7 (8.5-8.9)
Low Apgar (0-3 at 5 minutes)	NA	0.2(0.2-0.3)	NA	0.1 (0.1-0.2)	NA	0.4 (0.4-0.5)	0.2 (0.2-0.2)
Major congenital anomalies	NA	4.7 (4.7-5.0)	NA	NA	NA	NA	3.9 (3.7-4.0)
Microcephaly	NA	0.04 (0.02-0.08)	NA	0.09 (0.04-0.16)	NA	NA	NA

Notes:

1. In Aarhus University (Denmark), results are based on a cohort of pregnancies ending between 01.01.2018 and 31.12.2018
 2. When SGA is extracted from the birth registry (UiO, Aarhus University), the raw z-score is computed based on gestational age-specific and sex-specific weight distribution of live borns. SGA is defined as a z-score below -1.282 (below the 10th percentile). Other DAPs use a diagnostic code which is likely an underestimate of the prevalence of this outcome.
 3. In BPE, there was incomplete linkage of neonates to the pregnancy, hence neonatal outcomes were not reported for this DAP.
- * Results in FISABIO-HSRU for this table are currently undergoing re-checking.

Abbreviations: NA: not available; IUGR; Intrauterine growth restriction. SGA: Small-for-gestational age.

8.5.2 Prevalence of adverse maternal and pregnancy outcomes in a matched cohort of pregnant women with and without COVID-19 in pregnancy

The prevalence of adverse pregnancy and neonatal outcomes and association with COVID-19 in pregnancy is presented in the following tables. Results are stratified by the trimester of pregnancy when the infection took place and severity of infection.

8.5.2.1 Gestational diabetes

There was no evidence to suggest that a COVID-19 positive test/ diagnosis in trimester 1 of pregnancy was associated with an increased risk of gestational diabetes.

Table 24 Prevalence of gestational diabetes (GDM) and its association with COVID-19 infection in pregnancy trimester 1 (by severity of COVID-19 disease)

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group
IT-ARS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	151	<10	149	603
Prevalence % (95% CI)	11.3 (6.9-17.7)	50.0 (9.5-90.5)	10.7 (6.5-17.1)	8.0 (6-10.5)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.11 (0.66-1.86)	5.34 (1.28-22.27)	1.05 (0.62-1.79)	reference
FR-BPE				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	<10	<10	NA	NA
Prevalence % (95% CI)	33.3 (6-75.9)	33.3 (6-75.9)	NA	NA
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	NA	NA	NA	NA
ES-FISABIO-HSRU				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	806	<10	802	2,820
Prevalence % (95% CI)	7.9 (6.2-10.1)	25 (1.3-78.1)	7.9 (6.1-10)	6.2 (5.4-7.2)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.0 (0.75-1.31)	3.85 (0.7-21.2)	0.98 (0.74-1.3)	reference
ES-IACS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	157	<10	151	546
Prevalence % (95% CI)	11.5 (7.1-17.8)	16.7 (0.9-63.5)	11.3 (6.9-17.7)	13.4 (10.7-16.6)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.76 (0.47-1.23)	1.21 (0.2-7.26)	0.74 (0.46-1.22)	reference
NO-UIO				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	229	13	216	690
Prevalence % (95% CI)	7.0 (4.2-11.3)	7.7 (0.4-37.9)	6.9 (4.1-11.4)	5.9 (4.3-8.0)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.31 (0.75-2.28)	1.37 (0.19-9.71)	1.31 (0.74-2.3)	reference

Notes:

1. Analyses restricted to pregnancies that reached at least 20 weeks of gestation.
2. Because the operational definition of GDM is any outcome occurrence from start of second trimester, only exposure to COVID-19 in the first trimester was investigated.
3. Matched comparator group were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they had a pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.
4. Estimates adjusted for age; presence of at least one condition increasing the risk of hospitalized COVID-19; presence of least one obstetric risk.
5. BPE did not have a matched comparator cohort of pregnant women without COVID-19, as they did not have access to COVID-19 positive test results in the community, hence there is no risk estimate presented. Furthermore, as they only had access to inpatient data with ICD10 codes of COVID-diagnoses only, all episodes of COVID-19 identified in their data were classed as hospitalized (with the caveat that those diagnoses within 2 days of delivery were not included in this classification, in a similar manner to other DAPS). As the numbers of women with a COVID-19 positive test /diagnosis in the first and second trimester were very low, the prevalence estimates are imprecise

8.5.2.2 Pre-eclampsia

There was no evidence to suggest that a COVID-19 positive test/ diagnosis in trimester 1 of pregnancy was not associated with an increased risk of pre-eclampsia.

Table 25 Prevalence of pre-eclampsia and its association with COVID-19 infection in pregnancy trimester 1 (by severity of COVID-19 disease)

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group
IT-ARS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	151	<10	149	603
Prevalence % (95% CI)	2.6 (0.9-7.1)	0 (0-80.2)	2.7 (0.9-7.2)	1.7 (0.8-3.1)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.17 (0.39-3.54)	0 (0-0)	1.18 (0.39-3.57)	reference
FR-BPE				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	<10	<10	NA	NA
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-48.3)	0 (0-48.3)	NA	NA
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	NA	NA	NA	NA
ES-FISABIO-HSRU				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	806	<10	802	2,820
Prevalence % (95% CI)	1.1 (0.5-2.2)	25.0(1.3-78.1)	1 (0.5-2)	1.0 (0.6-1.4)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.94 (0.44-2.01)	25.09 (4.31-145.97)	0.84 (0.38-1.84)	reference
ES-IACS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	157	<10	151	546
Prevalence % (95% CI)	1.9 (0.5-5.9)	16.7 (0.9-63.5)	1.3 (0.2-5.2)	2.7 (1.6-4.6)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.6 (0.17-2.07)	4.61 (0.64-33.22)	0.42 (0.1-1.82)	reference
NO-UIO				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	229	13	216	690
Prevalence % (95% CI)	1.7 (0.6-4.7)	0 (0-28.3)	1.9 (0.6-5)	2.9 (1.8-4.5)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.63 (0.21-1.82)	0 (0-0)	0.66 (0.23-1.92)	reference

Notes:

1. Analyses restricted to pregnancies that reached at least 20 weeks of gestation.
2. Because the operational definition of pre-eclampsia is any outcome occurrence from start of second trimester, only exposure to COVID-19 in the first trimester was investigated.
3. Matched comparator group were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they had a pseudo trimester of pregnancy when infection occurred, but no severity of infection.
4. Estimates adjusted for age; presence of at least one condition increasing the risk of hospitalized COVID-19; presence of least one obstetric risk condition.
5. BPE did not have a matched comparator cohort of pregnant women without COVID-19, as they did not have access to COVID-19 positive test results in the community, hence there is no risk estimate presented. Furthermore, as they only had access to inpatient data with ICD10 codes of COVID-diagnoses only, all episodes of COVID-19 identified in their data were classed as hospitalized (with the caveat that those diagnoses within 2 days of delivery were not included in this classification, in a similar manner to other DAPS). As the numbers of women with a COVID-19 positive test /diagnosis in the first and second trimester were very low, prevalence estimates are imprecise.

8.5.2.3 Maternal death

There were no maternal deaths observed in the pregnant cohort with COVID-19 or the comparator group without COVID-19.

Table 26 Prevalence of maternal death and its association with COVID-19 infection (by pregnancy trimester and severity of COVID-19 disease)

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group.
IT-ARS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	201	<10	177	603
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-2.338)	0 (0-43.907)	0 (0-2.648)	0 (0-0.789)
Trimester 2				
Trimester 2 diagnosis	273	17	256	819
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-1.73)	0 (0-22.922)	0 (0-1.843)	0 (0-0.582)
Trimester 3				
Trimester 3 diagnosis	508	106	296	1,524
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-0.936)	0 (0-4.358)	0 (0-1.597)	0 (0-0.313)
FR-BPE				
Trimester 1				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	<10	<10	NA	NA
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-48.318)	0 (0-48.318)	NA	NA
Trimester 2				
Trimester 2 diagnosis	85	85	NA	NA
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-5.388)	0 (0-5.388)	NA	NA
Trimester 3				
Trimester 3 diagnosis	954	218	NA	NA
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-0.500)	0 (0-2.158)	NA	NA
ES-FISABIO-HSRU				
Trimester 1				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	940	<10	914	2,820
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-0.507)	0 (0-48.318)	0 (0-0.522)	0 (0-0.17)
Trimester 2				
Trimester 2 diagnosis	856	13	839	2,568
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-0.557)	0 (0-28.344)	0 (0-0.568)	0 (0-0.186)
Trimester 3				
Trimester 3 diagnosis	1,181	82	756	3,543
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-0.404)	0 (0-5.576)	0 (0-0.63)	0 (0-0.135)
ES-IACS				
Trimester 1				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	182	<10	171	546
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-2.576)	0 (0-48.318)	0 (0-2.739)	0 (0-0.871)
Trimester 2				
Trimester 2 diagnosis	261	16	245	783
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-1.808)	0 (0-24.074)	0 (0-1.924)	0 (0-0.609)
Trimester 3				
Trimester 3 diagnosis	431	68	197	1,293
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-1.101)	0 (0-6.662)	0 (0-2.384)	0 (0-0.369)

Notes:

1. All pregnancies included in the analyses.
2. Matched comparator group were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they had a pseudo trimester of pregnancy when

infection occurred, but no severity of infection.

3. No modelling due to small numbers. 4. BPE did not have a matched comparator cohort of pregnant women without COVID-19, as they did not have access to COVID-19 positive test results in the community.

4. BPE did not have a matched comparator cohort of pregnant women without COVID-19, as they did not have access to COVID-19 positive test results in the community, hence there is no risk estimate presented. Furthermore, as they only had access to inpatient data with ICD10 codes of COVID-diagnoses only, all episodes of COVID-19 identified in their data were classed as hospitalized (with the caveat that those diagnoses within 2 days of delivery were not included in this classification, in a similar manner to other DAPS). As the numbers of women with a COVID-19 positive test /diagnosis in the first and second trimester were very low, prevalence estimates are imprecise.

8.5.2.4 Spontaneous abortion

Results are being re-analyzed as errors were detected in the modelling. These data will be included in the meta-analyses, if available.

Table 27 Prevalence of spontaneous abortion and its association with COVID-19 diagnosis (by pregnancy trimester and severity of COVID-19 disease) – see meta-analysis.

8.5.2.5 Cesarean section

There were mixed results for the association of a COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis during pregnancy and caesarean section.

In ARS, women with a COVID-19 positive test/ diagnosis in trimester 2 were 50% more likely to have a cesarean section than those in the matched comparator group (aRR: 1.51 (1.18-1.94)). Those with a positive test /diagnosis in trimester 3 had a 29% increased risk (aRR: 1.29 (1.06-1.57)). In FISABIO-HSRU, those with a diagnosis in trimester 3, had a 26% elevated risk (1.26 (1.06-1.49)); the increased risk in trimester 2 was not significant. In this DAP, the risk of caesarean section was much more pronounced in the hospitalized group: trimester 2 (aRR: 3.66 (1.91-7.03)) and trimester 3 (aRR: 2.69 (1.91-3.79)) respectively, than that observed in ARS.

BPE did not have a comparator group of pregnant women without COVID-19, but among women classed as having a hospitalized infection in trimester 3, rates of caesarean section were almost twice those observed among women having a hospitalized infection in trimester 2 (31.7% (25.6-38.3) vs. 18.8 (11.5-29.1)).

Table 28 Prevalence of caesarean section and its association with COVID-19 diagnosis (by pregnancy trimester and severity of COVID-19 disease)

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group.
IT-ARS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	201	<10	177	603
Prevalence % (95% CI)	15.9 (11.3-21.9)	0 (0-43.9)	18.1 (12.9-24.7)	16.3 (13.4-19.5)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.98 (0.68-1.41)	0 (0-0)	1.12 (0.78-1.6)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis	273	17	256	819
Prevalence % (95% CI)	26.4 (21.3-32.1)	17.6 (4.7-44.2)	27 (21.7-32.9)	17.5 (15-20.3)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.51 (1.18-1.94)	1.01 (0.36-2.85)	1.55 (1.2-1.99)	reference

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group.
Trimester 3 diagnosis	508	106	296	1,524
Prevalence % (95% CI)	22.2 (18.8-26.2)	23.6 (16.1-33)	21.3 (16.9-26.5)	17.4 (15.5-19.4)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.29 (1.06-1.57)	1.37 (0.96-1.96)	1.24 (0.97-1.59)	reference
FR-BPE				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	<10	<10	NA	NA
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-48.3)	0 (0-48.3)	NA	NA
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Trimester 2 diagnosis	85	85	NA	NA
Prevalence % (95% CI)	18.8 (11.5-29.1)	18.8 (11.5-29.1)	NA	NA
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Trimester 3 diagnosis	954	218	NA	NA
Prevalence % (95% CI)	24.9 (22.3-27.8)	31.7 (25.6-38.3)	NA	NA
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	NA	NA	NA	NA
ES-FISABIO-HSRU				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	940	<10	914	2,820
Prevalence % (95% CI)	9.3 (7.5-11.3)	50.0 (18.8-81.2)	9.2 (7.4-11.3)	9.4 (8.4-10.6)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.99 (0.78-1.24)	5.39 (2.39-12.13)	0.98 (0.77-1.24)	
Trimester 2 diagnosis	856	13	839	2,568
Prevalence % (95% CI)	11.8 (9.8-14.2)	38.5 (15.1-67.7)	11.3 (9.3-13.7)	10.1 (9-11.3)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.16 (0.94-1.45)	3.66 (1.91-7.03)	1.12 (0.9-1.4)	reference
Trimester 3 diagnosis	1181	82	756	3,543
Prevalence % (95% CI)	14.2 (12.3-16.4)	30.5 (21.1-41.8)	12.6 (10.3-15.2)	11.3 (10.2-12.4)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.26 (1.06-1.49)	2.69 (1.91-3.79)	1.11 (0.9-1.37)	reference

Notes:

1. All pregnancies included in the analyses.
2. Matched comparator group were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they had a pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.
3. Estimates adjusted for age; presence of at least one condition increasing the risk of hospitalized COVID-19; presence of at least one obstetric risk condition.
4. BPE did not have a matched comparator cohort of pregnant women without COVID-19, as they did not have access to COVID-19 positive test results in the community, hence there is no risk estimate presented. Furthermore, as they only had access to inpatient data with ICD10 codes of COVID-diagnoses only, all episodes of COVID-19 identified in their data were classed as hospitalized (with the caveat that those diagnoses within 2 days of delivery were not included in this classification). As the numbers of women with a positive test /diagnosis in the first and second trimester were very low, prevalence estimates are imprecise.

8.5.2.6 Pre-term birth

There were mixed results for the association of a COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis during pregnancy and pre-term birth.

There was no association between a COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis in the first or second trimester and pre-term birth in any of the DAPS. The numbers classed as hospitalized in trimester

1 and trimester 2 were low and the non-significant risk estimates which tended to show an increased association with a hospitalized infection in trimester 2, were accompanied by wide confidence intervals.

A positive test/diagnosis in trimester 3 was associated with an increased risk (across all cases) in ARS, and FISABIO-HSRU, and was more pronounced in the hospitalized group (ARS - aRR: 3.95 (95% CI: 2.06-7.59)) and (FISABIO-HSRU – aRR: 2.63 (95% CI: 1.39-4.96)). In IACS, it was only in the hospitalized group that the elevated risk was significant. In ARS, FISABIO-HSRU and IACS respectively the prevalence of pre-term births among women classed as having a hospitalized COVID-19 infection in trimester 3 was 20.5%, 19.0% and 18.8%. The corresponding prevalence in the respective comparator groups was 5.0%, 7.2%, and 5.7%.

In UIO Norway, there was no association between COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis in any trimester and increased risk of pre-term birth.

Table 29 Prevalence of preterm birth and its association with COVID-19 diagnosis (by pregnancy trimester and severity of COVID-19 disease)

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group.
IT-ARS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	133	<10	132	435
Prevalence % (95% CI)	5.3 (2.3-10.9)	0 (0-94.5)	5.6 (2.9-11.0)	6.7 (4.6-9.5)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.79 (0.36-1.75)	0 (0-0)	0.79 (0.36-1.76)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis	252	16	236	593
Prevalence % (95% CI)	5.2 (2.0-8.9)	12.5 (2.2-39.6)	4.7 (2.5-8.4)	6.9 (5.1-9.3)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.74 (0.4-1.35)	1.8 (0.47-6.94)	0.66 (0.35-1.27)	reference
Trimester 3 diagnosis	250	44	191	1092
Prevalence % (95% CI)	10.8 (7.4-15.5)	20.5 (10.3-35.8)	4.7 (2.4-9.0)	5.0 (3.8-6.5)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	2.12 (1.36-3.29)	3.95 (2.06-7.59)	0.61 (0.3-1.22)	reference
FR-BPE				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	<10	<10	NA	NA
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-48.3)	0 (0-48.3)	NA	NA
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Trimester 2 diagnosis	85	85	NA	NA
Prevalence % (95% CI)	8.2 (3.7-16.8)	8.2 (3.7-16.8)	NA	NA
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Trimester 3 diagnosis	155	130	NA	NA
Prevalence % (95% CI)	25.2 (18.7-32.9)	10.8 (6.2-17.7)	NA	NA
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	NA	NA	NA	NA
ES-FISABIO-HSRU				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	796	<10	792	2,294

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group.
Prevalence % (95% CI)	7.3 (5.6-9.4)	0 (0-60.4)	7.3 (5.7-9.4)	6.8 (5.9-8)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.05 (0.78-1.41)	0 (0-0)	1.05 (0.78-1.42)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis	846	13	831	2,112
Prevalence % (95% CI)	6.1 (4.7-8)	15.4 (2.7-46.3)	5.8 (4.3-7.6)	6.9 (5.8-8)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.9 (0.66-1.23)	2.22 (0.62-8.01)	0.85 (0.62-1.16)	reference
Trimester 3 diagnosis	721	42	634	2,948
Prevalence % (95% CI)	11.9 (9.7-14.6)	19.0 (9.1-34.6)	7.6 (5.7-10)	7.2 (6.3-8.2)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.65 (1.3-2.09)	2.63 (1.39-4.96)	0.88 (0.65-1.19)	reference
ES-IACS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	157	<10	151	468
Prevalence % (95% CI)	6.4 (3.3-11.7)	0 (0-48.3)	6.6 (3.4-12.2)	7.7 (5.5-10.6)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.83 (0.42-1.62)	0 (0-0)	0.86 (0.44-1.68)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis	260	16	244	676
Prevalence % (95% CI)	4.2 (2.2-7.7)	12.5 (2.2-39.6)	3.7 (1.8-7.1)	5.5 (3.9-7.5)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.79 (0.41-1.53)	2.37 (0.63-8.93)	0.69 (0.34-1.41)	reference
Trimester 3 diagnosis	203	32	160	1,128
Prevalence % (95% CI)	6.4 (3.6-10.9)	18.8 (7.9-37)	1.9 (0.5-5.8)	5.7 (4.4-7.2)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.14 (0.64-2.03)	3.31 (1.55-7.04)	0.27 (0.09-0.84)	reference
NO-UIO				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	229	13	216	683
Prevalence % (95% CI)	3.5 (1.6-7)	7.7 (0.4-37.9)	3.2 (1.4-6.8)	4.5 (3.2-6.5)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.77 (0.36-1.66)	1.72 (0.25-11.72)	0.72 (0.32-1.61)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis	396	39	357	1,180
Prevalence % (95% CI)	3.8 (2.2-6.3)	7.7 (2-22)	3.4 (1.8-6)	5.2 (4-6.6)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.76 (0.43-1.31)	1.55 (0.5-4.79)	0.67 (0.37-1.24)	reference
Trimester 3 diagnosis	306	47	257	1,316
Prevalence % (95% CI)	5.6 (3.4-8.9)	0 (0-9.4)	5.8 (3.4-9.6)	5.9 (4.7-7.3)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.95 (0.57-1.57)	0 (0-0)	0.85 (0.5-1.45)	reference

Notes:

1. Analyses restricted to live births only
2. Because pre-term is defined as occurring before 37 weeks' gestation, only exposure to COVID-19 in weeks 0-36 (inclusive) of gestation was investigated.
3. Matched comparator group were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they had a pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.
4. Estimates adjusted for age; presence of at least one condition increasing the risk of hospitalized COVID-19; presence of least one obstetric risk condition.
5. BPE did not have a matched comparator cohort of pregnant women without COVID-19, as they did not have access to COVID-19 positive test results in the community, hence there is no risk estimate presented. Furthermore, as they only had access to inpatient data with ICD10 codes of COVID-diagnoses only, all episodes of COVID-19 identified in their data were classed as hospitalized (with the caveat that those diagnoses within 2 days of delivery were not included in this classification, in a similar manner to other DAPS). As the numbers of women with a COVID-19 positive test /diagnosis in the first and second trimester were very low, prevalence estimates are imprecise.

8.5.2.7 Stillbirth

A COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis in trimester 3 was associated with an increased risk of stillbirth in IACS (Spain) but not in FISABI-HSRU (Spain) or UIO (Norway). In IACS prevalence of stillbirths among total cases with a positive test/diagnosis in trimester 3 was 1.2%, in contrast with 0.2% in the matched comparator group, leading to an adjusted hazard ratio of 6.69 (95% CI: 1.3-34.49). In the hospitalized group, the adjusted hazard ratio was 30.88 (95% CI: 5.1-186.93).

Table 30 Prevalence of stillbirth and its association with COVID-19 diagnosis (by pregnancy trimester and severity of COVID-19 disease)

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group.
ES-FISABIO-HSRU				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	805	4	801	2309
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0.2 (0-1)	0 (0-60.4)	0.2 (0-1)	0.5 (0.3-0.9)
Adjusted hazard ratio (95% CI)	0.92 (0.25-3.35)	0 (0-Inf)	0.93 (0.25-3.37)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis				
Trimester 2 diagnosis	851	13	834	2127
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0.5 (0.2-1.3)	0 (0-28.3)	0.2 (0-1)	0.4 (0.2-0.8)
Adjusted hazard ratio (95% CI)	1.52 (0.44-5.18)	0 (0-Inf)	0.76 (0.16-3.68)	reference
Trimester 3 diagnosis				
Trimester 3 diagnosis	1181	82	756	2966
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0.2 (0-0.7)	0 (0-5.6)	0.3 (0-1.1)	0.4 (0.2-0.7)
Adjusted hazard ratio (95% CI)	0.3 (0.04-2.43)	0 (0-Inf)	0.46 (0.06-3.69)	reference
ES-IACS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	157	<10	151	469
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-3)	0 (0-48.3)	0 (0-3.1)	0.2 (0-1.4)
Adjusted hazard ratio (95% CI)	0 (0-Inf)	0 (0-Inf)	0 (0-Inf)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis				
Trimester 2 diagnosis	261	16	245	677
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0.4 (0-2.5)	0 (0-24.1)	0.4 (0-2.6)	0.1 (0-1)
Adjusted hazard ratio (95% CI)	2.58 (0.16-41.42)	0 (0-Inf)	2.81 (0.18-44.89)	reference
Trimester 3 diagnosis				
Trimester 3 diagnosis	431	68	197	1131
Prevalence % (95% CI)	1.2 (0.4-2.8)	4.4 (1.1-13.2)	0.5 (0-3.2)	0.2 (0-0.7)
Adjusted hazard ratio (95% CI)	6.69 (1.3-34.49)	30.88 (5.1-186.93)	2.71 (0.24-30.02)	reference
NO-UIO				
Trimester 1 diagnosis				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	229	13	216	686
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-2.1)	0 (0-28.3)	0 (0-2.2)	0.3 (0.1-1.2)
Adjusted hazard ratio (95% CI)	0 (0-Inf)	0 (0-Inf)	0 (0-Inf)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis				
Trimester 2 diagnosis	397	39	358	1,185
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0.3 (0-1.6)	0 (0-11.2)	0.3 (0-1.8)	0.4 (0.2-1)
Adjusted hazard ratio (95% CI)	0.7 (0.08-6.04)	0 (0-Inf)	0.77 (0.09-6.61)	reference
Trimester 3 diagnosis				
Trimester 3 diagnosis	443	104	301	1,322
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0.7 (0.2-2.1)	1.0 (0.1-6)	0.7 (0.1-2.6)	0.5 (0.2-1)

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group.
Adjusted hazard ratio (95% CI)	1.52 (0.38-6.09)	2.21 (0.27-18.42)	1.48 (0.3-7.35)	reference

Notes:

1. Analyses restricted to just pregnancies that reached at least 22 weeks of gestation.
2. Matched comparator group were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they had a pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.
3. Estimates adjusted for age; presence of at least one condition increasing the risk of hospitalized COVID-19; presence of least one obstetric risk.

8.5.2.7 Neonatal death

There were neonatal deaths in either pregnancy cohort.

Table 31 Prevalence of neonatal death and its association with COVID-19 infection (by trimester and severity of infection)

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group.
IT-ARS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	133	<10	132	432
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-3.499)	0 (0-94.538)	0 (0-3.524)	0 (0-1.099)
ES-FISABIO-HSRU				
Trimester 2 diagnosis	252	16	236	603
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-1.872)	0 (0-24.074)	0 (0-1.996)	0 (0-0.789)
ES-IACS				
Trimester 3 diagnosis	472	100	270	1083
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-1.006)	0 (0-4.61)	0 (0-1.749)	0 (0-0.441)
ES-FISABIO-HSRU				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	685	<10	681	1972
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-0.695)	0 (0-60.423)	0 (0-0.699)	0 (0-0.242)
ES-IACS				
Trimester 2 diagnosis	704	11	693	1824
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-0.677)	0 (0-32.145)	0 (0-0.687)	0 (0-0.262)
ES-FISABIO-HSRU				
Trimester 3 diagnosis	1051	78	635	2558
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-0.454)	0 (0-5.849)	0 (0-0.75)	0 (0-0.187)
ES-IACS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	103	<10	100	339
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-4.481)	0 (0-69.001)	0 (0-4.61)	0 (0-1.397)
ES-FISABIO-HSRU				
Trimester 2 diagnosis	175	12	163	487
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-2.677)	0 (0-30.125)	0 (0-2.87)	0 (0-0.976)
ES-IACS				
Trimester 3 diagnosis	329	52	145	873
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-1.439)	0 (0-8.57)	0 (0-3.217)	0 (0-0.546)

Notes:

1. Analyses restricted to live births only.
2. Matched comparator group were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they had a pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.
3. Estimates adjusted for age; presence of at least one condition increasing the risk of hospitalized COVID-19; presence of least one obstetric risk condition.
4. No modelling due to small numbers.

8.5.2.8 Low birth weight

Across ‘all cases’, there was no association between COVID-19 test/diagnosis in pregnancy, and low birth weight. In hospitalized cases, there was evidence of elevated risk among those with a positive test or diagnosis in trimester 2(FISABIO-HSR, IACS and UIO). There was approximately a 3-fold increase in the risk of low birth weight among these women with a hospitalized infection, though this was based on a small number of pregnant women (n=64).

Table 32 Prevalence of low birth weight and its association with COVID-19 diagnosis (by pregnancy trimester and severity of COVID-19 disease)

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group.
IT-ARS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	133	<10	132	432
Prevalence % (95% CI)	6.8 (3.3-12.8)	0 (0-94.5)	6.8 (3.4-12.9)	10.4 (7.8-13.8)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.66 (0.33-1.32)	0 (0-0)	0.67 (0.34-1.33)	reference
ES-FISABIO-HSRU				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	685	<10	681	1,972
Prevalence % (95% CI)	7.5 (5.6-9.7)	0 (0-60.4)	7.5 (5.7-9.8)	8.2 (7.1-9.5)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.92 (0.68-1.25)	0 (0-0)	0.93 (0.68-1.26)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis	704	11	693	1,824
Prevalence % (95% CI)	7.1 (5.4-9.3)	27.3 (7.3-60.7)	6.8 (5.1-9.0)	7.9 (6.7-9.3)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.90 (0.66-1.23)	3.4 (1.28-9.02)	0.86 (0.63-1.18)	reference
Trimester 3 diagnosis	1051	78	635	2,558
Prevalence % (95% CI)	8.2 (6.6-10.0)	11.5(5.7-21.3)	6.8 (5.0-9.1)	9.7(8.6-10.9)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.84 (0.66-1.06)	1.18 (0.63-2.19)	0.69 (0.51-0.94)	reference
ES-IACS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	103	<10	100	339
Prevalence % (95% CI)	6.8 (3.0-14.0)	0 (0-69.0)	7.0 (3.1-14.4)	9.1 (6.4-12.9)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.75 (0.34-1.65)	0 (0-0)	0.77 (0.35-1.7)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis	175	12	163	487
Prevalence % (95% CI)	6.9 (3.8-11.0)	33.3 (11.3-64.6)	4.9 (2.3-9.8)	9.2 (6.9-12.3)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.76 (0.41-1.41)	3.44 (1.48-7.98)	0.55 (0.26-1.14)	reference
Trimester 3 diagnosis	329	52	145	873
Prevalence % (95% CI)	6.1 (3.8-9.4)	9.6 (3.6-21.8)	3.4 (1.3-8.3)	8.0 (6.3-10.1)

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group.
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.76 (0.47-1.22)	1.18 (0.51-2.74)	0.43 (0.18-1.05)	reference
NO-UIO				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	232	13	219	691
Prevalence % (95% CI)	4.7 (2.5-8.6)	0 (0-28.3)	5.0(2.7-9.1)	3.5 (2.3-5.2)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.41 (0.7-2.82)	0 (0-0)	1.49 (0.74-2.99)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis	403	41	362	1198
Prevalence % (95% CI)	4.1(2.4-6.5)	12.2 (4.6-27.0)	3 (1.6-5.5)	4.4 (3.4-5.8)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.92 (0.54-1.59)	2.93 (1.21-7.06)	0.71 (0.37-1.34)	reference
Trimester 3 diagnosis	444	105	300	1,327
Prevalence % (95% CI)	4.1 (2.5-6.5)	1.9 (0.3-7.4)	4.7 (2.7-7.9)	4.7 (3.7-6.1)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.85 (0.51-1.41)	0.4 (0.1-1.59)	0.99 (0.56-1.73)	reference

Notes:

1. Analyses restricted to live births only.
2. Matched comparator group were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they had a pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.
3. Estimates adjusted for age; presence of at least one condition increasing the risk of hospitalized COVID-19; presence of least one obstetric risk condition.

8.5.2.9 SGA/FGR

Across 'all cases', there was no association between COVID-19 test/diagnosis in pregnancy, and SGA/FGR. However, among hospitalized cases in IACS and UIO, there was an elevated risk among those with a positive test or diagnosis in trimester 2, based on a small number of pregnant women (n=53).

Table 33 Prevalence of SGA/FGR and its association with COVID-19 diagnosis (by pregnancy trimester and severity of COVID-19 disease)

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group.
IT-ARS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	133	<10	132	432
Prevalence % (95% CI)	3.0 (1-8.0)	0 (0-94.5)	3.0 (1.0-8.1)	5.3 (3.5-8.0)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.57 (0.2-1.63)	0 (0-0)	0.58 (0.2-1.64)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis	252	16	236	603
Prevalence % (95% CI)	3.6 (1.8-6.9)	6.2 (0.3-32.3)	3.4 (1.6-6.8)	5.5 (3.9-7.7)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.65 (0.32-1.32)	1.14 (0.16-7.94)	0.62 (0.29-1.32)	reference
Trimester 3 diagnosis	472	100	270	1083
Prevalence % (95% CI)	4.7 (3.0-7.1)	3.0 (0.8-9.2)	6.3 (3.8-10.1)	5.3 (4.0-6.8)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.89 (0.55-1.45)	0.57 (0.18-1.79)	1.19 (0.7-2.02)	reference
ES-IACS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	103	<10	100	339
Prevalence % (95% CI)	1.9 (0.3-7.5)	0 (0-69.0)	2 (0.3-7.7)	1.5 (0.5-3.6)

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group.
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.3 (0.25-6.69)	0 (0-0)	1.34(0.26-6.93)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis	175	12	163	487
Prevalence % (95% CI)	2.3 (0.7-6.1)	16.7(2.9-49.1)	1.2 (0.2-4.8)	1.8 (0.9-3.6)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.3 (0.41-4.13)	9.56 (2.33-39.28)	0.7 (0.15-3.2)	reference
Trimester 3 diagnosis	329	52	145	873
Prevalence % (95% CI)	1.5 (0.6-3.7)	0 (0-8.6)	2.1(0.5-6.4)	1.8 (1.1-3.0)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.83 (0.31-2.24)	0 (0-0)	1.13 (0.34-3.84)	reference
NO-UIO				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	232	13	219	691
Prevalence % (95% CI)	9.9 (6.5-14.7)	0 (0-28.3)	10.5 (6.9-15.5)	8.2 (6.4-10.6)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.21 (0.76-1.91)	0 (0-0)	1.28 (0.81-2.03)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis	403	41	362	1,198
Prevalence % (95% CI)	10.9 (8.1-14.5)	17.1 (7.7-32.6)	10.2 (7.4-13.9)	8.1 (6.6-9.8)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.35 (0.96-1.89)	2.11 (1.05-4.25)	1.26 (0.88-1.81)	reference
Trimester 3 diagnosis	444	105	300	1,327
Prevalence % (95% CI)	11.5 (8.7-14.9)	10.5 (5.6-18.4)	13 (9.5-17.5)	8.7 (7.2-10.3)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.33 (0.97-1.81)	1.20 (0.67-2.15)	1.51 (1.07-2.12)	reference

Notes:

1. Analyses restricted to live births only.

2. Matched comparator group were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they had a pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.

3. Estimates adjusted for age; presence of at least one condition increasing the risk of hospitalized COVID-19; presence of least one obstetric risk condition.

4. Norway use observations from its birth registry to capture information on Small for Gestational Age (SGA). The other DAPs use diagnostic codes to capture this information which may lead to underestimation of the prevalence of this condition.

8.5.2.10 Low Apgar Score (0-3)

There was no association between a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis in any trimester and the outcome of low Apgar score (0-3) in the three DAPS with information about Apgar score.

Table 34 Prevalence of low Apgar score (0-3) and its association with COVID-19 diagnosis (by pregnancy trimester and severity of COVID-19 disease)

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group.
IT-ARS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	133	<10	132	432
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-3.5)	0 (0-94.5)	0 (0-3.5)	0.2 (0.0-1.5)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis	252	16	236	603
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0.4 (0.0-2.5)	6.3 (0.3-32.3)	0 (0-2.0)	0.2 (0.0-1.1)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	2.4 (0.15-38.23)	35.67 (2.37-537.03)	0 (0-0)	reference

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group.
Trimester 3 diagnosis	472	100	270	1,083
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-1.0)	0 (0-4.6)	0 (0-1.7)	0.4 (0.1-1.0)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	reference
ES-IACS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	103	<10	100	339
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-4.5)	0 (0-69.0)	0 (0-4.6)	0.3 (0.0-1.9)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis	175	12	163	487
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-2.677)	0 (0-30.1)	0 (0-2.9)	0 (0-1.0)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.0 (0.84-1.19)	1 (0.56-1.77)	1 (0.84-1.19)	reference
Trimester 3 diagnosis	329	52	145	873
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0.6 (0.1-2.4)	0 (0-8.6)	0.7(0.04.4)	0.5(0.2-1.2)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.33 (0.24-7.23)	0 (0-0)	1.52 (0.17-13.71)	reference
NO-UIO				
Trimester 1 diagnosis				
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-2.0)	0 (0-28.3)	0 (0-2.1)	0 (0-0.7)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.0 (0.86-1.16)	1.0 (0.58-1.73)	1.0 (0.86-1.16)	reference
Trimester 2 diagnosis				
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0.2 (0-1.6)	0 (0-10.7)	0.3 (0-1.8)	0.2 (0-0.7)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.38 (0.13-15.17)	0 (0-0)	1.54 (0.14-16.88)	reference
Trimester 3 diagnosis				
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0.2 (0-1.4)	1.0 (0.1-6.0)	0 (0-1.6)	0.3 (0.1-0.8)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.76 (0.09-6.7)	3.2 (0.36-28.18)	0 (0-0)	reference

Notes:

1. Analyses restricted to live births only.
2. Matched comparator group were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they had a pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.
3. Estimates adjusted for age; presence of at least one condition increasing the risk of hospitalized COVID-19; presence of least one obstetric risk condition.

8.5.2.11 Major congenital anomalies

There was no association between a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis in the first trimester and the outcome of major congenital anomaly in the two DAPS that investigated this.

Table 35 Prevalence of major congenital anomalies and its association with COVID-19 infection in pregnancy trimester 1 (by severity of COVID-19 disease)

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group.
IT-ARS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	133	<10	132	432
Prevalence % (95% CI)	5.3 (2.3-10.9)	0 (0-94.5)	5.3 (2.3-11.0)	4.4 (2.7-6.9)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	1.26 (0.54-2.95)	0 (0-0)	1.27 (0.54-2.97)	reference
NO-UIO				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	232	13	219	691
Prevalence % (95% CI)	3.0 (1.3-6.4)	0 (0-28.3)	3.2 (1.4-6.7)	3.0 (1.9-4.7)
Adjusted risk ratio (95% CI)	0.99 (0.43-2.29)	0 (0-0)	1.05 (0.46-2.43)	reference

Notes:

1. All pregnancies included in the analyses.
2. Only exposure to COVID-19 in the first trimester was investigated.
3. Matched comparator group were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they had a pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.
4. Estimates adjusted for age; presence of at least one condition increasing the risk of hospitalized COVID-19; presence of least one obstetric risk condition.

8.5.2.12 Microcephaly

In the two DAPS that investigated this outcome, there were no cases of microcephaly among the pregnant women who tested positive for COVID-19 during their pregnancy.

Table 36 Prevalence of microcephaly and its association with COVID-19 infection in pregnancy trimester 1 (by severity of COVID-19 disease)

	All cases	Hospitalized cases	Non-hospitalized cases	Matched comparator pregnant non-COVID-19 group.
IT-ARS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	133	<10	132	432
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-3.5)	0 (0-94.5)	0 (0-3.5)	0 (0-1.1)
ES-IACS				
Trimester 1 diagnosis	103	<10	100	339
Prevalence % (95% CI)	0 (0-4.5)	0 (0-69.0)	0 (0-4.6)	0.3 (0.0-1.9)

Notes:

1. All pregnancies included in the analyses.
2. Only exposure to COVID-19 in the first trimester was investigated.
3. Matched comparator group were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they had a pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.
4. No modelling due to low numbers.

8.5.3 Prevalence of adverse maternal and pregnancy outcomes according to medicines use in pregnancy among women with COVID-19 on pregnancy that were not hospitalized for COVID-19

The prevalence of gestational diabetes and pre-eclampsia by level of medication exposure presented in the following tables. Three level of medication exposure were examined:

- exposed to the medication group in the 30 days pre COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis
- not exposed to the medication group in the 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis
- exposed to the medication group in the 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis.

Analyses were restricted to pregnancies that reached at least 20 weeks of gestation only. Because the operational definition of both gestational diabetes and pre-eclampsia is any outcome occurrence from start of second trimester, only exposure to COVID-19 in the first trimester was investigated. Given the risk of exposure miss-classification (lack of information on medication administration in hospital), the analyses were conducted on non-hospitalized cases only.

8.5.3.1 Prevalence of gestational diabetes

All medication groups at the ATC-2nd level were analyzed. The tables have been edited to remove those medication groups which were not dispensed in either the 30-day pre- or the 30-day post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis window. Cells contain ‘no matches’ if there were no women exposed to that medication group in the time window under observation. A prevalence of ‘0’ indicates that of those women exposed to the medication group during the window of observation, there was zero prevalence of the outcome (i.e., gestational diabetes or pre-eclampsia).

We can see from Table 37 that the prevalence of gestational diabetes among pregnant women who were dispensed an antithrombotic in the 30 days before their COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis was 12.5% (0.7-53.3); the prevalence among those who were NOT exposed in the 30 days post their COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis was 3.8% (1.4-9.1); and the prevalence among those exposed was 16.7% (4.4-42.3).

Table 37 Prevalence of gestational diabetes among pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis in the first trimester, by exposure to medication, ARS

Drug group	(a) Exposed to medication in 30 days pre COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis	(b) Not exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis	(c) Exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis
Analgesics	0 (0-94.5)	1.3 (0.2-5.3)	no matches
Antibacterials	9.1 (0.5-42.9)	9.5 (5.4-16)	0 (0-30.1)
Anthelmintics	no matches	0 (0-3.2)	100 (5.5-100)
Antithrombotic	12.5 (0.7-53.3)	3.8 (1.4-9.1)	16.7 (4.4-42.3)
Antivirals	0 (0-94.5)	0 (0-3.1)	no matches
Corticosteroids	0 (0-69)	5.6 (2.6-11.2)	14.3 (0.8-58)
Obstructive_Airway	0 (0-94.5)	2 (0.5-6.3)	0 (0-94.5)
Psychoanaleptics	0 (0-80.2)	1.4 (0.2-5.3)	0 (0-80.2)
Psycholeptics	0 (0-94.5)	0 (0-3.2)	0 (0-94.5)

Table 38 Prevalence of gestational diabetes among pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis in the first trimester, by exposure to medication, FISABIO-HSRU

Drug group	(a) Exposed to medication in 30 days pre COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis	(b) Not-exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis	(c) Exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis
Analgesics	5.6 (0.3-29.4)	4.4 (3.1-6.1)	0 (0-19.2)
Anti_inflammatory	18.2 (3.2-52.2)	3.9 (2.7-5.6)	0 (0-34.5)
Antibacterials	3.7 (0.2-20.9)	5 (3.6-6.8)	2.8 (0.1-16.2)
Antihypertensives	0 (0-69)	0.4 (0.1-1.2)	0 (0-94.5)
Antithrombotic	0 (0-21.9)	1.5 (0.7-3.1)	9.2 (6.2-13.5)
Antivirals	0 (0-80.2)	0.2 (0-1)	no matches
Corticosteroids	0 (0-53.7)	0.8 (0.3-1.7)	0 (0-69)
Cough_cold	33.3 (1.8-87.5)	0.6 (0.2-1.5)	0 (0-80.2)
Diabetes	28.6 (5.1-69.7)	2.5 (1.6-3.9)	42.9 (11.8-79.8)
Immunosuppressants	0 (0-94.5)	0 (0-0.6)	no matches
Nasal	0 (0-60.4)	1.3 (0.6-2.4)	0 (0-69)
Obstructive_Airway	0 (0-28.3)	1.8 (1-3.1)	3.6 (0.2-20.2)
Psychoanaleptics	0 (0-32.1)	0.4 (0.1-1.2)	12.5 (0.7-53.3)
Psycholeptics	0 (0-28.3)	1.6 (0.9-2.9)	9.1 (0.5-42.9)

Table 39 Prevalence of gestational diabetes among pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis in the first trimester, by exposure to medication, IACS

Drug group	(a) Exposed to medication in 30 days pre COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis	(b) Not-exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis	(c) Exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis
Analgesics	22.2 (7.4-48.1)	6.7 (3.3-12.6)	12.5 (2.2-39.6)
Anti_inflammatory	66.7 (12.5-98.2)	8.7 (4.9-14.7)	0 (0-94.5)
Antibacterials	28.6 (5.1-69.7)	7.9 (4.2-14)	9.1 (0.5-42.9)
Antihypertensives	0 (0-80.2)	0.7 (0-4.2)	no matches
Antithrombotic	12.5 (0.7-53.3)	3.3 (1.1-8.8)	9.7 (2.5-26.9)
Corticosteroids	no matches	1.3 (0.2-5.2)	0 (0-94.5)
Cough_cold	no matches	0 (0-3.1)	0 (0-94.5)
Diabetes	no matches	2.7 (0.9-7.1)	100 (5.5-100)
Nasal	50 (9.5-90.5)	2 (0.5-6.3)	33.3 (1.8-87.5)
Obstructive_Airway	0 (0-80.2)	2 (0.5-6.3)	0 (0-69)
Psychoanaleptics	0 (0-60.4)	2.1 (0.5-6.4)	0 (0-48.3)
Psycholeptics	0 (0-60.4)	2 (0.5-6.3)	0 (0-60.4)

Table 40 Prevalence of gestational diabetes among pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis in the first trimester, by exposure to medication, UIO

Drug group	(a) Exposed to medication in 30 days pre COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis	(b) Not-exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis	(c) Exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis
Analgesics	12.5 (0.7-53.3)	3.8 (1.8-7.6)	0 (0-48.3)
Anti_inflammatory	0 (0-80.2)	1.9 (0.6-5)	0 (0-94.5)
Antibacterials	25 (1.3-78.1)	4.3 (2.1-8.4)	11.1 (0.6-49.3)

Antithrombotic	0 (0-60.4)	1.4 (0.4-4.4)	0 (0-60.4)
Antivirals	0 (0-94.5)	0 (0-2.2)	no matches
Corticosteroids	0 (0-80.2)	0 (0-2.2)	0 (0-94.5)
Cough_cold	no matches	0.5 (0-3)	0 (0-60.4)
Diabetes	0 (0-94.5)	5.6 (3-9.7)	no matches
Nasal	no matches	0 (0-2.2)	0 (0-80.2)
Obstructive_Airway	0 (0-80.2)	0.5 (0-3)	0 (0-94.5)
Psycholeptics	0 (0-80.2)	0.9 (0.2-3.7)	50 (9.5-90.5)
Vaccinations	0 (0-94.5)	0.5 (0-3)	no matches

8.5.3.1 Prevalence of pre-eclampsia

Table 41 Prevalence of pre-eclampsia among pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis in the first trimester, by exposure to medication, ARS

Drug group	(a) Exposed to medication in 30 days pre COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis	(b) Not-exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis	(c) Exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis
Analgesics	0 (0-94.5)	0 (0-3.1)	no matches
Antibacterials	18.2 (3.2-52.2)	2.2 (0.6-6.8)	8.3 (0.4-40.2)
Anthelmintics	no matches	0 (0-3.2)	0 (0-94.5)
Antithrombotic	0 (0-40.2)	0.8 (0-4.8)	16.7 (4.4-42.3)
Antivirals	0 (0-94.5)	0 (0-3.1)	no matches
Corticosteroids	0 (0-69)	0.7 (0-4.4)	0 (0-43.9)
Obstructive_Airway	100 (5.5-100)	0.7 (0-4.3)	0 (0-94.5)
Psychoanaleptics	0 (0-80.2)	0 (0-3.2)	0 (0-80.2)
Psycholeptics	0 (0-94.5)	0 (0-3.2)	0 (0-94.5)

Table 42 Prevalence of pre-eclampsia among pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis in the first trimester, by exposure to medication, FISABIO-HSRU

Drug group	(a) Exposed to medication in 30 days pre COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis	(b) Not-exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis	(c) Exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis
Analgesics	0 (0-21.9)	0.5 (0.2-1.4)	0 (0-19.2)
Anti_inflammatory	0 (0-32.1)	0.5 (0.2-1.4)	0 (0-34.5)
Antibacterials	0 (0-15.5)	0.7 (0.2-1.6)	0 (0-12)
Antihypertensives	0 (0-69)	0.2 (0-1)	0 (0-94.5)
Antithrombotic	0 (0-21.9)	0.8 (0.2-2.1)	1.5 (0.5-4)
Antivirals	0 (0-80.2)	0 (0-0.6)	no matches
Corticosteroids	0 (0-53.7)	0.1 (0-0.8)	0 (0-69)
Cough_cold	0 (0-69)	0 (0-0.6)	0 (0-80.2)
Diabetes	0 (0-43.9)	0.1 (0-0.8)	0 (0-43.9)
Immunosuppressants	0 (0-94.5)	0 (0-0.6)	no matches
Nasal	0 (0-60.4)	0.1 (0-0.8)	0 (0-69)
Obstructive_Airway	0 (0-28.3)	0.3 (0-1)	0 (0-15)
Psychoanaleptics	0 (0-32.1)	0 (0-0.6)	0 (0-40.2)

Psycholeptics	0 (0-28.3)	0.3 (0-1)	0 (0-32.1)
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Table 43 Prevalence of pre-eclampsia among pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis in the first trimester, by exposure to medication, IACS

Drug group	(a) Exposed to medication in 30 days pre COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis	(b) Not-exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis	(c) Exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis
Analgesics	0 (0-21.9)	1.5 (0.3-5.8)	0 (0-24.1)
Anti_inflammatory	0 (0-69)	1.3 (0.2-5.2)	0 (0-94.5)
Antibacterials	0 (0-43.9)	1.4 (0.2-5.6)	0 (0-32.1)
Antihypertensives	0 (0-80.2)	0.7 (0-4.2)	no matches
Antithrombotic	0 (0-40.2)	0 (0-3.9)	3.2 (0.2-18.5)
Corticosteroids	no matches	0 (0-3.1)	0 (0-94.5)
Cough_cold	no matches	0 (0-3.1)	0 (0-94.5)
Diabetes	no matches	0 (0-3.1)	0 (0-94.5)
Nasal	0 (0-80.2)	0 (0-3.2)	0 (0-69)
Obstructive_Airway	0 (0-80.2)	0 (0-3.2)	0 (0-69)
Psychoanaleptics	0 (0-60.4)	0 (0-3.2)	0 (0-48.3)
Psycholeptics	0 (0-60.4)	0 (0-3.2)	0 (0-60.4)

Table 44 Prevalence of pre-eclampsia among pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis in the first trimester, by exposure to medication, UIO

Drug group	(a) Exposed to medication in 30 days pre COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis	(b) Not-exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis	(c) Exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis
Analgesics	0 (0-40.2)	1.4 (0.4-4.5)	0 (0-48.3)
Anti_inflammatory	0 (0-80.2)	0.5 (0-3)	0 (0-94.5)
Antibacterials	0 (0-60.4)	1.9 (0.6-5.2)	0 (0-37.1)
Antithrombotic	0 (0-60.4)	0 (0-2.2)	0 (0-60.4)
Antivirals	0 (0-94.5)	0 (0-2.2)	no matches
Corticosteroids	0 (0-80.2)	0 (0-2.2)	0 (0-94.5)
Cough_cold	no matches	0.9 (0.2-3.7)	0 (0-60.4)
Diabetes	0 (0-94.5)	0.5 (0-3)	no matches
Nasal	no matches	0.5 (0-3)	0 (0-80.2)
Obstructive_Airway	0 (0-80.2)	0 (0-2.2)	0 (0-94.5)
Psycholeptics	0 (0-80.2)	0 (0-2.2)	0 (0-80.2)
Vaccinations	0 (0-94.5)	0.5 (0-3)	no matches

9 Discussion

This report from Work Package 1 of the CONSIGN project using electronic health care data from seven Data Access Providers in six countries, presents findings on medicines utilisation and pregnancy and neonatal outcomes in a cohort of 8,943 pregnant women who tested positive for COVID-19 during their pregnancy.

Comparison was made between this cohort and two matched comparator groups: pregnant women who did not test positive for COVID-19 during pregnancies in the pandemic, and non-pregnant women (of childbearing age) who tested positive for COVID-19. Analyses were undertaken at the level of trimester when the infection took place and were stratified by level of COVID-19 disease severity.

9.1 Caveats on interpretation of the findings

There are several caveats that need to be taken into consideration when interpreting the findings of this work.

Firstly, this report presents data on dispensing (or prescribing) in the outpatient/primary care setting only. It does not include medication administered to women during hospitalization for COVID-19. Therefore, the patterns of medication use are likely to differ from hospital-based studies as provided by INOSS and COVI-PREG in the CONSIGN project, which have a higher proportion of women with hospitalized COVID-19 and use of injectable medications.

Secondly, it is likely that the differences in the diverse health systems examined here, as well as their models of reimbursements for pharmaceuticals, will have contributed to the differences observed in patterns of medication use across the data sources. For example, paracetamol is reimbursed in FISABIO, IACS, but only in the Norwegian registries if prescribed by a physician. All prescriptions are free of charge in Wales, but many analgesics can be conveniently bought in pharmacies and supermarkets. It is not feasible to disentangle these influences from differences in prescribing patterns.

Thirdly, small sample sizes lead to less precise prevalence estimates, as seen by the wide confidence intervals in the analyses of hospitalized COVID-19 cases, especially in trimester 1 and 2. This needs to be taken into consideration when comparing across data sources.

Fourthly, we observed different absolute prevalences of maternal and pregnancy outcomes between DAPS, both in the pre-pandemic cohort (2018-2019), and during the pandemic. While some of this is as a result of true difference in prevalence of these outcomes; there is likely an element of both methodological and clinical heterogeneity here. Methodological heterogeneity

includes measurement heterogeneity (clinical classification system, and provenance of data in the data sources (e.g. GP only, Hospital only or both) and information heterogeneity (granularity of clinical codes). Furthermore, DAPS had access to different type of data. DAPs that have access to birth registries will have rich data specific to the pregnancy and the neonatal outcomes (e.g., low birth weight of the infant, small for gestational age) which may not necessarily be detected in hospital records using diagnostic codes. Clinical heterogeneity includes differences in population characteristics, prescription patterns, health care systems (incl. level of treatment, in patient out patient management, screening in pregnancy), different methods to diagnosis the disease (eg. rare diseases) and behaviors. Some of the differences in outcomes are documented in Europeristat. There was no formal validation study done, but DAPs checked the observed prevalences against published data for their own country, such as Europeristat 2022.²³

9.2 Main findings

9.2.1 Baseline characteristics

We categorized women as having hospitalized or non-hospitalized COVID-19 based on whether they had a diagnosis for COVID-19 during a hospital admission. For the pregnant cohort, we ‘quarantined’ those cases where the diagnosis was within 2 days of delivery, in an attempt to reduce misclassification of severity. There was no evidence to show that pregnant women who were hospitalized with COVID-19 (defined as hospitalized by definition) had a higher prevalence of co-morbidities than those without an admission (non-hospitalized COVID-19). In contrast, among the non-pregnant comparator group, those classed as hospitalized (again based on a hospital admission with a COVID-19 diagnosis) had considerably higher prevalence of these medical conditions. From this we may surmise that the threshold to admit pregnant women with a COVID-19 diagnosis to hospital was considerably lower than among the non-pregnant cohort of women.

9.2.2 Medicines use

Of the 23 drug classes examined at the ATC-2 level, antithrombotic medicines (B01) was the only medicines class to show an increase in 30-day prevalence of use in pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test or diagnosis. Smaller increases observed among other medicines classes were not significant, and patterns were inconsistent across DAPS. We did not see significant an increase in the use of antibacterials, corticosteroids, or antivirals between the 30-day prior and post-COVID-19 diagnosis.

The increase in use of antithrombotic medicines was experienced across all pregnancy trimesters and was most pronounced in the second and third trimester of pregnancy. In the IACS data source, over one third of women who test positive for or were diagnosed with COVID-19 during their second trimester were dispensed a prescription for an antithrombotic agent (B01) in the following 30 days; this increased to two thirds among those classed as being hospitalized. In trimester 3

infections, almost half of women were dispensed an antithrombotic in the 30 days post COVID-19 infection; this increased to over 80% among hospitalized cases. Prevalence of antithrombotic use in FISABIO—HSRU (also in Spain) after COVID-19 infection was equally as high. In contrast with the two Spanish DAPS, usage of antithrombotic in UIO was considerably lower, with no increase observed among trimester 1 and 2 infections and a very moderate increase to 6% in trimester 3 infections. Usage was higher in cases classed as hospitalized but was dispensed in less than 20% of cases in the 30 days following COVID-19 positive test or diagnosis in trimester 3. There was no change in the *prescribing* of antithrombotic medicines in Wales, with prevalence estimates of 1-2% in each trimester, which was not influenced by COVID-19 diagnosis. SWANSEA (Wales) uses GP prescription data, in contrast to the other DAPS who use pharmacy dispensing data. The divergent results are likely driven by the dispensing of hospital-initiated prescriptions (including ambulatory care and outpatient clinics) in the other DAPS.

Within antithrombotics (B01), the vast majority of dispensing was for heparin (unfractionated) (B01AB01). Among some DAPs this accounted for nearly all usage within the B01AB group; while in other DAPs (e.g., ARS, UIO) there was evidence of other substance(s) contributing to B01AB usage. The analysis did not investigate all substance level codes within B1; it examined enoxaparin, heparin (unfractionated) and acetylsalicylic acid only.

The findings of the present study might also be used to identify women vulnerable to hospitalized COVID infection. In Wales for example, we identified some groups of medicines (at ATC2 level) where prevalence of prescribing in the 30 days before hospitalized infection in trimester 2 (table 85) was higher than amongst the control cohorts. Most of these medicines or the underlying conditions treated (such as obstructive airways disease and diabetes) have been linked with vulnerability to infection, and others (such as antidepressants) are linked with socio-economic status.²⁴ This finding supports the suggestion that certain prescription medicines might usefully serve as a marker for increased vulnerability to hospitalized COVID-19 infection in pregnancy. We saw less difference between non-hospitalized cases and controls.

Comparison with the literature

A systematic review and meta-analysis of 62 observational studies (both case series and cohort studies) published between December 2019 and February 2021, included data on 31,016 pregnant women with confirmed COVID-19. The review found that among those studies that reported on the pharmacotherapeutic management of COVID-19, approximately half of the pregnant women were given antibiotics, anticoagulants, and hydroxychloroquine, one in three were given antivirals, and nearly one in five were managed with either corticosteroids or immunotherapy.²⁵ A key difference in the studies examined in this meta-analysis was that the majority were conducted in the hospital setting, thus not directly comparable with our study.

A preprint published by the OHDSI network of 6 databases consisting of electronic medical records and claims data from France, Spain, and the United States included 8,598 pregnant women with COVID-19 (2,031 hospitalized) between January 2020 and June 2020. Most pregnancies occurred in the US.²⁶ The ten most common inpatient treatments (US only) were systemic corticosteroids (29.6%), enoxaparin (24.0%), immunoglobulins (21.4%), famotidine (20.9%), azithromycin (18.1%), heparin (15.8%), ceftriaxone (7.9%), aspirin (7.0%), hydroxychloroquine (5.4%) and amoxicillin (3.5%). Data was not presented on medication prescribed or dispensed in the outpatient setting, thereby precluding comparison of the findings with our study. Additionally, between country results were not presented or discussed.

Results using the International Registry of Coronavirus Exposure in Pregnancy (IRCEP) – a cohort study where participants enroll in the study during their pregnancy or within 6 months of pregnancy end – were published in 2022.²⁷ The most frequently reported COVID-19 therapies, other than analgesics, included azithromycin (12.8%), steroids (3.5%), interferon (2.4%), oseltamivir (2.1%), chloroquine/hydroxychloroquine (1.7%), anticoagulants (2.0%), antibodies (0.9%), and remdesivir (0.3%). They study found that therapy use patterns varied by country and severity of disease but not notably between trimesters of infection.

9.2.3 Adverse maternal and pregnancy outcomes

We found no evidence of an association between a COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis in pregnancy and an increased risk of gestational diabetes, pre-eclampsia, maternal death, neonatal death, low Apgar score (0-3), major congenital anomalies or microcephaly. We found that COVID-19 infection during pregnancy was associated with an increased risk of pre-term birth, cesarean section, low birth weight, and small for gestational age (SGA). The evidence regarding stillbirth was mixed.

A positive test/diagnosis in trimester 3 was associated with an increased risk of pre-term birth in ARS (Italy), and FISABIO-HSRU (Spain), which was more pronounced in the hospitalized group (ARS - aRR: 3.95 (95% CI: 2.06-7.59)) and (FISABIO-HSRU – aRR: 2.63 (95% CI: 1.39-4.96))). In IACS (Spain), it was only in the hospitalized group that the elevated risk was significant. In ARS (Italy), FISABIO-HSRU (Spain) and IACS (Spain) respectively, the prevalence of pre-term births among women classed as having a hospitalized COVID-19 infection in trimester 3 was 20.5%, 19.0% and 18.8%. The corresponding prevalence in the respective comparator groups was 5.0%, 7.2%, and 5.7%. A COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis in trimester 1 or 2 was not associated with an increased risk of pre-term birth.

While results for cesarean section were mixed, there was evidence that women with a COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis in trimester 2 or trimester 3 were more likely to have caesarean section than

those in the matched comparator group. The greater risk among the hospitalized group was more pronounced in FISABIO-HSRU (Spain), than it was in ARS (Italy).

A hospitalized COVID-19 infection in trimester 2 was associated with a three-fold increased risk of low birth weight. Risk estimates for SGA were less consistent (small numbers of patient with hospitalized infection in trimester 2) but showed evidence of an increased risk with trimester 2 infections.

Only three DAPS investigated stillbirth, and the results were mixed. In IACS (Spain), the prevalence of stillbirths among total cases with a positive test/diagnosis in trimester 3 was 1.2%, in contrast with 0.2% in the matched comparator group, leading to an adjusted hazard ratio of 6.69 (95% CI: 1.3-34.49). There was no increased risk observed among cases in FISABIO-HSRU (Spain) or UIO (Norway).

It is important to reiterate that the numbers of infections in the first trimester classed as hospitalized was very low (each DAP had less than 10 hospitalized cases in trimester 1 (with the exception of UIO which had 13), which led to imprecise and unstable risk estimates for this trimester of pregnancy.

Comparison with the literature

A 2021 systematic review and meta-analysis by Wei et al examining the impact of COVID-19 on pregnancy outcomes pooled the results from 44 studies including 440,000 pregnant women.²⁸ They found an increased risk of pre-eclampsia, pre-term birth and other adverse pregnancy outcomes. Compared with women without COVID-19 infection in pregnancy, women with COVID-19 had a higher risk of preeclampsia (OR 1.33, 95% CI 1.03 to 1.73); preterm birth (OR 1.82, 95% CI 1.38 to 2.39); stillbirth (OR 2.11, 95% CI 1.14 to 3.90) Risks were significantly greater among those with hospitalized infections. Compared with mild COVID-19, hospitalized COVID-19 was strongly associated with preeclampsia (OR 4.16, 95% CI 1.55 to 11.15); preterm birth (OR 4.29, 95% CI 2.41 to 7.63); gestational diabetes (OR 1.99, 95% CI 1.09 to 3.64); low birth weight (OR 1.89, 95% CI 1.14 to 3.12).

Findings in the second update of the BMJ living systematic review and meta-analysis by Allotey et al. examining *maternal and perinatal outcomes of coronavirus disease in pregnancy: living systematic review and meta-analysis*) were consistent with their original review and first update previous update.²⁹ When compared with pregnant and recently pregnant women without the disease, pregnant women with COVID-19 were at higher risk of any preterm birth (odds ratio 1.57, 95% confidence interval 1.36 to 1.81; 48 studies, 449 040 women), stillbirth (1.81, 1.38 to 2.37; 25 studies, 423 477 women), and neonatal death (2.35, 1.16 to 4.76; 21 studies, 12 416). However, the overall number of neonatal deaths was small (only sixteen events in the COVID-19 group).

Piekos et al also reviewed the literature on the impact of maternal COVID-19 infection on maternal-fetal outcomes.³⁰ Studies indicated elevated risk of pre-term birth; most studies reported a 1.2 to 2.0-fold increased rate of preterm birth following maternal SARS-CoV-2 infection. The maternal SARS-CoV-2 infection itself rather than infection severity, had the major impact on the increased risk of adverse maternal and perinatal outcomes.³⁰

A large multicenter study by the same authors investigated how timing of infection during pregnancy impacted risk of adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes.³¹ The authors reported that the single greatest predictor of gestational age at delivery was gestational age at infection, with earlier age at infection associated with earlier age at delivery. There was no correlation between severity of COVID-19 and gestational age at delivery.³¹

9.3 Strengths and limitations

The study has several strengths.

It includes a large number of pregnant women (n=295,094) and 9,011 who tested positive for COVID-19 during their pregnancy among X data partners in X countries. It therefore provides rich information on similarities and disparities across these countries. It covers a long time period time - namely all pregnancies coming to completion between the start of pandemic (March 2020) and October 2021.

The breadth of data available was substantial. DAPS had access to primary care data, hospital data, surveillance data, vaccine data, pharmacy dispensing data, GP prescribing data birth registries and procedure data,

We could use two matched comparator groups to compare medicines utilisation patterns something that is not available in COVID-19 based data collections such as in INOSS or COVI-PREG: 1) pregnant women without COVID-19 whose pregnancies started at the same time as their matched cases – this allowed us to ensure that we were comparing medication use at the trimester level between cases and control; 2) non-pregnant women who tested positive for COVID-19 at the same calendar time as the pregnant cases, and looked at how medication use among this group compared with the pregnant cases.

All analyses were conducted at the level of the trimester of pregnancy, which is an important factor to be considered when making decisions about the pharmacological management of illness in pregnancy. Furthermore, analyses were conducted on (i) all cases of COVID-19, (ii) those classed as hospitalized and (iii) those classed as non-hospitalized, to highlight the difference in management of those women who had a hospital admission for COVID-19 during their pregnancy. In an attempt to reduce miss-classifying as hospitalized those cases where COVID-19 was detected

during screening in hospital, women who tested positive for COVID-19 within 2 days of delivery, were ‘quarantined’ from the hospitalized group.

The depth of the analyses undertaken provided rich information on trends in medicines utilisation. For example, when interesting patterns emerged in the medicines utilisation review, access to data at the 3, 4, 5th level facilitated further investigation as to what substances were being used to manage COVID-19, and did this differ across countries.

Limiting the exposure window to 30 days before and 30 days after COVID-19 positive test, sharpened the analysis, especially focusing in on medicines used immediately pre- and post-diagnosis. It also highlighted greater prevalence of use of several medicines in the baseline (i.e. pre-COVID19 window) in the hospitalized group than controls, a pattern not seen in non-hospitalized cases. This supports the suggestion that certain prescription medicines might serve as a marker for increased vulnerability to hospitalized COVID-19 infection in pregnancy. This may assist in the identification of women at increased risk of hospitalized infection.

There are several limitations.

A first limitation is that we underestimate the total prevalence of medication use as we do not capture in-patient prescribing and administration in those women who were admitted to hospital for treatment. This includes treatments with antithrombotics, antivirals, corticosteroids and immunoglobulins. The underestimation will be most prominent for the women with more hospitalized COVID-19 disease. Our analysis does examine medication use in the thirty days following COVID-9 positive test/diagnosis which would capture usage post hospital discharge, but not throughout the duration of hospital stay.

A second limitation is misclassification of both medication exposure and COVID-19 status may occur. Medications may not be used at the exact time as they are prescribed/dispensed and may be stockpiled or not taken.³¹ COVID-19 is not always tested; this was especially the case early on in the pandemic, as surveillance systems were being established, and only patients with more hospitalized symptoms and healthcare workers were tested initially. However, this is unlikely to have impacted the result of this study, as those who contracted COVID-19 in the first wave of the pandemic were mostly older and therefore less likely to be included in a pregnancy cohort. We now have the opposite challenge; widescale screening of populations resulting in asymptomatic positive patients who would have not been identified if not for screening. We attempted to account for that in all analyses by ‘quarantining’ those cases of women whose positive results were within 2 days of delivery.

We used the IMI-ConcePTION pregnancy algorithm which allows for several streams of information to detect pregnancies in databanks. This enabled us to capture pregnancies in a more

complete manner, however, for a proportion of pregnancies the start or end data need to be imputed (Gini R el at). We cannot exclude potential misclassification of medication exposure and COVID-19 infection in pregnancy but expect this to be non-differential.

A fourth limitation is that not all DAPs were able to contribute to the analysis of adverse pregnancy outcomes. This was as a result of not having access to that information, or the number of events being too low and the risk of re-identification too high.

A final limitation concerns the inclusion criteria for the pre-pandemic cohort. We included pregnancies that started from 1.1.2018 and ended by 31.12.2019. However, selecting on the end date of pregnancy rather than based on start date of pregnancy plus nine months is likely to have biased upwards the number of early terminations.

9.4 Concluding remarks

This study was conducted among 294,126 pregnant women; 8,943 (3.0%) of whom tested positive for, or were diagnosed with COVID-19, during their pregnancy. Electronic health care registry data from seven Data Access Providers in six European countries between 2018 and 2021 were used.

We found large differences in the prevalence of medication use for several drug categories between and within countries. The most frequently used medications among women with COVID-19 was antithrombotics (B01), with heparin (unfractionated) accounting for the vast majority of this usage. Prevalence of antithrombotics use was higher among those classed as having a hospitalized infection. Increases seen in other drug classes (e.g., antibacterials, corticosteroids) were small in magnitude, and not consistent across DAPS.

Women with COVID-19 infections in pregnancy had increased risk of pre-term birth, cesarean section, small for gestational age, and low birth weight. This was especially seen if the infection was in the 2nd or 3rd trimester of pregnancy, and heightened among cases classed as hospitalized. Results for stillbirths were inconsistent and too imprecise to conclude on.

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Appendices

Annex 1. List of stand-alone documents

Number	Document reference number	Title
1		Prevalence of medication prescribed or dispensed to pregnant women with COVID-19 during their pregnancy
2		Prevalence of medication prescribed or dispensed to pregnant women with COVID-19 and matched pregnant controls
3		Prevalence of medication prescribed or dispensed to pregnant women with COVID-19 and matched non-pregnant controls
4		ARS_ATC3_4_5_all_cases
5		ARS_ATC3_4_5_non_hospitalized_cases
6		ARS_ATC3_4_5_hospitalized_cases
7		BPE_ATC3_4_5_all_cases
8		BPE_ATC3_4_5_hospitalized_cases
9		FISABIO_ATC3_4_5_all_cases
10		FISABIO_ATC3_4_5_non_hospitalized_cases
11		FISABIO_ATC3_4_5_hospitalized_cases
12		IACS_ATC3_4_5_all_cases
13		IACS_ATC3_4_5_non_hospitalized_cases
14		IACS_ATC3_4_5_hospitalized_cases
15		UOSL_ATC3_4_5_all_cases
16		UOSL_ATC3_4_5_non_hospitalized_cases
17		UOSL_ATC3_4_5_hospitalized_cases
18		20221017_CODELIST_CONSIGN_NARROW

Annex 2. Description of data access providers and data banks used

Denmark: Danish linked registries

Denmark has a tax-funded health care system ensuring equal access to health care for all its residents. All hospital-based encounters in Denmark are recorded in medical registers (Schmidt et al., 2019). Administrative registry Danish Civil Registration System contains data on the unique personal identifier (CPR-number), sex, and dates of birth, immigration, emigration, and death. The CPR-number is assigned to every Danish resident upon birth or immigration. The linkage of registers at an individual level is possible via CPR-number, which is used in all Danish registers. Danish registers have a nationwide coverage and a virtually complete capture of hospital-based encounters of 5.8 million Danish residents. For the purpose of the study, we will obtain information from the following registries: The Danish National Prescription Registry (DNPR) includes data on all outpatient dispensing of medicines and vaccines at Danish pharmacies from 1995 and onwards, including dispensing date, ATC code, product code and amount. From the Danish Civil Registration System, data on demographics (sex, date of birth) and censoring (migration, vital status). The Danish National Patient Registry contains diagnoses and procedures from all hospitalizations since 1977 and contacts to hospital specialist outpatient clinics since 1995. The Danish National Health Service Register contains information on referrals for vaccine administration from GPs. COVID-19: COVID and SARS-COV-2 data cannot be promised by the data cut date. Aarhus University will be Data Access Provider for the Danish registries.

Quality of the data banks and linkage

The CRS has routine quality controls and is considered to be of very high quality and completeness⁴. The linkage of data from various Danish registries is unambiguous and performed at an individual level. The linkage is conducted using a unique personal identifier allocated to every resident of Denmark upon birth or immigration. The MBR has nearly 100% completeness and a high validity of data⁵. The DNPR allows identification of medical conditions via diagnostic codes, examinations, surgical and other procedures at the hospital-based encounter. The positive predictive values vary for conditions defined using the DNPR, however, validation studies are available for many algorithms and these in general show high validity⁶. The National Prescription Registry collects high-quality data on redeemed prescriptions at the

⁴ Schmidt M, Pedersen L, Sorensen HT. The Danish Civil Registration System as a tool in epidemiology. *Eur J Epidemiol.* 2014;29(8):541-549. doi:[10.1007/s10654-014-9930-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10654-014-9930-3)

⁵ Bliddal M, Broe A, Pottgard A, Olsen J, Langhoff-Roos J. The Danish Medical Birth Register. *Eur J Epidemiol.* 2018;33(1):27-36. doi:[10.1007/s10654-018-0356-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10654-018-0356-1)

⁶ Schmidt M, Schmidt SA, Sandegaard JL, Ehrenstein V, Pedersen L, Sorensen HT. The Danish National Patient Registry: a review of content, data quality, and research potential. *Clin Epidemiol.* 2015;7:449-490. doi:[10.2147/CLEP.S91125](https://doi.org/10.2147/CLEP.S91125)

Danish community pharmacies; however, the information on the indication, prescribed duration of use and dosage is not available⁷.

Data bank	Type	Dates covered (for CONSIGN project)
The Danish Civil registration system (CRS)	Inhabitant registry	From 1969 onward
The Danish National Patient Registry (DNPR)	Hospital-based encounters (inpatient and outpatient specialist clinic encounters)	From 1995 onward
The Danish Medical Birth Registry (MBR)	Birth registry	From 1997 onward
The Danish National Prescription Registry	Dispensation of medicines in community pharmacies	From 1995 onward

France: **Système National des Données de Santé (SNDS)**

The SNDS (Système National des Données de Santé) is the French nationwide healthcare database. It currently covers the overall French population (about 67 million persons) from birth (or immigration) to death (or emigration), even if a subject changes occupation or retires. Using a unique pseudonymized identifier, the SNDS merges all reimbursed outpatient claims from all French health care insurance schemes (SNIIRAM database), hospital-discharge summaries from French public and private hospitals (PMSI database), and the national death registry. SNDS data are available since 2006 and contains information on: General characteristics: gender, year of birth, area of residence, etc. Death: month, year and cause. Long-Term Disease registration associated with an ICD-10 diagnostic codes. Outpatient reimbursed healthcare expenditures with dates and codes (but not the medical indication nor result): visits, medical procedures, nursing acts, physiotherapy, lab tests, dispensed drugs and medical devices, etc. For each expenditure, associated costs, prescriber and caregiver information (specialty, private/public practice) and the corresponding dates are provided. Inpatients details: primary, related and associated ICD-10 diagnostic codes resulting from hospital discharge summaries with the date and duration of the hospital stay, the performed medical procedures, and the related costs. Drugs included in the diagnosis related group cost are not captured. However, expensive drugs (i.e. the one charged in addition to the group cost) are. COVID19: To date, only hospitalized COVID-19 cases are captured by the SNDS through the ICD-10 hospital discharge diagnoses codes U07.1. Testing for SARS-CoV2 in outpatient settings can be tracked through French CCAM procedures codes but results are not recorded. Bordeaux PharmacoEpi (BPE), a research platform of the University of

⁷ Pottegard A, Schmidt SAJ, Wallach-Kildemoes H, Sorensen HT, Hallas J, Schmidt M. Data Resource Profile: The Danish National Prescription Registry. *Int J Epidemiol.* 2017;46(3):798-798f. doi:[10.1093/ije/dyw213](https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyw213)

Bordeaux specialized in real world studies, will be Data Access Provider for SNDS data. Given the very broad inclusion criteria, a representative 1/10th sample of the full SNDS will be used (around 6.7 million patients).

Quality of the data banks and linkage

The French national claims database (Système National des Données de Santé, SNDS) includes information on all healthcare expenses reimbursed among 99% of the population from 2006, linking 3 distinct databases on an individual level:

- DCIR (Datamart de Consommation Inter Régime – outpatient healthcare): all outpatient visits, dispensed medication, procedures, chronic conditions, socio-demographics data...
- PMSI (Programme de Médicalisation des Systèmes d'Information – inpatient healthcare): all hospital admission with diagnoses (ICD10), duration, inpatient visits, lab tests and procedures,
- CepadC (Centre d'épidémiologie sur les causes médicales de Décès - national death registry): date and causes of death.

For each of these databases, data are collected locally from the social security card ('Carte Vitale'), treatment forms, private institution invoices and procedures and outpatient visits billed by public hospitals. At this level, data are inevitably linked to the patient's name to ensure reimbursement, by the Caisse Nationale d'Assurance Maladie (CNAM) via the unique personal identification number (NIR) of the patient which is deidentified using 2 successive hash scrambling operations (FOIN). This irreversible algorithm allows the linkage of the different databases but does not permit to return to the original NIR or to the patient's identification. A data quality and consistency plan, common to all national health insurance schemes, ensures homogeneous data processing. Data quality control is performed at several levels: at the time of acquisition of data derived from electronic exchanges, at the time of data entry in a data processing center, and then after coding before integration in the national data warehouse. Secure data flow is performed daily for the general scheme, monthly for other schemes and both monthly and annually (consolidated database) for hospital information. (Bezin et al, 2017; Tuppin et al, 2017)

SNDS data are extracted and can be accessed in different versions, corresponding to the different levels of data quality check ("consolidation") and different lag times:

- Complete and consolidated SNDS data for Year N are available in Q4 Year N+1 (i.e., consolidated data from the Year 2022 will be available at the end of 2023). This is the version ensuring the highest level of data accuracy and completeness.
- Unconsolidated SNDS data for a month N are available with a 4-month lag, with the first data of the year made available in May (i.e., unconsolidated data from Q1 2022 will be available in Q3 2022). This version relies on data that have not passed through all the validation steps executed by the French Health Insurance (CNAM), hospital diagnoses

may be missing or inexact. This version should not be used to work on outcome assessment.

Data bank	Type	Dates covered
PMSI	Inpatient healthcare database	Data extracted for this project: 2015-01-01/2020-12-31 for patients selected on 2017-2020
DCIR	Outpatient healthcare database	Data extracted for this project: 2015-01-01/2020-12-31 for patients selected on 2017-2020
CéPiDC	National death registry	From 2006 to 2017 (for the moment)

Italy: ARS database

The Italian National Health care System is organized at regional level: the national government sets standards of assistance and a tax-based funding for each region, and regional governments are responsible to provide to all their inhabitants. Tuscany is an Italian region, with around 3.6 million inhabitants. The Agenzia Regionale di Sanita' della Toscana (ARS) is a research institute of the Tuscany Region. The ARS database comprises all information that are collected by the Tuscany Region to account for the health care delivered to its inhabitants. Moreover, ARS collects data from regional initiatives. All the data in the ARS data source can be linked with each other at the individual level, through a pseudo-anonymous identifier. The ARS database routinely collects primary care and secondary care prescriptions of drugs for outpatient use, and is able to link them at the individual level with hospital admissions, admissions to emergency care, records of exemptions from copayment, diagnostic tests and procedures, causes of death, mental health services registry, birth registry, spontaneous abortion registry, induced terminations registry. Mother-child linkage is possible through the birth registry. Vaccine data is available since 2016 for children and since 2019 for adults. COVID-19: COVID-19 is identified via the Tuscan section of the national COVID surveillance registry, which records and follows all persons with a positive test result. This can be integrated with other sources to improve the quality of follow-up study variables.

Quality of the data banks and linkage

The data banks are all originated by the local health units, which have access to a shared regional inhabitant register, therefore identification of the patient in the original data is of high quality. Conversion to the pseudonym at the moment of sharing data with ARS is also managed centrally. Each data bank is subject to control at regional level, according to the purpose of the data bank (reimbursement and/or surveillance). Subsequently at the moment of the (approximately bimonthly) transmission to ARS, data is subject to internal consistency control by comparing

monthly prevalence or records and of main variables with the past data. Control is shared with investigators in a dashboard.

Data bank	Type	Dates covered
ARS ANAG MED RES storico	inhabitant registry	from 2003
CAP	birth registry	from 2003
ABS	spontaneous abortions	from 2003
IVG	induced abortions	from 2003
SDO	hospital discharge records	from 2003
SPF	dispensation of medicines in community pharmacies	from 2003
FED	dispensations of medicines from hospital pharmacies for outpatient use	from 2003
SEA	exemptions from copayment	from 2003
PS	emergency admissions	from 2010
SPA	ambulatory procedures	from 2004
SALM	mental health services	from 2010
VCN	vaccinations	from 2019
COVID_DATASET	COVID vaccination registry	from 2020
SPC	primary care community activities	from 2010

Norway: Norwegian linked registries

The core data that UIO has access to is the health care administrative databases of the entire Norwegian population, which amounts to approximately 5.3 million inhabitants. Norway has a universal public health care system, consisting of primary health care services and specialist health care services. Many population-based health registries were established in the 1960s, with use of a unique personal identifier facilitating linkage between registries. The mandatory national health registries were established to maintain national functions. They are used for health analysis, health statistics, improving the quality of health care, research, administration and emergency preparedness. Since January 2004, all pharmacies in Norway have been obliged to send data electronically to the Norwegian Institute of Public Health on all prescribed drugs (irrespective of reimbursement) dispensed to individuals in ambulatory care.

The Norwegian data sources, in this project are the national, mandatory Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS), which will be linked to four national health registries, i.e. the Medical Birth Registry (MBRN), the National Patient Register, the Norwegian Immunisation Registry, and the National Prescription Registry. Information about all Norwegian National Registries can be found here: www.fhi.no/en/more/access-to-data/about-the-national-health-registries2/

Quality of the data banks and linkage

All registries have extensive quality control procedures and deliver quality assured data files to researchers. University of Oslo (UiO) is the Data Access Provider for Norwegian linked registry data in CONSIGN. UiO performs additional internal quality controls of variable missingness, outliers checks, etc. In general data, data have low degree of missingness with a few exceptions (e.g. MBRN: smoking in pregnancy, previous pregnancy loss and employment > 7% missing).

Linkage between data banks is complete as the linkage is performed using the personal ID allocated to every citizen in Norway and all the registries are mandatory by law.

Data bank	Type	Dates covered
MSIS	Communicable diseases registry – COVID-19 positive test	2018-01-01/2021-10-31
MBRN	Birth Registry – identification of pregnancies	2018-01-01/2021-10-31
NorPD	Prescription registry – identification of medication use	2018-01-01/2021-10-31
NPR	Patient registry (secondary care) - COVID-19 diagnosis	2018-01-01/2021-10-31
SYSVAK	Vaccine registry – identification of vaccines	2018-01-01/2021-10-31
KUHR	Primary care registry- COVID-19 diagnosis	2018-01-01/2021-10-31

Spain: IACS Aragon

The EpiChron Research Group at the Instituto Aragonés de Ciencias de la Salud (IACS) provides the data. The source of data for this study will be the PRECOVID study and the EpiChron Cohort. The PRECOVID study includes all individuals with laboratory-confirmed infection by SARS-CoV-2 from an ad hoc registry developed by the Aragon Health System for monitoring the evolution of the COVID-19 disease pandemic in the region of Aragon. This registry links, at a patient level and in a pseudo-anonymized way, the information contained in the users' database, primary care EHRs and primary care and hospital pharmaceutical billing records. The EpiChron Cohort Study links socio-demographic and clinical anonymized information of all the inhabitants of Aragon, built from the BIGAN platform. Aragon BIGAN platform integrates a technical infrastructure and a data lake gathering individual patient data from the regional health service information systems, including primary care, specialized care, hospitalisations, ER episodes, drug prescription, image diagnosis, laboratory analytical determinations, diagnostics, vaccination, anamnesis and demographics from the whole population of Aragon, about 2M subjects with historic data, and 1.3 M active population subjects. Mother-child linkage and some information regarding labour outcomes are possible through hospital birth registry.

Quality of the data banks and linkage

The BIGAN platform includes several mechanisms to control and improve the quality of its data, mainly in the ETL processes of capture and persistence in the data lake. Among these

mechanisms, there are validation rules (for example, for dates and time intervals) or crosses with master tables, requiring that certain coded data exist in a standardized dictionary. Analysis of the distribution of variables is also carried out periodically, in search of "outliers" that identify errors in the data capture or transformation processes. As a general rule, records that do not validate QA procedures are kept in a "staging" area, in order to be reviewed and discarded or reprocessed.

Linkage between data banks is complete as the linkage is performed using an anonymized ID based on personal ID allocated to every citizen in Aragon.

Data bank	Type	Dates covered
COVID-19	Ad-hoc registry developed for monitoring the evolution of the COVID-19 disease pandemic	2020-03-31/2021-12-31
DISPENSACIONES	Medicines dispensed by a community pharmacy office	2018-01-01/2021-12-31
DIAGNOSTICOS	Reason for consultation Primary care	2018-01-01/2021-12-31
CMBD	Hospital discharge reports	2018-01-01/2021-12-31
BDU	Users database	2018-01-01/2021-12-31
CARTILLA_EMBARAZO	First visit for pregnancy control	2018-01-01/2021-12-31

Spain: Valencia Integrated Databases (VID)

The Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencia Region (FISABIO) is Data Access Provider for Valencia Integrated Databases (VID), through the Health Services Research and Pharmacoepidemiology Unit (HSRU). The Valencia health system integrated database (VID) is a set of multiple, public, population-wide electronic databases for the Valencia Region, the fourth most populated Spanish region, with ≈ 5 million inhabitants and an annual birth cohort of 32,000 newborns, representing 10.7% of the Spanish population and around 1% of the European population. The VID provides exhaustive longitudinal information including sociodemographic and administrative data (sex, age, nationality, etc.), clinical (diagnoses, procedures, diagnostic tests, imaging, etc.), pharmaceutical (prescription, dispensation) and health care utilisation data from hospital care, emergency departments, specialized care (including mental and obstetrics care), primary care and other public health services. It also includes a set of associated population databases and registries of significant care areas such as cancer, rare diseases, vaccines, congenital anomalies, microbiology and others, and also public health databases from the population screening programmes. All electronic health systems in the VID use the ICD-9-CM and the ICD-10-CM. The databases were initiated at different moments in time, but all in all the VID provides comprehensive individual-level data fed by all the databases from 2008 to date. Information on PCR test results as well as serological/antibody tests results for the whole population of the Valencia region is available and linkable from the Microbiological Surveillance Network (RedMIVA).

Quality of the data banks and linkage

The extraction of data for any study from the VID to the FISABIO-HSRU is performed following the ENCePP's Guide. After the protocol is presented, it is revised through three supervising committees to obtain the corresponding approvals/classifications (Ethical Committee, Spanish Medicines Agency, and Data Access Commission). Once the extraction is completed, quality control is performed by two independent senior data managers and the outputs are reviewed by a senior epidemiologist. After a double quality check, the extracted data are persisted or corrected, and the statistical analyses are performed using adequate statistical software (Stata and/or R). All results are reviewed by at least one researcher who is not involved in the analysis and a senior epidemiologist.

All the information in the VID databases can be linked at the individual level through a single personal identification code.

Data bank	Type	Dates covered
AEHR	Ambulatory Electronic Health Records (Includes primary, specialist care and active diagnoses)	2018-01-01/2021-12-31
GAIA	Electronic Pharmaceutical records;	2018-01-01/2021-12-31
AED	Accident & Emergency Department record (Emergency room visits);	2018-01-01/2021-12-31
MBDS	Hospital admissions	2018-01-01/2021-12-31
MDR	Metabolic Disease Registry and to identify pregnancies	2018-01-01/2021-12-31
PMR	Perinatal Mortality Registry	2018-01-01/2020-12-31
EOS	Electronic Obstetric Sheet	2018-01-01/2021-12-31
RedMIVA	Microbiological Surveillance Network of the Valencian Community (Includes all PCR or Antigen test results).	2020-03-01/2021-12-31

United Kingdom: Wales, Swansea University

The Secure Anonymised Information Linkage (SAIL) Databank sources, accesses, links and analyses prospectively collected routine health and population data, within a governed infrastructure that is safe and secure. All datasets are anonymised and encrypted by a third party, and returned to SAIL for linkage. Data are held on 5, 400,000 people, since 1998. Data are available within 3 months of events. SAIL holds linkable, anonymised national datasets, including: Accident and emergency care from 2009, Critical care from 2016, Congenital Anomaly Register and Information Service for Wales (CARIS), In-patient and out-patient PEDW records, Maternity dataset from 2015 for additional data on childbirth, National Community Child Health Database (NCCHD, includes gestation (ultrasound), birth centiles, childbirth, infant feeding, developmental screening and vaccinations), National Pupil Database

Wales (education attainment to 16), ONS births and deaths (compulsory registration), Primary care data (including all prescriptions and diagnoses) from ~75% of Welsh GP practices. COVID-19: SAIL receives a daily extract from the national laboratory system containing COVID-19 test results from all sources (both public and private testing). This dataset is available in SAIL and previously linked to other datasets in the data bank, as above. Swansea University will be Data Access Provider for the SAIL data in this project.

Quality of the data banks and linkage

Swansea University is the Data Access Provider for the Wales national linked registry data (SAIL databank)⁸ which is used in CONSIGN. Swansea University performs additional internal quality controls of variable missingness, outliers' checks, and correspondence between datasets. In general data, data have low degree of missingness with a few exceptions (e.g., 11.04% women do not have credible data for obesity. In contrast, ~1% have missing data on socio-economic status, <1% have missing data for birth weight, and gestation is available for all birth.

Approximately 20% of women do not have primary care data in SAIL, because some primary care providers, general practitioners (GPs) do not contribute to the national databank. (GPs are independent contractors to the NHS Health Boards, and cannot be compelled to provide data; they are not reimbursed for participation.) Individuals' presence in the data is determined by an algorithm.⁹

The SAIL Programme has implemented an ISO 27001 Information Security Management System (ISMS), which was externally certified by independent industry assessors in DEC 2015.

<https://saildatabank.com/faq/>

Linkage between data banks is complete as the linkage is performed using each person's unique ALF (anonymous linking field) based on personal information and the NHS (National Health Service) number, when available (<https://saildatabank.com/about-us/data-linkage/>).¹⁰

Data bank	Type	Dates covered
SAIL	Linked databank	2018-01-01/2021-12-31
NCCHD	Birth registrations	2018-01-01/2021-12-31
MIDS	Maternity indicators dataset	2018-01-01/2021-12-31
GP records and prescribing	Primary care records	2018-01-01/2021-12-31
Hospital admissions	By ICD10 codes (not included here)	2018-01-01/2021-12-31

8 Ford DV, Jones KH, Verplancke JP, Lyons RA, John G, Brown G, Brooks CJ, Thompson S, Bodger O, Couch T, Leake K. The SAIL Databank: building a national architecture for e-health research and evaluation. *BMC Health Serv Res.* 2009 Sep 4;9:157. doi: 10.1186/1472-6963-9-157. PMID: 19732426; PMCID: PMC2744675.

9 Thayer D, Rees A, Kennedy J, Collins H, Harris D, Halcox J, Ruschetti L, Noyce R, Brooks C. Measuring follow-up time in routinely-collected health datasets: Challenges and solutions. *PLoS One.* 2020 Feb 11;15(2):e0228545. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0228545. PMID: 32045428; PMCID: PMC7012444.

10 Jones KH, Ford DV, Thompson S, Lyons RA. A Profile of the SAIL Databank on the UK Secure Research Platform. *Int J Popul Data Sci.* 2019 Nov 20;4(2):1134. doi: 10.23889/ijpds.v4i2.1134. PMID: 34095541; PMCID: PMC8142954.

Annex 3. Details of the DAP-specific data banks used for different aspects of the study

Table 45 Data banks used to identify pregnancy start and end date

DAP	Data banks used to identify pregnancy start and end date	Explanation
ARS	Birth registry, spontaneous abortion registry, termination registry, hospital discharge records, recordings of diagnostic procedures.	Pregnancy start: date of record minus gestational age if extracted from a registry; otherwise, estimated based on the diagnostic code, or on the period of pregnancy when the procedure is first expected, based on an <i>a priori</i> rule Pregnancy end: date of record if a registry; or a record with a diagnostic/ procedure code implying end of pregnancy; if the pregnancy is based only on 'red' records, the end of pregnancy is the date of the last record of the pregnancy.
Aarhus University	Birth registry (MFR): all live- and stillbirths after 22 complete gestational weeks	Pregnancy end: Date of delivery Pregnancy start = Date of delivery – gestational length in days
BPE	National healthcare database (SNDS), including inpatient (PMSI) and outpatient (DCIR) healthcare databases	A specific SNDS algorithm (Blotière et al, 2018) is executed on the extracted data (DCIR and PMSI), estimating the theoretical start date, end date and type of pregnancy. Pregnancy start dates are calculated from: 1. pregnancy outcome dates. Exact admission, discharge, and medical procedure dates recorded in inpatient data. 2. gestational ages or numbers of days after the last menstrual period (LMP). Gestational age is recorded in the inpatient data and expressed in completed gestational weeks. For inpatient abortions and other pregnancy outcomes, the number of days after the LMP is recorded. The median gestational ages observed in the inpatient data in 2014 is used to replace missing gestational ages or numbers of days after the LMP according to the type of pregnancy outcome. Pregnancy end dates are identified on the basis of pregnancy outcome from the outpatient database for outpatient medical abortions and from the inpatient database for all other pregnancy outcomes. The algorithm searches the database for discharge diagnoses and medical procedures indicative of completion of a pregnancy Pregnancy outcomes estimated from the algorithm: <i>PRE1</i> = VTP (<i>voluntary termination of pregnancy</i>) <i>PRE2</i> = MTP (<i>medical termination of pregnancy</i>) <i>PRE3</i> = VTP or MTP

		<p><i>PRE4 = ectopic pregnancy</i></p> <p><i>PRE5 = spontaneous miscarriage</i></p> <p><i>PRE6 = hydatid mole</i></p> <p><i>PRE7 = other abnormal products of conception</i></p> <p><i>PRE8 = medicated VTP</i></p> <p><i>PRE9 = MTP after 22 weeks of amenorrhea</i></p> <p><i>PRE10 = still-birth</i></p> <p><i>PRE11 = live-birth</i></p>
FISABIO-HSRU	<p>In the Valencia Integrated Database (VID) the information about pregnancies can be extracted from registry databases (MDR, PMR and EOS) or from Diagnostic codes databases (PRIMARY_CARE_VISITS, CEX, MBDS, AED, DIAGNOSTICS).</p> <p>- MDR (Metabolic Diseases Registry) Deliveries.</p> <p>- PMR (Perinatal Mortality Registry): Stillbirth, neonatal death</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">a. EOS (Electronic Obstetric Sheet): Deliveries, Spontaneous abortions, stillbirth.</p> <p>PRIMARY_CARE_VISITS, CEX, MBDS, AED, DIAGNOSTICS are databases used for extraction of diagnostic or procedure codes in the pregnancy algorithm.</p>	<p>For the registry databases, the start of pregnancy is the date of LMP. The end of pregnancy is the date of delivery or abortion (elective/spontaneous).</p> <p>Pregnancy end: Date of delivery (live or stillbirth), date of abortion or miscarriage.</p> <p>Pregnancy start:</p> <p>-For those with gestational age available (around 90% of deliveries) = Date of delivery minus gestational age in weeks. Gestational age is estimated based on ultrasound.</p> <p>- For those without gestational age available (around 10% of deliveries) = Date of delivery minus 40 weeks when newborns' weight is 2500 gr or above; AND through a linear regression model when newborns' weight under 2500 gr.</p> <p>For the diagnostic codes databases, the period of pregnancy is estimated based on the diagnostic code, or on the period of pregnancy when the procedure is first expected, based on a predictive model.</p>
IACS	<p>The pregnancy control data bank (CARTILLA_EMBARAZO) captures information from all pregnancy related visits, including the date of the LMP, which is recorded at the first visit. The end of pregnancy is obtained from the date of the pregnancy delivery or abortion recorded in primary care or hospital discharge. For those pregnancies without information of delivery or abortion prior to the end of the study (31th December 2021), these were considered to be ongoing at that date.</p>	<p>Regarding the pregnancy database, pregnancy monitoring is carried out by the obstetrician (specialized care) after referral by the primary care physician if the pregnancy test is positive. Until 2018, all observations related to pregnancy care were written by the obstetrician in a notebook during each follow-up visit: laboratory test results, ultrasound results, other measurements (e.g., blood pressure, BMI). From 2018, this is the same process, but all annotations are made using an electronic form, although most of the information is free text providing comments regarding the evolution of pregnancy. Free text was not extracted for the study.</p>
SWANSEA	<p>National Community Child Health Database (NCCHD), Maternity Indicators Dataset (MIDS)</p>	<p>Births (live and still) are identified as child IDs in NCCHD. NCCHD is based on birth registrations with the Office of National Statistics (ONS), which records all</p>

		<p>legal births in the UK. This data bank does not release information on spontaneous and induced abortions.</p> <p>End date of pregnancy is defined as Monday of the subject's (infant's) week of birth (live birth or stillbirth), to avoid use of identifiable data. Gestational age at birth, based on ultrasound scans, was obtained from NCCHD. Data were checked against MIDS. This improved the completeness of the data. If gestational age was missing or implausible, the pregnancy was excluded/ gestation was estimated for term births from the mean value for the database. In the event, all births had a gestational age.</p>
UiO	<p>Birth registry (MBRN)</p> <p>A record is created for any pregnancy of gestational age 12 weeks or beyond (live, miscarriage, elective abortion, stillbirth), at the end of pregnancy (not during pregnancy).</p>	<p>Pregnancy end: Date of delivery</p> <p>Pregnancy start = Date of delivery – gestational length in days.</p> <p>Gestational length is estimated based on ultrasound. Rarely, when UL is missing, GL is based on the woman's report of the LMP.</p>

Abbreviations: ARS = Agenzia Regionale di Sanita' della Toscana; FISABIO-HSRU = Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencia Region - Health Services Research Unit; IACS = Instituto Aragones de Ciencias de la Salud; SWANSEA = Swansea University; UiO = University of Oslo.

Table 46 Data banks used to identify the presence of medical conditions that increase the risk of hospitalized COVID-19

DAP	Country	Type
ARS	Italy	Hospital discharge records, emergency admissions, exemptions from co-payment, dispensing of medicines from community or hospital pharmacies for outpatient use or inpatient for cancer medicines
Aarhus University	Denmark	Patient Registry (LPR, 1 year look back possible), Prescription registry (LMS, 1 year look back possible)
BPE	France	Inpatient data (PMSI) with Hospital discharge records (ICD10 codes of diagnoses) and for specific drugs (only for expensive/innovative medicines), outpatient data (DCIR) for specific drugs (dispensing of medicines from community or hospital pharmacies for outpatient use).
FISABIO-HSRU	Spain	Ambulatory Electronic Health Records (AEHR) includes primary (PCV) and specialist care (CEX) and active diagnoses (DIAGNOSTICS) (1 year look-back), Electronic pharmaceutical records (GAIA) (1 year look-back), Accident & Emergency Department record (AED) (1 year look-back) Hospital admission (MBDS) (1 year look-back)
IACS	Spain	Dispensed medicines from community pharmacies (1 year look back)
SWANSEA	Wales	Primary care (GP) database, Hospital admissions (PEDW). Maternity Indicators Dataset (MIDS)
UiO	Norway	Norwegian Patient Registry (NPR) (1 year look back) Norwegian Prescription Database (NorPD) (1 year look back)

Abbreviations: ARS = Agenzia Regionale di Sanita' della Toscana; BPE = Bordeaux PharmacoEpi platform; FISABIO-HSRU = Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencia Region - Health Services Research Unit; IACS = Instituto Aragonés de Ciencias de la Salud; SWANSEA = Swansea University; UiO = University of Oslo.

Table 47 Data banks used to identify positive test or diagnosis for COVID-19

DAP	Type	Explanation
ARS	Registry COVID-19	This is the official surveillance system of the pandemic. Several variables are collected on the case and during the first year of the pandemic the variables were updated during the disease.
Aarhus University	NA	NA
BPE	Inpatient data (PMSI) with ICD10 codes of COVID-diagnoses.	No laboratory positive test result available
FISABIO-HSRU	RedMIVA (Microbiological Surveillance Network of the Valencian Community)	All positive PCR or antigen test results are recorded
IACS	Registry developed for monitoring the evolution of the COVID-19 disease pandemic in the region of Aragon	All PCR or antigen test results are recorded
SWANSEA	COVID-19 Test results dataset available from healthdatagateway.org	All test results and symptom trackers
UiO	MSIS (Norwegian surveillance system for communicable diseases)	Laboratory confirmed positive test

Abbreviations: ARS = Agenzia Regionale di Sanita' della Toscana; BPE = Bordeaux PharmacoEpi platform; FISABIO-HSRU = Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencia Region - Health Services Research Unit; IACS = Instituto Aragonés de Ciencias de la Salud; PCR = polymerase chain reaction; SWANSEA = Swansea University; UiO = University of Oslo.
 NA: Not applicable

Table 48 Data bank(s) used by each DAP to identify maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes

DAP	Type of databank
ARS	CAP1, SDO, IVG, SPA, SPC, ABS, SALM
Aarhus University	Medical Birth registry (MFR), National patient register (LPR)
BPE	Mainly inpatient data (PMSI) with ICD10 codes of diagnoses, biological (NABM) and medical procedures (CCAM codes) indicative of completion of a pregnancy. Outpatient data (DCIR) for some specific codes of termination.
FISABIO-HSRU	Maternal outcomes from hospital admissions (MBDS) and emergency visits (AED). In addition, for neonatal outcomes, we also use the information from Perinatal mortality registry (PMR) and Congenital Anomalies Registry (CONG).
IACS	Maternal outcomes from hospital admissions, emergency room visits or primary care diagnosis. Neonatal outcomes from hospital birth registry.
SWANSEA	ONS births and deaths (via NCCHD for births), NCCHD for breastfeeding, gestation length, SGA, HV assessments, PEDW for hospital admissions, primary care database (WLGP) for prescriptions and diagnoses, MIDS for BMI/ obesity, illness in pregnancy, Apgar scores, sections, birth wt. CARIS for congenital anomalies.
UiO	Medical Birth registry (MBRN)

Abbreviations: ARS = Agenzia Regionale di Sanita' della Toscana; BPE = Bordeaux PharmacoEpi platform; FISABIO-HSRU = Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencia Region - Health Services Research Unit; IACS = Instituto Aragonés de Ciencias de la Salud; PCR = polymerase chain reaction; SWANSEA = Swansea University; UiO = University of Oslo.

Annex 4. ATC-levels 2-3-4-5 of medicines of special relevance to COVID-19

ATC level 2 name	ATC level 2 code	ATC level 3 name	ATC level 3 code	ATC level 4 name	ATC level 4 code	ATC level 5 name	ATC level 5 code
Drugs used in diabetes	A10						
Antithrombotic agents	B01	Antithrombotic agents	B01A	Heparin group	B01AB	heparin (unfractionated) enoxaparin (Low molecular weight heparin) acetylsalicylic acid	B01AB01 B01AB05 B01AC06
Antihypertensives	C02 C03 C04 C07 C08 C09						
Corticosteroids for systemic use	H02	Glucocorticoids for systematic use, plain	H02A	Glucocorticoids	H02AB	dexamethasone betamethasone hydrocortisone methylprednisolone prednisolone	H02AB02 H02AB01 H02AB09 H02AB04 H02AB06
Antibacterials for systemic use	J01	Beta-lactam antibacterials, penicillins	J01C	Penicillins with extended spectrum	J01CA	Amoxicillin Ampicillin ampicillin, combinations	J01CA04 J01CA01 J01CA51
				Combination of penicillins, including beta-lactamase inhibitors	J01CR	Piperacilline and beta-lactamase inhibitor ampicillin and beta-lactamase inhibitor amoxicillin and beta-lactamase inhibitor	J01CR05 J01CR01 J01CR02

ATC level 2 name	ATC level 2 code	ATC level 3 name	ATC level 3 code	ATC level 4 name	ATC level 4 code	ATC level 5 name	ATC level 5 code		
		Other beta-lactam antibacterials (J01D)	J01D	First generation cephalosporins	J01DB	cefalexin	J01DB01		
						cefazolin	J01DB04		
				Second generation cephalosporins	J01DC	Third-generation cephalosporins	J01DD	cefuroxime	J01DC02
								cefotaxime	J01DD01
								ceftazidime	J01DD02
								ceftriaxone	J01DD04
								cefixime	J01DD08
								cefodizime	J01DD09
						Fourth-generation cephalosporins	J01DE	cefepime	J01DE01
						Carbapenems	J01DH	meropenem	J01DH02
		Macrolides, Lincosamides and Streptogramins	J01F	Macrolides	J01FA	azithromycin	J01FA10		
						clarithromycin	J01FA09		
						erythromycin	J01FA01		
				Lincosamides	J01FF	clindamycin	J01FF01		
		Aminoglycoside antibacterials	J01G	Other aminoglycosides	J01GB	amikacin	J01GB06		
						gentamicin	J01GB03		
		Other antibacterials	J01X	Glycopeptide antibacterials	J01XA	vancomycin	J01XA01		
						teicoplanin	J01XA02		
Antimycotics	J02								
Antimycobacterials	J04								
Antivirals for systemic use	J05	Direct acting antivirals	J05A	Nucleosides and nucleotides excl. Reverse transcriptase inhibitors	J05AB	remdesivir	J05AB16		

ATC level 2 name	ATC level 2 code	ATC level 3 name	ATC level 3 code	ATC level 4 name	ATC level 4 code	ATC level 5 name	ATC level 5 code
				Antivirals for treatment of HIV infections, combinations	J05AR	lopinavir-ritonavir	J05AR10
				Neuraminidase inhibitors	J05AH	oseltamivir	J05AH02
				Antivirals for treatment of HCV infections, combinations	J05AP	Ribavirin	J05AP01
			/	/	/	molnupiravir	No ATC code available
			/	/	/	nirmatrelvir	No ATC code available
				Other antivirals	J05AX	favipiravir	J05AX27
Immune sera and globulins	J06	Immunoglobulins	J06B	Antiviral monoclonal antibodies	J06BD	casirivimab-imdevimab (anti-SARS-CoV2 mABs) tixagevimab-cilgavimab (anti-SARS-CoV2 mABs) bamlanivimab, bamlanivimab + etesevimab sotrovimab (anti-SARS-CoV2 mABs)	No ATC code available No ATC code available No ATC code available
			/	/	/	plasma of convalescent	No ATC code available
			/	/	/	plasma of convalescent	No ATC code available
				Immunoglobulins, normal human	J06BA	IV Immunoglobulins	J06BA02

ATC level 2 name	ATC level 2 code	ATC level 3 name	ATC level 3 code	ATC level 4 name	ATC level 4 code	ATC level 5 name	ATC level 5 code
Vaccinations	J07	Viral vaccines	J07B	Other viral vaccines	J07BX	COVID-19 vaccines	J07BX03
Antineoplastic agents	L01	Protein kinase inhibitors	L01E	BCR-ABL tyrosine kinase inhibitors	L01EA	imatinib	L01EA01
				Janus-associated kinase (JAK) inhibitors	L01EJ	ruxolitinib	L01EJ01
Immunostimulants	L03	Immunostimulants	L03A	Interferons	L03AB		
Immunosuppressants	L04	Immunosuppressants	L04A	Selective immunosuppressants	L04AA	Baricitinib	L04AA37
						tofacitinib (kinase inhibitor)	L04AA29
				Interleukin inhibitors	L04AC	tocilizumab (IL6 receptor blockers)	L04AC07
						sarilumab (IL6 receptor blockers)	L04AC14
						anakinra (Interleukin-1 Inhibitors)	L04AC03
canakinumab (Interleukin-1 Inhibitors)	L04AC08						
Calcineurin inhibitors	L04AD	ciclosporin	L04AD01				
Anti-inflammatory drugs	M01						
Antigout preparations	M04	Antigout preparations	M04A	Preparations with no effect on uric acid metabolism	M04AC	colchicine	M04AC01
Analgesics	N02	Other analgesics and antipyretics	N02B	Anilides	N02BE	paracetamol	N02BE01
Psycholeptics	N05						
Psychoanaleptics	N06	Antidepressants	N06A	Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors	N06AB	fluvoxamine	N06AB08
Antiprotozoals	P01	Agents against amoebiasis and other protozoals diseases	P01A	Nitroimidazole derivatives	P01AB	metronidazole	P01AB01

ATC level 2 name	ATC level 2 code	ATC level 3 name	ATC level 3 code	ATC level 4 name	ATC level 4 code	ATC level 5 name	ATC level 5 code
		Antimalarials	P01B	Other agents against amoebiasis and other protozoals diseases Aminoquinolines	P01AX	nitazoxanide	P01AX11
					P01BA	Chloroquine hydroxychloroquine	P01BA01 P01BA02
Anthelmintics	P02	Antinematodal agents	P02C	Avermectines	P02CF	ivermectin	P02CF01
Nasal preparations	R01						
Medicines for obstructive airway disease	R03	Adrenergics, inhalants		Selective beta-2-adrenoreceptor agonists	R03AC	Salbutamol	R03AC02
Cough and cold preparations	R05						

Annex 5. Details of data transformation to the ConcePTION common data model

This study was conducted in a distributed manner using a common protocol, common data model (CDM), and common analytics programs. This process was used successfully in several other European multi-database projects. The data pipeline has been further improved in the IMI-ConcePTION project (<https://www.imi-conception.eu/>). This process maximized the involvement of the data providers in the study by utilizing their knowledge on the characteristics and the process underlying the data collection which made analysis more efficient.

First, to harmonize the structure of the data sets held by each partner, a shared syntactic foundation was utilized. Syntactic foundation is described in Annex 1 and refers to the syntactically harmonized CDM. In this common data model, data were represented in a common structure but the content of the data remained in their original format.

Second, to reconcile differences across terminologies a shared semantic foundation was built for the definition of events under study by collecting relevant concepts in a structured fashion using a standardized event definition template. The Codemapper tool was used to create diagnosis code lists based upon completed event definition templates for each AESI and comorbid risk condition (Becker et al., 2017). Based on the relevant diagnostic medical codes and keywords one or more algorithms were constructed (typically one sensitive, or broad, algorithm and one specific, or narrow algorithm) to operationalize the identification and measurement of each event by medically trained persons. These algorithms can differ per database. No validation was done for this study, as there were no resources for this within the budget of the EMA tender. Wherever possible the event definition sheet specified prior validation of algorithms and codes. Scripts for semantic harmonization were coded in R, distributed to data access providers for local deployment, and shared on the catalogue. The impact of choices of different algorithms were assessed quantitatively. This resulted in a set of study variables which were both semantically and syntactically harmonized.

Third, following conversion to harmonized study variable sets, R programs for calculation of incidence and prevalence were distributed to data access providers for local deployment. The aggregated results produced by these scripts were then uploaded to the Digital Research Environment (DRE) for pooled analysis and visualization (see Figure 2). The DRE was made available through UMCU/VAC4EU (<https://www.andrea-consortium.org/>). The DRE is a cloud based, globally available research environment where data is stored and organized securely and where researchers can collaborate (<https://www.andrea-consortium.org/azure-dre/>).

Figure 2 Data management plan

1.1.1 Data extraction

Each database access provider (DAP) created ETL specifications using the standard ConcePTION ETL design template. Following completion of this template and review with study statisticians, each DAP extracted the relevant study data locally using their software (eg Stata, SAS, R, Oracle). This data was loaded into the CDM structure in csv format. These data remained local (Figure 2). Data that were loaded to the CDM were verified using quality checks (level 1 and 2). Specifics of quality checks can be found at the IMI-ConcePTION website.

1.1.2 Data engineering and analysis

Centrally written R scripts were sent to the DAPs and this script transformed the data in the syntactically harmonized CDM to semantically harmonized study variables (see Figure 2). The R scripts were structured in modular form with validated functions. Functions were either standard R packages or packages designed, developed and tested on purpose for multi-database studies. The DAPs ran the R code locally and sent aggregated analysis results to the anDREa digital research environment using a secure file transfer protocol. In the anDREa platform, results were aggregated using SAS and rates were calculated and plotted using R. DAPs that were not able to share low cell counts ran SAS code locally and submitted the incidence rates. All submitted data was inspected (for quality assessment) and pooled (if needed) for final reporting. All steps were detailed in the statistical plan.

1.1.3 Storage of data

Data access providers had access to the workspace for verification of the scripts. Aggregated results, ETL specifications, and a repository of study scripts were stored in the DRE. Within the DRE, each project-specific area consisted of a separate, secure folder, called a 'workspace'. Each workspace was completely secure, so researchers were in full control of their data. Each workspace had its own list of users, which was managed by its administrators. Access to this workspace was only possible with double authentication using an ID and password together with the user's mobile phone for authentication. Upload of files was possible for all researchers with

access to the workspace within the DRE. Download of files was only possible after requesting and receiving permission from a workspace member with an ‘owner’ role.

1.1.4 Archiving and record retention

Documents that individually and collectively permit evaluation of the conduct of a study and the quality of the data produced will be retained for a period of 5 years in accordance with GPP guidelines. These documents could be retained for a longer period, however, if required by the applicable regulatory requirements or by an agreement between study partners. It is the responsibility of the principal investigator to inform the other investigators/institutions as to when these documents no longer need to be retained. Study records or documents may also include the analyses files, syntaxes (usually stored at the site of the database), ETL specifications, and output of data quality check.

Annex 6. Prevalence of medication use in the cohort of pregnant women with COVID-9 in pregnancy

Total COVID-19 cases

Table 49 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (ARS, total COVID-19 cases)

DAP:ARS	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)
TOTAL COVID-19 cases						
Antibacterials (J01)	6.8 (4.1-11)	12.1 (8.3-17.2)	5.8 (3.6-9.2)	6.9 (4.4-10.5)	5.3 (3.7-7.6)	8.9 (6.7-11.6)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	3.9 (2-7.4)	12.6 (8.7-17.8)	4.3 (2.5-7.4)	16.6 (12.7-21.4)	3.7 (2.4-5.8)	29.5 (25.7-33.6)
Corticosteroids (H02)	2.4 (1-5.5)	8.2 (5.2-12.8)	1.4 (0.6-3.7)	5.4 (3.3-8.7)	2.8 (1.6-4.6)	3.9 (2.6-6)

Table 50 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (BPE, total COVID-19 cases)

DAP:BPE	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)
TOTAL COVID-19 cases						
Analgesics (N02)	42.9 (15.8-75)	28.6 (8.2-64.1)	35.9 (26.8-46.1)	38 (28.8-48.3)	15.3 (13.1-17.7)	71.6 (68.7-74.4)
Antibacterials (J01)	42.9 (15.8-75)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	19.6 (12.7-28.8)	34.8 (25.8-44.9)	6.6 (5.2-8.3)	17.8 (15.6-20.4)
Antimycotics (J02)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	1.1 (0.2-5.9)	4.3 (1.7-10.7)	0.1 (0-0.6)	0.4 (0.2-1.1)
Antiprotozoals (P01)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-4)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	1.1 (0.6-2)	0.3 (0.1-0.9)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	0 (0-35.4)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	3.3 (1.1-9.2)	6.5 (3-13.5)	1.9 (1.2-2.9)	22.8 (20.3-25.5)
Corticosteroids (H02)	0 (0-35.4)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	5.4 (2.3-12.1)	4.3 (1.7-10.7)	2.1 (1.3-3.2)	1.3 (0.8-2.3)
Cough and cold medications (R05)	28.6 (8.2-64.1)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	5.4 (2.3-12.1)	4.3 (1.7-10.7)	1.8 (1.1-2.8)	0.5 (0.2-1.2)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	1.1 (0.2-5.9)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	3.5 (2.5-4.9)	1.2 (0.7-2.1)
Immune sera and globulins (J06)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	1.1 (0.2-5.9)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	0.6 (0.3-1.3)	0.4 (0.2-1.1)
Nasal preparations (R01)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	0 (0-35.4)	12 (6.8-20.2)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	2 (1.3-3)	0.8 (0.4-1.6)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	8.7 (4.5-16.2)	9.8 (5.2-17.6)	1.6 (1-2.7)	2 (1.3-3)
Psychoanaleptics (N06)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	1.1 (0.6-2)	1.1 (0.6-2)
Psycholeptics (N05)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	3.3 (1.1-9.2)	3.3 (1.1-9.2)	1.3 (0.8-2.3)	1.4 (0.9-2.4)

Table 51 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (FISABIO-HSRU, total COVID-19 cases)

DAP:FISABIO-HSRU	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
TOTAL COVID-19 cases						
Analgesics (N02)	2.2 (1.5-3.4)	3.2 (2.2-4.5)	0.9 (0.5-1.8)	3 (2.1-4.4)	1.6 (1-2.5)	3 (2.2-4.2)
Anti_inflammatory drugs (M01)	1.2 (0.7-2.1)	1.6 (1-2.6)	0.4 (0.1-1)	0.7 (0.3-1.5)	0.4 (0.2-1)	2.8 (2-3.9)
Antibacterials (J01)	3.3 (2.3-4.6)	4.3 (3.1-5.7)	3.5 (2.5-5)	5.3 (4-7)	4.5 (3.4-5.8)	5.3 (4.2-6.8)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	2.3 (1.5-3.5)	31 (28.2-34.1)	4.4 (3.3-6)	50.7 (47.4-54)	3.8 (2.9-5.1)	61.9 (59.1-64.6)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	1.6 (1-2.6)	4 (3-5.5)	1.2 (0.6-2.1)	2.8 (1.9-4.1)	0.7 (0.3-1.3)	2.9 (2.1-4)

Table 52 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (IACS, total COVID-19 cases)

DAP:IACS	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
TOTAL COVID-19 cases						
Analgesics (N02)	12.3 (8.5-17.4)	11.3 (7.7-16.3)	11.6 (8.4-15.8)	10.5 (7.5-14.6)	8.9 (6.6-11.8)	14.0 (11.2-17.5)
Anti_inflammatory drugs (M01)	1.9 (0.7-4.8)	1.4 (0.5-4.1)	1.1 (0.4-3)	0.7 (0.2-2.5)	1.3 (0.6-2.8)	9.9 (7.5-13)
Antibacterials (J01)	5.7 (3.3-9.6)	7.5 (4.7-11.9)	5.6 (3.5-8.9)	5.3 (3.2-8.5)	5.2 (3.5-7.6)	8.4 (6.2-11.3)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	5.2 (2.9-9.1)	20.8 (15.8-26.7)	17.9 (13.9-22.8)	37.5 (32.1-43.3)	14.7 (11.8-18.2)	44.7 (40.2-49.3)
Nasal preparations (R01)	1.9 (0.7-4.8)	2.4 (1-5.4)	0.7 (0.2-2.5)	1.1 (0.4-3)	0.4 (0.1-1.6)	0.9 (0.3-2.2)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	1.4 (0.5-4.1)	1.9 (0.7-4.8)	1.1 (0.4-3)	3.9 (2.2-6.8)	1.9 (1-3.7)	3 (1.8-5)
Psychoanaleptics (N06)	3.3 (1.6-6.7)	3.8 (1.9-7.3)	0.7 (0.2-2.5)	0.7 (0.2-2.5)	0.4 (0.1-1.6)	0.4 (0.1-1.6)
Psycholeptics (N05)	2.4 (1-5.4)	2.8 (1.3-6)	0.7 (0.2-2.5)	1.8 (0.8-4)	0.9 (0.3-2.2)	2.6 (1.5-4.5)

Table 53 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (SWANSEA, total COVID-19 cases)

DAP:SWANSEA	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre-infection	30 days post-infection	30 days pre-infection	30 days post-infection	30 days pre-infection	30 days post-infection
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
TOTAL COVID-19 cases						
Analgesics (N02)	2.4 (1.5-4)	2.8 (1.7-4.5)	1.7 (1-3.1)	2.5 (1.5-4)	1.7 (0.9-2.9)	2.2 (1.4-3.5)
Antibacterials (J01)	4.9 (3.4-6.9)	6.4 (4.7-8.7)	6 (4.4-8.1)	6.1 (4.5-8.2)	3.4 (2.3-5)	8.1 (6.3-10.3)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	1.2 (0.6-2.5)	1.7 (0.9-3.2)	2.2 (1.3-3.6)	2.5 (1.5-4)	1.4 (0.7-2.5)	1.2 (0.7-2.3)
Corticosteroids (H02)	*	1 (0.5-2.3)	1.1 (0.5-2.2)	0.8 (0.3-1.8)	*	*
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	*	0.9 (0.4-2)	1.9 (1.1-3.3)	2.2 (1.3-3.6)	1.8 (1-3)	2.1 (1.3-3.4)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	2.4 (1.5-4)	4 (2.7-5.9)	4.5 (3.2-6.5)	5.2 (3.7-7.2)	2.3 (1.5-3.7)	2.9 (1.9-4.4)
Psychoanaleptics (N06)	7.5 (5.6-9.9)	6.4 (4.7-8.7)	6.3 (4.6-8.4)	6.4 (4.8-8.6)	5 (3.6-6.8)	5 (3.6-6.8)

Table 54 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (UIO, total COVID-19 cases)

DAP:UIO	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre	30 days post-
TOTAL COVID-19 cases	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	3.9 (2.1-7.3)	2.6 (1.2-5.6)	2.3 (1.2-4.2)	2.3 (1.2-4.2)	1.4 (0.6-2.9)	4.5 (2.9-6.9)
Antibacterials (J01)	2.6 (1.2-5.6)	4.3 (2.4-7.8)	4.3 (2.7-6.7)	4 (2.5-6.4)	3.4 (2.1-5.5)	7.2 (5.2-10)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	1.7 (0.7-4.4)	1.7 (0.7-4.4)	1.3 (0.5-2.9)	2.5 (1.4-4.6)	0.9 (0.4-2.3)	5.9 (4-8.5)
Cough and cold medications (R05)	0 (0-1.6)	2.2 (0.9-5)	0.3 (0-1.4)	3.3 (1.9-5.5)	0.7 (0.2-2)	2.7 (1.6-4.7)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	0.4 (0.1-2.4)	0 (0-1.6)	0.8 (0.3-2.2)	0.5 (0.1-1.8)	3.4 (2.1-5.5)	2 (1.1-3.8)
Nasal preparations (R01)	0 (0-1.6)	0.9 (0.2-3.1)	1.3 (0.5-2.9)	2.8 (1.6-4.9)	0.5 (0.1-1.6)	0.5 (0.1-1.6)

Hospitalized COVID-19 cases

Table 55 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (ARS, hospitalized COVID-19 cases)

DAP:ARS	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre	30 days post-
HOSPITALIZED COVID-19 cases	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Antibacterials (J01)	11.1 (2-43.5)	33.3 (12.1-64.6)	17.6 (6.2-41)	17.6 (6.2-41)	2.8 (1-8)	8.5 (4.5-15.4)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	0 (0-29.9)	66.7 (35.4-87.9)	5.9 (1-27)	47.1 (26.2-69)	7.5 (3.9-14.2)	50 (40.6-59.4)
Corticosteroids (H02)	11.1 (2-43.5)	33.3 (12.1-64.6)	0 (0-18.4)	23.5 (9.6-47.3)	2.8 (1-8)	9.4 (5.2-16.5)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	11.1 (2-43.5)	0 (0-29.9)	0 (0-18.4)	5.9 (1-27)	0.9 (0.2-5.2)	4.7 (2-10.6)

Table 56 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (BPE, hospitalized COVID-19 cases)

DAP:BPE	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre	30 days post-
HOSPITALIZED COVID-19 cases	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	42.9 (15.8-75)	28.6 (8.2-64.1)	35.9 (26.8-46.1)	38 (28.8-48.3)	21.9 (17-27.7)	59.8 (53.3-66)
Anti_inflammatory drugs (M01)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-4)	0 (0-4)	0 (0-1.7)	2.7 (1.2-5.7)
Antibacterials (J01)	42.9 (15.8-75)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	19.6 (12.7-28.8)	34.8 (25.8-44.9)	7.6 (4.8-11.8)	23.7 (18.6-29.6)
Antimycotics (J02)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	1.1 (0.2-5.9)	4.3 (1.7-10.7)	0.4 (0.1-2.5)	0.4 (0.1-2.5)
Antiprotozoals (P01)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-4)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	1.3 (0.5-3.9)	0.4 (0.1-2.5)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	0 (0-35.4)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	3.3 (1.1-9.2)	6.5 (3-13.5)	3.1 (1.5-6.3)	25.9 (20.6-32)
Antivirals (J05)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	1.1 (0.2-5.9)	1.1 (0.2-5.9)	1.3 (0.5-3.9)	2.2 (1-5.1)
Corticosteroids (H02)	0 (0-35.4)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	5.4 (2.3-12.1)	4.3 (1.7-10.7)	3.6 (1.8-6.9)	3.1 (1.5-6.3)

Cough and cold medications (R05)	28.6 (8.2-64.1)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	5.4 (2.3-12.1)	4.3 (1.7-10.7)	4 (2.1-7.5)	1.8 (0.7-4.5)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	1.1 (0.2-5.9)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	4.9 (2.8-8.6)	3.6 (1.8-6.9)
Immune sera and globulins (J06)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	1.1 (0.2-5.9)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	1.8 (0.7-4.5)	0.9 (0.2-3.2)
Nasal preparations (R01)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	0 (0-35.4)	12 (6.8-20.2)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	4.5 (2.4-8)	0.9 (0.2-3.2)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	8.7 (4.5-16.2)	9.8 (5.2-17.6)	3.1 (1.5-6.3)	2.2 (1-5.1)
Psychoanaleptics (N06)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	1.8 (0.7-4.5)	0.9 (0.2-3.2)
Psycholeptics (N05)	0 (0-35.4)	0 (0-35.4)	3.3 (1.1-9.2)	3.3 (1.1-9.2)	1.8 (0.7-4.5)	2.7 (1.2-5.7)

Table 57 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (FISABIO-HSRU, hospitalized COVID-19 cases)

DAP:FISABIO-HSRU	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)
HOSPITALIZED COVID-19 cases						
Analgesics (N02)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	1.2 (0.2-6.6)	2.4 (0.7-8.5)
Anti_inflammatory drugs (M01)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-4.5)	3.7 (1.3-10.2)
Antibacterials (J01)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	7.3 (3.4-15.1)	8.5 (4.2-16.6)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	0 (0-39)	50 (18.8-81.2)	7.7 (1.4-33.3)	61.5 (35.5-82.3)	2.4 (0.7-8.5)	74.4 (64-82.6)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	4.9 (1.9-11.9)	0 (0-4.5)
Immune sera and globulins (J06)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-22.8)	7.7 (1.4-33.3)	0 (0-4.5)	0 (0-4.5)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-4.5)	3.7 (1.3-10.2)

Table 58 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (IACS, hospitalized COVID-19 cases)

DAP:IACS	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)
HOSPITALIZED COVID-19 cases						
Analgesics (N02)	16.7 (4.7-44.8)	8.3 (1.5-35.4)	22.2 (9-45.2)	16.7 (5.8-39.2)	12.2 (6.5-21.5)	18.9 (11.6-29.3)
Anti_inflammatory drugs (M01)	8.3 (1.5-35.4)	0 (0-24.2)	0 (0-17.6)	5.6 (1-25.8)	0 (0-4.9)	5.4 (2.1-13.1)
Antibacterials (J01)	0 (0-24.2)	16.7 (4.7-44.8)	22.2 (9-45.2)	0 (0-17.6)	4.1 (1.4-11.3)	9.5 (4.7-18.3)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	0 (0-24.2)	41.7 (19.3-68)	16.7 (5.8-39.2)	66.7 (43.7-83.7)	24.3 (16-35.2)	83.8 (73.8-90.5)
Corticosteroids (H02)	0 (0-24.2)	16.7 (4.7-44.8)	0 (0-17.6)	5.6 (1-25.8)	0 (0-4.9)	9.5 (4.7-18.3)
Cough and cold medications (R05)	0 (0-24.2)	0 (0-24.2)	5.6 (1-25.8)	5.6 (1-25.8)	0 (0-4.9)	1.4 (0.2-7.3)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	8.3 (1.5-35.4)	8.3 (1.5-35.4)	0 (0-17.6)	0 (0-17.6)	1.4 (0.2-7.3)	2.7 (0.7-9.3)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	0 (0-24.2)	0 (0-24.2)	0 (0-17.6)	11.1 (3.1-32.8)	0 (0-4.9)	6.8 (2.9-14.9)
Psycholeptics (N05)	0 (0-24.2)	0 (0-24.2)	0 (0-17.6)	5.6 (1-25.8)	0 (0-4.9)	2.7 (0.7-9.3)

Table 59 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (Wales, hospitalized COVID-19 cases)

DAP:SWANSEA	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre-infection	30 days post-infection	30 days pre-infection	30 days post-infection	30 days pre-infection	30 days post-infection
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
HOSPITALIZED COVID-19 cases						
Antibacterials (J01)	*	5.6 (4-7.8)	*	*	2.9 (1.7-4.8)	7.4 (5.4-10)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	*	*	*	1.8 (1-3.2)	*	*
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	*	*	*	*	1.4 (0.7-2.9)	2 (1.1-3.7)
Psychoanaleptics (N06)	*	*		5.8 (4.2-8)	*	4.1 (2.7-6.2)
						5.5 (3.8-7.9)

Table 60 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (UIO, hospitalized COVID-19 cases)

DAP:UIO	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
HOSPITALIZED COVID-19 cases						
Analgesics (N02)	7.7 (1.4-33.3)	0 (0-22.8)	7.7 (2.7-20.3)	7.7 (2.7-20.3)	1.9 (0.5-6.7)	5.8 (2.7-12)
Anti_inflammatory drugs (M01)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-9)	0 (0-9)	1 (0.2-5.2)	3.8 (1.5-9.5)
Antibacterials (J01)	15.4 (4.3-42.2)	7.7 (1.4-33.3)	2.6 (0.5-13.2)	10.3 (4.1-23.6)	5.8 (2.7-12)	10.6 (6-18)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	2.6 (0.5-13.2)	17.9 (9-32.7)	2.9 (1-8.1)	15.4 (9.7-23.5)
Cough and cold medications (R05)	0 (0-22.8)	7.7 (1.4-33.3)	0 (0-9)	5.1 (1.4-16.9)	1.9 (0.5-6.7)	5.8 (2.7-12)
Immunosuppressants (L04)	0 (0-22.8)	7.7 (1.4-33.3)	0 (0-9)	0 (0-9)	0 (0-3.6)	0 (0-3.6)
Nasal preparations (R01)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	5.1 (1.4-16.9)	5.1 (1.4-16.9)	0 (0-3.6)	0 (0-3.6)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	5.1 (1.4-16.9)	2.6 (0.5-13.2)	1 (0.2-5.2)	4.8 (2.1-10.8)
Psycholeptics (N05)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	2.6 (0.5-13.2)	2.6 (0.5-13.2)	1 (0.2-5.2)	1 (0.2-5.2)

Non-hospitalized COVID-19 cases

Table 61 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (ARS, non-hospitalized COVID-19 cases)

DAP:ARS	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)
NON-HOSPITALIZED COVID-19 cases						
Antibacterials (J01)	6.6 (3.8-11.2)	7.7 (4.7-12.6)	5 (2.9-8.4)	6.2 (3.8-9.8)	5.1 (3.1-8.2)	8.4 (5.8-12.2)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	4.4 (2.3-8.5)	10.5 (6.8-15.8)	4.2 (2.4-7.4)	14.6 (10.8-19.4)	2.7 (1.4-5.2)	21.3 (17-26.3)
Corticosteroids (H02)	1.7 (0.6-4.8)	5 (2.6-9.2)	1.5 (0.6-3.9)	4.2 (2.4-7.4)	2.4 (1.2-4.8)	2.4 (1.2-4.8)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	0 (0-2.1)	0 (0-2.1)	0.4 (0.1-2.1)	1.2 (0.4-3.3)	2 (0.9-4.4)	1 (0.3-2.9)

Table 62 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (FISABIO-HSRU, non-hospitalized COVID-19 cases)

DAP:FISABIO-HSRU	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)
NON-HOSPITALIZED COVID-19 cases						
Analgesics (N02)	2.2 (1.4-3.4)	3.2 (2.2-4.5)	1 (0.5-1.9)	3.1 (2.1-4.5)	2.1 (1.3-3.4)	3.3 (2.2-4.8)
Anti_inflammatory drugs (M01)	1.2 (0.7-2.1)	1.5 (0.9-2.6)	0.4 (0.1-1)	0.7 (0.3-1.6)	0.7 (0.3-1.5)	2 (1.2-3.2)
Antibacterials (J01)	3.3 (2.3-4.6)	4.4 (3.2-5.9)	3.3 (2.3-4.8)	5.4 (4-7.1)	4.2 (3-5.9)	5.3 (3.9-7.1)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	2.3 (1.5-3.5)	31.3 (28.3-34.3)	4.3 (3.1-5.9)	50.4 (47-53.8)	4.5 (3.2-6.2)	61.8 (58.3-65.2)
Immune sera and globulins (J06)	0 (0-0.4)	0 (0-0.4)	0.6 (0.3-1.4)	1.4 (0.8-2.5)	2.4 (1.5-3.7)	0.5 (0.2-1.4)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	1.6 (1-2.7)	4.2 (3-5.6)	1.2 (0.6-2.2)	2.9 (1.9-4.2)	0.9 (0.4-1.9)	3.6 (2.5-5.1)

Table 63 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (IACS, non-hospitalized COVID-19 cases)

DAP:IACS	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)
NON-HOSPITALIZED COVID-19 cases						
Analgesics (N02)	12.3 (8.4-17.7)	11.3 (7.6-16.5)	10.9 (7.7-15.2)	10.1 (7-14.3)	11.3 (7.7-16.1)	13.1 (9.3-18.1)
Anti_inflammatory drugs (M01)	1.5 (0.5-4.4)	1.5 (0.5-4.4)	1.1 (0.4-3.3)	0.4 (0.1-2.1)	1.8 (0.7-4.5)	5.4 (3.1-9.2)
Antibacterials (J01)	6.2 (3.6-10.4)	7.2 (4.3-11.7)	4.5 (2.6-7.7)	5.6 (3.4-9.1)	5 (2.8-8.7)	6.8 (4.1-10.8)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	5.6 (3.2-9.8)	19.5 (14.5-25.6)	18 (13.8-23)	35.6 (30.1-41.5)	18.5 (13.9-24.1)	33.3 (27.5-39.8)
Nasal preparations (R01)	2.1 (0.8-5.2)	2.6 (1.1-5.9)	0.7 (0.2-2.7)	1.1 (0.4-3.3)	0.5 (0.1-2.5)	0.5 (0.1-2.5)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	1.5 (0.5-4.4)	2.1 (0.8-5.2)	1.1 (0.4-3.3)	3.4 (1.8-6.3)	3.6 (1.8-6.9)	3.6 (1.8-6.9)
Psychoanaleptics (N06)	3.6 (1.7-7.2)	4.1 (2.1-7.9)	0.7 (0.2-2.7)	0.7 (0.2-2.7)	0.9 (0.2-3.2)	0.9 (0.2-3.2)
Psycholeptics (N05)	2.6 (1.1-5.9)	3.1 (1.4-6.5)	0.7 (0.2-2.7)	1.5 (0.6-3.8)	0.5 (0.1-2.5)	2.3 (1-5.2)

Table 64 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (SWANSEA, non-hospitalized COVID-19 cases)

DAP SWANSEA	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre-infection % (95% CI)	30 days post-infection % (95% CI)	30 days pre-infection % (95% CI)	30 days post-infection % (95% CI)	30 days pre-infection % (95% CI)	30 days post-infection % (95% CI)
NON-HOSPITALIZED COVID-19 cases						
Analgesics (N02)	*	*	*	*	*	4.2 (2-8.9)
Antibacterials (J01)	0 (0-15.5)	28.6 (13.8-50)	*	*	4.2 (2-8.9)	10.6 (6.5-16.7)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	*	*	*	13.9 (6.1-28.7)	*	*
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	*	*	*	13.9 (6.1-28.7)	*	*
Psychoanaleptics (N06)	*	*	13.9 (6.1-28.7)	*	7 (3.9-12.5)	*

Table 65 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, by trimester of pregnancy (UIO, non-hospitalized COVID-19 cases)

DAP:UIO	COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the first trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the second trimester		COVID-19 test/diagnoses in the third trimester	
	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)	30 days pre- % (95% CI)	30 days post- % (95% CI)
NON-HOSPITALIZED COVID-19 cases						
Analgesics (N02)	3.7 (1.9-7.1)	2.8 (1.3-5.9)	1.7 (0.8-3.6)	1.7 (0.8-3.6)	1.3 (0.5-3.4)	3 (1.6-5.6)
Antibacterials (J01)	1.8 (0.7-4.6)	4.1 (2.2-7.7)	4.5 (2.8-7.1)	3.3 (1.9-5.8)	2.7 (1.4-5.2)	5.3 (3.3-8.5)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	1.8 (0.7-4.6)	1.8 (0.7-4.6)	1.1 (0.4-2.8)	0.8 (0.3-2.4)	0.3 (0.1-1.9)	2.3 (1.1-4.7)
Cough and cold medications (R05)	0 (0-1.7)	1.8 (0.7-4.6)	0.3 (0-1.6)	3.1 (1.7-5.4)	0.3 (0.1-1.9)	2 (0.9-4.3)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	0.5 (0.1-2.6)	0 (0-1.7)	0.8 (0.3-2.4)	0.6 (0.2-2)	4.3 (2.5-7.2)	2.7 (1.4-5.2)
Nasal preparations (R01)	0 (0-1.7)	0.9 (0.3-3.3)	0.8 (0.3-2.4)	2.5 (1.3-4.7)	0.7 (0.2-2.4)	0.7 (0.2-2.4)

Annex 7. Baseline characteristics of the matched cohort of pregnant women with/without COVID-19 in pregnancy

Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 had estimated pregnancy start within +/- 14 days from pregnancy start for pregnant women with COVID-19 and had the same age category. Pregnant women without COVID-19 were assigned the date of the matched partner's COVID-19 positive test or diagnosis, hence they had a 'pseudo' index date and trimester of pregnancy when diagnosis occurred to enable comparison

Table 66 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (ARS, trimester 1)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched pregnant women without COVID-19
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total
ARS					
Trimester 1	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)
Number of pregnancies ¹	201	<10	177		603
Number of unique women	201	<10	177		603
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	8.9	8.7	8.4		8.3
Age, Median	32	28	32		33
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>					
Cancer	<10	<10	<10	0.86	<10
Cardiovascular disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.22	21(3.5%)
Diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.08	<10
HIV	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.08	0(0%)
Use of immunosuppressants	25 (12.4%)	0(0%)	21(11.9%)	-0.37	74(12.3%)
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Mental disorders	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.22	23(3.8%)
Severe obesity	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.08	0(0%)
Chronic lung disease	10(5%)	0(0%)	<10	-0.24	29(4.8%)
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	43(21.4%)	<10	37(20.9%)	-0.16	133(22.1%)
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>					
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.22	33(5.5%)
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>					
Gestational diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.08	<10
Pre-eclampsia	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	11(5.5%)	0(0%)	10(5.6%)	-0.25	27(4.5%)
Any of the above conditions	12(6%)	0(0%)	11(6.2%)	-0.26	34(5.6%)

¹ If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 67 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (BPE, trimester 1)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)	Total
BPE					
Trimester 1	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		
Number of pregnancies ²	<10	<10	no records		
Number of unique women	<10	<10	no records		
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	13.2	13.2	no records		
Age, Median	30	30	no records		
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>					
Cancer	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		
Cardiovascular disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		
Diabetes	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		
HIV	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		
Use of immunosuppressants	<10	<10	no records		
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		
Mental disorders	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		
Severe obesity	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		
Chronic lung disease	<10	<10	no records		
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	<10	<10	no records		
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>					
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>					
Gestational diabetes	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		
Pre-eclampsia	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		
Any of the above conditions	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		

¹ BPE did not have access to COVID-19 surveillance data. Cases were identified based on admission to hospital with a COVID-19 diagnosis, hence it was not possible to create a cohort of pregnant women who did not have a diagnosis of COVID-19, given the likelihood of misclassification of COVID-19 status.² If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 68 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (FISABIO-HSRU, trimester 1)

FISABIO-HSRU	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)	Matched pregnant women without COVID-19
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19		Total
Trimester 1	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)
Number of pregnancies ¹	940	<10	914		2820
Number of unique women	940	<10	914		2820
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis)	7.1	10.1	7		7.3
Age, Median	32	26.5	32		33
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>					
Cancer	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	22(0.8%)
Cardiovascular disease	55(5.9%)	0(0%)	54(5.9%)	-0.25	130(4.6%)
Diabetes	18(1.9%)	0(0%)	18(2%)	-0.14	30(1.1%)
HIV	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Use of immunosuppressants	40(4.3%)	0(0%)	37(4%)	-0.21	84(3%)
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Chronic liver disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.05	<10
Mental disorders	91(9.7%)	0(0%)	88(9.6%)	-0.33	233(8.3%)
Severe obesity	20(2.1%)	0(0%)	20(2.2%)	-0.15	37(1.3%)
Chronic lung disease	117(12.4%)	0(0%)	115(12.6%)	-0.38	263(9.3%)
Sickle cell disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.06	<10
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	253(26.9%)	0(0%)	246(26.9%)	-0.61	637(22.6%)
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>					
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>					
Gestational diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.09	19(0.7%)
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.03	<10
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	86(9.1%)	0(0%)	83(9.1%)	-0.32	120(4.3%)
Any of the above conditions	96(10.2%)	0(0%)	92(10.1%)	-0.34	140(5%)

¹ If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 69 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (IACS, trimester 1)

IACS	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)	Matched pregnant women without COVID-19
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19		Total
Trimester 1	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)
Number of pregnancies ¹	182	<10	171		546
Number of unique women	182	<10	171		546
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	7.1	9.4	7.0		7.2
Age, Median	33	33.5	33		33
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>					
Cancer	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Cardiovascular disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.14	13(2.4%)
Diabetes	<10	<10	0(0%)	2.22	<10
HIV	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Use of immunosuppressants	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.18	26(4.8%)
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Mental disorders	35(19.2%)	<10	32(18.7%)	0.37	68(12.5%)
Severe obesity	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.08	<10
Chronic lung disease	13(7.1%)	0(0%)	13(7.6%)	-0.29	44(8.1%)
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	48(26.4%)	<10	45(26.3%)	0.16	131(24%)
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>					
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>					
Gestational diabetes	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.11	<10
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.16	21(3.8%)
Any of the above conditions	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.19	31(5.7%)

¹ If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 70 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (SWANSEA, trimester 1)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched pregnant women without COVID-19
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)	Total
SWANSEA					
Trimester 1	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)
Number of pregnancies ¹	567	21	546		1701
Number of unique women	567	21	546		1701
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	7.3	8.6	7.1		7.1
Age, Median	28	29	28		29
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>					
Cancer	*	*	*	0.77	5(0.3%)
Cardiovascular disease	5(0.9%)	*	*	0.43	16(0.9%)
Diabetes	5(0.9%)	0(0%)	5(0.9%)	-0.10	21(1.2%)
Use of immunosuppressants	21(3.7%)	*	*	0.58	48(2.8%)
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Chronic liver disease	*	0(0%)	*	-0.04	*
Mental disorders	116(20.5%)	*	*	0.33	331(19.5%)
Severe obesity	8(1.4%)	*	*	0.29	11(0.6%)
Chronic lung disease	63(11.1%)	*	*	0.10	157(9.2%)
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		*
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	174(30.7%)	10(47.6%)	164(30%)	0.38	461(27.1%)
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>					
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>					
Gestational diabetes	5(0.9%)	0(0%)	5(0.9%)	-0.10	19(1.1%)
Pre-eclampsia	7(1.2%)	0(0%)	7(1.3%)	-0.12	11(0.6%)
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	*	8(38.1%)	*	0.52	*
Any of the above conditions	107(18.9%)	8(38.1%)	99(18.1%)	0.51	266(15.6%)

¹ If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 71 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (UIO, trimester 1)

UIO	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched pregnant women without COVID-19
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)	Total
Trimester 1	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)
Number of pregnancies ¹	230	13	217		690
Number of unique women	230	13	217		690
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	8.2	8	8.3		8.1
Age, Median	30	32	30		30
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>					
Cancer	<10	<10	<10	0.21	36(5.2%)
Cardiovascular disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.20	22(3.2%)
Diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.14	12(1.7%)
HIV	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Use of immunosuppressants	<10	<10	<10	0.21	33(4.8%)
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Chronic liver disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	<10
Mental disorders	11(4.8%)	3(23.1%)	<10	0.91	36(5.2%)
Severe obesity	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.16	10(1.4%)
Chronic lung disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.20	40(5.8%)
Sickle cell disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	0(0%)
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	44(19.1%)	<10	40(18.4%)	0.31	145(21%)
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>					
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.19	39(5.7%)
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>					
Gestational diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	<10
Pre-eclampsia	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Any of the above conditions	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	14(2%)

¹ If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 72 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (ARS, trimester 2)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)	Matched pregnant women without COVID-19
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19		Total
ARS					
Trimester 2	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)
Number of pregnancies ¹	273	17	256		819
Number of unique women	273	17	256		819
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	21.7	24.4	21.6		21.3
Age, Median	32	34	32		32
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>					
Cancer	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.11	10(1.2%)
Cardiovascular disease	14(5.1%)	<10	12(4.7%)	0.32	28(3.4%)
Diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.13	11(1.3%)
HIV	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.06	0(0%)
Use of immunosuppressants	36(13.2%)	<10	34(13.3%)	-0.04	99(12.1%)
Chronic kidney disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.06	0(0%)
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Mental disorders	12(4.4%)	0(0%)	12(4.7%)	-0.23	35(4.3%)
Severe obesity	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.06	0(0%)
Chronic lung disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.20	48(5.9%)
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	62(22.7%)	<10	58(22.7%)	0.02	185(22.6%)
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>					
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.09	28(3.4%)
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>					
Gestational diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.13	<10
Pre-eclampsia	<10	<10	<10	0.49	<10
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	17(6.2%)	0(0%)	17(6.6%)	-0.27	38(4.6%)
Any of the above conditions	22(8.1%)	<10	21(8.2%)	-0.09	45(5.5%)

¹ If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 73 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (BPE, trimester 2)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)
BPE				
Trimester 2	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies ²	85	85	no records	
Number of unique women	85	85	no records	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	21.9	21.9	no records	
Age, Median	29	29	no records	
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>				
Cancer	<10	<10	no records	
Cardiovascular disease	<10	<10	no records	
Diabetes	<10	<10	no records	
HIV	<10	<10	no records	
Use of immunosuppressants	22(25.9%)	22(25.9%)	no records	
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records	
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records	
Mental disorders	16(18.8%)	16(18.8%)	no records	
Severe obesity	<10	<10	no records	
Chronic lung disease	12(14.1%)	12(14.1%)	no records	
Sickle cell disease	<10	<10	no records	
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	40(47.1%)	40(47.1%)	no records	
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>				
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records	
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>				
Gestational diabetes	<10	<10	no records	
Pre-eclampsia	<10	<10	no records	
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	<10	<10	no records	
Any of the above conditions	<10	<10	no records	

¹ BPE did not have access to COVID-19 surveillance data. Cases were identified based on admission to hospital with a COVID-19 diagnosis, hence it was not possible to create a cohort of pregnant women who did not have a diagnosis of COVID-19, given the likelihood of misclassification of COVID-19 status. ² If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 74 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (FISABIO-HSRU, trimester 2)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)	Total
		N (%)	N (%)		
FISABIO-HSRU					
Trimester 2	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)
Number of pregnancies ¹	856	13	839		2568
Number of unique women	856	13	839		2568
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	20.7	24	20.7		20.7
Age, Median	32	33	32		32
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>					
Cancer	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.10	27(1.1%)
Cardiovascular disease	48(5.6%)	<10	44(5.2%)	0.78	113(4.4%)
Diabetes	13(1.5%)	0(0%)	13(1.5%)	-0.13	20(0.8%)
HIV	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.03	<10
Use of immunosuppressants	24(2.8%)	0(0%)	24(2.9%)	-0.17	71(2.8%)
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Chronic liver disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.05	<10
Mental disorders	56(6.5%)	<10	54(6.4%)	0.36	197(7.7%)
Severe obesity	14(1.6%)	0(0%)	13(1.5%)	-0.13	29(1.1%)
Chronic lung disease	88(10.3%)	<10	86(10.3%)	-0.08	226(8.8%)
Sickle cell disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.03	10(0.4%)
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	185(21.6%)	<10	180(21.5%)	0.23	564(22%)
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>					
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>					
Gestational diabetes	13(1.5%)	<10	12(1.4%)	0.51	19(0.7%)
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.06	<10
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	83(9.7%)	<10	82(9.8%)	-0.07	178(6.9%)
Any of the above conditions	98(11.4%)	<10	96(11.4%)	0.12	199(7.7%)

¹ If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 75 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (IACS, trimester 2)

IACS	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched pregnant women without COVID-19
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)	Total
Trimester 2	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)
Number of pregnancies ¹	261	16	245		783
Number of unique women	261	16	245		783
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	21.4	22.2	21.3		21.6
Age, Median	33	36	33		33
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>					
Cancer	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	<10
Cardiovascular disease	15(5.7%)	0(0%)	15(6.1%)	-0.26	20(2.6%)
Diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.16	<10
HIV	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Use of immunosuppressants	13(5%)	<10	12(4.9%)	0.06	27(3.4%)
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Mental disorders	31(11.9%)	<10	28(11.4%)	0.23	94(12%)
Severe obesity	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Chronic lung disease	26(10%)	<10	24(9.8%)	0.09	58(7.4%)
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	68(26.1%)	5(31.2%)	63(25.7%)	0.13	175(22.3%)
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>					
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>					
Gestational diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.18	<10
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.11	<10
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	<10	<10	<10	0.16	27(3.4%)
Any of the above conditions	18(6.6%)	<10	17(6.9%)	-0.03	38(4.9%)

¹ If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 76 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (SWANSEA, trimester 2)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched pregnant women without COVID-19
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)	Total
SWANSEA					
Trimester 2	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)
Number of pregnancies	626	35	590		1878
Number of unique women	626	35	590		1878
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis ¹	20.9	22	20.7		20.9
Age, Median	29	29	29		29
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>					
Cancer	*	0(0%)	*	-0.08	*
Cardiovascular disease	7(1.1%)	0(0%)	7(1.2%)	-0.11	20(1.1%)
Diabetes	15(2.4%)	*	*	0.23	27(1.4%)
Use of immunosuppressants	25(4%)	*	*	0.09	59(3.1%)
Chronic kidney disease	*	0(0%)	*	-0.04	0(0%)
Chronic liver disease	*	0(0%)	*	-0.04	*
Mental disorders	128(20.4%)	11(31.4%)	117(19.8%)	0.29	390(20.8%)
Severe obesity	8(1.3%)	*	*	0.15	14(0.7%)
Chronic lung disease	72(11.5%)	5(14.3%)	67(11.4%)	0.09	165(8.8%)
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		*
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	196(31.3%)	17(48.6%)	179(30.3%)	0.39	546(29.1%)
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>					
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>					
Gestational diabetes	*	*	*	0.36	28(1.5%)
Pre-eclampsia	5(0.8%)	*	*	0.24	8(0.4%)
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	112(17.9%)	6(17.1%)	106(18%)	-0.02	*
Any of the above conditions	112(17.9%)	6(17.1%)	106(18%)	-0.02	345(18.4%)

¹ If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 77 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (UIO, trimester 2)

UIO	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)	Matched pregnant women without COVID-19
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19		Total
Trimester 2	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)
Number of pregnancies ¹	398	39	359		1194
Number of unique women	398	39	359		1194
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	21.1	24.3	21		21.3
Age, Median	31	33	30		30
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>					
Cancer	14(3.5%)	<10	13(3.6%)	-0.1	61(5.1%)
Cardiovascular disease	11(2.8%)	0(0%)	11(3.1%)	-0.2	35(2.9%)
Diabetes	<10	<10	<10	0.0	21(1.8%)
HIV	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Use of immunosuppressants	13(3.3%)	<10	11(3.1%)	0.1	49(4.1%)
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Mental disorders	27(6.8%)	<10	24(6.7%)	0.0	71(5.9%)
Severe obesity	<10	<10	<10	0.1	18(1.5%)
Chronic lung disease	13(3.3%)	<10	11(3.1%)	0.1	73(6.1%)
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	70(17.6%)	<10	62(17.3%)	0.1	255(21.4%)
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>					
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	<10	<10	8(2.2%)	0.0	47(3.9%)
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>					
Gestational diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.11	<10
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.10	<10
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.06	<10
Any of the above conditions	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.15	16(1.3%)

¹ If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 78 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (ARS, trimester 3)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)	Matched pregnant women without COVID-19
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19		Total
ARS					
Trimester 3	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)
Number of pregnancies	508	106	296		1524
Number of unique women	508	106	296		1524
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	36.6	37.6	33.8		36.3
Age, Median	31	32	31		32
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>					
Cancer	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.10	<10
Cardiovascular disease	18(3.5%)	<10	10(3.4%)	0.02	60(3.9%)
Diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	24(1.6%)
HIV	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Use of immunosuppressants	68(13.4%)	16(15.1%)	39(13.2%)	0.06	154(10.1%)
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Mental disorders	16(3.1%)	<10	12(4.1%)	-0.12	57(3.7%)
Severe obesity	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Chronic lung disease	26(5.1%)	<10	16(5.4%)	-0.07	86(5.6%)
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	100(19.7%)	21(19.8%)	61(20.6%)	-0.02	325(21.3%)
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>					
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	<10	<10	<10	-0.06	34(2.2%)
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>					
Gestational diabetes	<10	<10	<10	0.02	15(1%)
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	10(0.7%)
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	42(8.3%)	<10	26(8.8%)	-0.01	79(5.2%)
Any of the above conditions	50(9.8%)	11(10.4%)	31(10.5%)	0.00	99(6.5%)

¹ If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 79 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (BPE, trimester 3)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)
BPE				
Trimester 3	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies ²	926	218	0	
Number of unique women	924	218	0	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	39.9	35.6		
Age, Median	30	30		
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>				
Cancer	29(3.1%)	<10	no records	
Cardiovascular disease	34(3.7%)	<10	no records	
Diabetes	16(1.7%)	<10	no records	
HIV	<10	<10	no records	
Use of immunosuppressants	198(21.4%)	49(22.5%)	no records	
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records	
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records	
Mental disorders	122(13.2%)	39(17.9%)	no records	
Severe obesity	11(1.2%)	<10	no records	
Chronic lung disease	85(9.2%)	18(8.3%)	no records	
Sickle cell disease	<10	<10	no records	
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	363(39.2%)	99(45.4%)	no records	
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>				
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records	
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>				
Gestational diabetes	15(1.6%)	<10	no records	
Pre-eclampsia	<10	<10	no records	
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	36(3.9%)	<10	no records	
Any of the above conditions	55(5.9%)	15(6.9%)	no records	

¹ BPE did not have access to COVID-19 surveillance data. Cases were identified based on admission to hospital with a COVID-19 diagnosis, hence it was not possible to create a cohort of pregnant women who did not have a diagnosis of COVID-19, given the likelihood of misclassification of COVID-19 status. ² If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases

Table 80 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (FISABIO-HSRU, trimester 3)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)	Total
FISABIO-HSRU					
Trimester 3	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)
Number of pregnancies ¹	1181	82	756		3543
Number of unique women	1181	82	756		3543
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	35.4	36.8	33.1		35.3
Age, Median	31	32	31		32
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>					
Cancer	10(0.8%)	0(0%)	<10	-0.10	40(1.1%)
Cardiovascular disease	42(3.6%)	<10	29(3.8%)	0.05	157(4.4%)
Diabetes	10(0.8%)	0(0%)	<10	-0.10	26(0.7%)
HIV	<10	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Use of immunosuppressants	31(2.6%)	<10	24(3.2%)	-0.04	90(2.5%)
Chronic kidney disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.04	0(0%)
Chronic liver disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.04	<10
Mental disorders	80(6.8%)	<10	<10	0.02	283(8%)
Severe obesity	19(1.6%)	<10	<10	-0.04	57(1.6%)
Chronic lung disease	108(9.1%)	<10	<10	-0.04	305(8.6%)
Sickle cell disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.04	10(0.3%)
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	246(20.8%)	15(18.3%)	166(22%)	-0.09	765(21.6%)
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>					
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>					
Gestational diabetes	15(1.3%)	0(0%)	<10	-0.11	<10
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	<10
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	96(8.1%)	<10	54(7.1%)	0.10	274(7.7%)
Any of the above conditions	112(9.5%)	<10	65(8.6%)	0.04	313(8.8%)

¹ If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 81 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (IACS, trimester 3)

IACS	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)	Matched pregnant women without COVID-19
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19		Total
Trimester 3	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)
Number of pregnancies ¹	431	68	197		1293
Number of unique women	431	68	197		1293
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	37	37.1	33.3		37
Age, Median	31	31	32		32
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>					
Cancer	<10	<10	<10	0.0	<10
Cardiovascular disease	21(4.9%)	<10	12(6.1%)	-0.1	50(3.9%)
Diabetes	<10	<10	<10	0.1	12(0.9%)
HIV	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Use of immunosuppressants	19(4.4%)	<10	11(5.6%)	-0.1	53(4.1%)
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Mental disorders	47(10.9%)	5(7.4%)	25(12.7%)	-0.2	138(10.7%)
Severe obesity	<10	<10	<10	0.1	<10
Chronic lung disease	28(6.5%)	<10	18(9.1%)	-0.2	98(7.6%)
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	101(23.4%)	12(17.6%)	55(27.9%)	-0.2	299(23.1%)
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>					
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>					
Gestational diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.08	15(1.2%)
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.11	<10
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	14(3.1%)	<10	<10	-0.1	47(3.6%)
Any of the above conditions	17(3.9%)	<10	10(5.1%)	-0.1	61(4.7%)

¹If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 82 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (SWANSEA, trimester 3)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched pregnant women without COVID-19
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)	Total
SWANSEA					
Trimester 3	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)
Number of pregnancies ¹	726	142	487		2178
Number of unique women	726	142	487		2178
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	34.6	35.3	33.3		34.7
Age, Median	29	29	29		29
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>					
Cancer	*	*	*	0.04	13(0.6%)
Cardiovascular disease	11(1.5%)	0(0%)	*	-0.15	28(1.3%)
Diabetes	13(1.8%)	*	7(1.4%)	0.00	34(1.6%)
Use of immunosuppressants	17(2.3%)	*	*	0.01	60(2.8%)
Chronic kidney disease	*	0(0%)	*	-0.05	0(0%)
Chronic liver disease	*	*	*	0.01	*
Mental disorders	143(19.7%)	29(20.4%)	93(19.1%)	0.03	440(20.2%)
Severe obesity	7(1%)	0(0%)	*	-0.13	16(0.7%)
Chronic lung disease	57(7.9%)	8(5.6%)	44(9%)	-0.12	224(10.3%)
Sickle cell disease	*	0(0%)	*	-0.05	0(0%)
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	202(27.8%)	38(26.8%)	138(28.3%)	-0.04	634(29.1%)
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>					
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>					
Gestational diabetes	9(1.2%)	*	*	0.26	23(1.1%)
Pre-eclampsia	*	0(0%)	*	-0.09	6(0.3%)
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	*	*	94(19.3%)	0.18	*
Any of the above conditions	149(20.5%)	39(27.5%)	94(19.3%)	0.20	393(18%)

¹ If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 83 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (UIO, trimester 3)

UIO	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched pregnant women without COVID-19
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized cases)	Total
Trimester 3	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)
Number of pregnancies	443	104	301		1329
Number of unique women	443	104	301		1329
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	34.6	37.1	33.3		34.9
Age, Median	30	31	30		30
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>					
Cancer	15(3.4%)	<10	12(4%)	-0.11	51(3.8%)
Cardiovascular disease	15(3.4%)	<10	10(3.3%)	0.03	41(3.1%)
Diabetes	10(2.3%)	0(0%)	10(3.3%)	-0.21	20(1.5%)
HIV	<10	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Use of immunosuppressants	10(2.3%)	<10	<10	-0.05	38(2.9%)
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10
Mental disorders	28(6.3%)	<10	17(5.6%)	0.12	78(5.9%)
Severe obesity	<10	<10	<10	0.12	20(1.5%)
Chronic lung disease	24(5.4%)	<10	19(6.3%)	-0.06	83(6.2%)
Sickle cell disease	<10	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)
Any risk factors for severe COVID-19	87(19.6%)	21(20.2%)	59(19.6%)	0.01	256(19.3%)
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>					
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	<10	<10	<10	0.13	43(3.2%)
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>					
Gestational diabetes	<10	<10	<10	-0.03	14(1.1%)
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.09	<10
Stillbirth/spontaneous abortion	<10	<10	<10	0.03	<10
Any of the above conditions	14(3.2%)	<10	10(3.3%)	-0.02	22(1.7%)

¹ If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases

Annex 8. Prevalence of medication use in the matched cohort of pregnant women with/without COVID-19 in pregnancy

Pregnancies with a COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis in Trimester 1

Table 84 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (ARS, Trimester 1 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: ARS	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 1	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched comparator group ¹	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre- ¹	30 days post- ¹
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Anti_inflammatory drugs (M01)	0 (0-1.8)	0.5 (0.1-2.7)	0 (0-29.9)	11.1 (2-43.5)	0 (0-2.1)	0 (0-2.1)	1 (0.5-2.2)	0 (0-0.6)
Antibacterials (J01)	6.8 (4.1-11)	12.1 (8.3-17.2)	11.1 (2-43.5)	33.3 (12.1-64.6)	6.6 (3.8-11.2)	7.7 (4.7-12.6)	3 (2.2-5.1)	3.3 (2.2-5.1)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	3.9 (2-7.4)	12.6 (8.7-17.8)	0 (0-29.9)	66.7 (35.4-87.9)	4.4 (2.3-8.5)	10.5 (6.8-15.8)	2 (1-3.2)	3 (1.9-4.7)
Corticosteroids (H02)	2.4 (1-5.5)	8.2 (5.2-12.8)	11.1 (2-43.5)	33.3 (12.1-64.6)	1.7 (0.6-4.8)	5 (2.6-9.2)	1 (0.7-2.6)	0.3 (0.1-1.2)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	0.5 (0.1-2.7)	0 (0-1.8)	11.1 (2-43.5)	0 (0-29.9)	0 (0-2.1)	0 (0-2.1)	0 (0-0.9)	0.2 (0-0.9)

¹Matched comparator group had an estimated pregnancy start within +/- 14 days from pregnancy start for pregnant women with COVID-19 and were in the same age category. They were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they have a pseudo date of COVID-19 and pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.

Table 85 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (BPE, Trimester 1 COVID-19 disease)

DAP:BPE	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 1	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched comparator group ¹	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-i	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre- ¹	30 days post- ¹
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	42.9 (15.8-75)	28.6 (8.2-64.1)	42.9 (15.8-75)	28.6 (8.2-64.1)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Antibacterials (J01)	42.9 (15.8-75)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	42.9 (15.8-75)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	0 (0-35.4)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	0 (0-35.4)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Corticosteroids (H02)	0 (0-35.4)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	0 (0-35.4)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Cough and cold medications (R05)	28.6 (8.2-64.1)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	28.6 (8.2-64.1)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Nasal preparations (R01)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	0 (0-35.4)	14.3 (2.6-51.3)	0 (0-35.4)	NA	NA	NA	NA

¹BPE did not have access to COVID-19 surveillance data. Cases were identified based on admission to hospital with a COVID-19 diagnosis, hence it was not possible to create a cohort of pregnant women who did not have a diagnosis of COVID-19, given the likelihood of misclassification of COVID-19 status.

Table 86 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (FISABIO-HSRU, Trimester 1 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: FISABIO-HSRU	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 1	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched comparator group ¹	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	2.2 (1.5-3.4)	3.2 (2.2-4.5)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-39)	2.2 (1.4-3.4)	3.2 (2.2-4.5)	1 (0.8-1.6)	1.3 (0.9-1.8)
Anti_inflammatory drugs (M01)	1.2 (0.7-2.1)	1.6 (1-2.6)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-39)	1.2 (0.7-2.1)	1.5 (0.9-2.6)	2 (1.6-2.6)	1.7 (1.3-2.2)
Antibacterials (J01)	3.3 (2.3-4.6)	4.3 (3.1-5.7)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-39)	3.3 (2.3-4.6)	4.4 (3.2-5.9)	2 (1.4-2.4)	3.2 (2.6-3.9)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	2.3 (1.5-3.5)	31 (28.2-34.1)	0 (0-39)	50 (18.8-81.2)	2.3 (1.5-3.5)	31.3 (28.3-34.3)	1 (1-1.9)	2.2 (1.7-2.8)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	1.6 (1-2.6)	4 (3-5.5)	0 (0-39)	0 (0-39)	1.6 (1-2.7)	4.2 (3-5.6)	1 (0.8-1.6)	1.6 (1.2-2.1)

¹Matched comparator group had an estimated pregnancy start within +/- 14 days from pregnancy start for pregnant women with COVID-19 and were in the same age category. They were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they have a pseudo date of COVID-19 and pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.

Table 87 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (IACS, Trimester 1 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: IACS	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 1	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched comparator group ¹	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	12.3 (8.5-17.4)	11.3 (7.7-16.3)	16.7 (4.7-44.8)	8.3 (1.5-35.4)	12.3 (8.4-17.7)	11.3 (7.6-16.5)	4 (2.9-6.4)	5.6 (4-7.9)
Anti_inflammatory drugs (M01)	1.9 (0.7-4.8)	1.4 (0.5-4.1)	8.3 (1.5-35.4)	0 (0-24.2)	1.5 (0.5-4.4)	1.5 (0.5-4.4)	3 (1.5-4.2)	2.2 (1.2-3.8)
Antibacterials (J01)	5.7 (3.3-9.6)	7.5 (4.7-11.9)	0 (0-24.2)	16.7 (4.7-44.8)	6.2 (3.6-10.4)	7.2 (4.3-11.7)	2 (1.1-3.5)	2.7 (1.7-4.4)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	5.2 (2.9-9.1)	20.8 (15.8-26.7)	0 (0-24.2)	41.7 (19.3-68)	5.6 (3.2-9.8)	19.5 (14.5-25.6)	3 (1.8-4.7)	2.7 (1.7-4.4)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	0.5 (0.1-2.6)	0.9 (0.3-3.4)	8.3 (1.5-35.4)	8.3 (1.5-35.4)	0 (0-1.9)	0.5 (0.1-2.8)	1 (0.2-1.6)	0.2 (0-1)
Nasal preparations (R01)	1.9 (0.7-4.8)	2.4 (1-5.4)	0 (0-24.2)	0 (0-24.2)	2.1 (0.8-5.2)	2.6 (1.1-5.9)	0 (0.1-1.3)	0 (0-0.7)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	1.4 (0.5-4.1)	1.9 (0.7-4.8)	0 (0-24.2)	0 (0-24.2)	1.5 (0.5-4.4)	2.1 (0.8-5.2)	0 (0-1)	0.7 (0.3-1.8)
Psychoanaleptics (N06)	3.3 (1.6-6.7)	3.8 (1.9-7.3)	0 (0-24.2)	0 (0-24.2)	3.6 (1.7-7.2)	4.1 (2.1-7.9)	2 (1.4-4)	2.2 (1.2-3.8)
Psycholeptics (N05)	2.4 (1-5.4)	2.8 (1.3-6)	0 (0-24.2)	0 (0-24.2)	2.6 (1.1-5.9)	3.1 (1.4-6.5)	3 (1.8-4.7)	2.4 (1.4-4)

Table 88 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (SWANSEA, Trimester 1 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: SWANSEA	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 1 INFECTION	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched controls ¹	
	30 days pre-infection	30 days post-infection	30 days pre-infection	30 days post-infection	30 days pre-infection	30 days post-infection	30 days pre-infection ¹	30 days post-infection ¹
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	2.4 (1.5-4)	2.8 (1.7-4.5)	*	*	2.2 (1.2-3.7)	2.5 (1.5-4.2)	2 (1.5-2.9)	1.9 (1.4-2.7)
Antibacterials (J01)	4.9 (3.4-6.9)	6.4 (4.7-8.7)	0 (0-15.5)	28.6 (13.8-50)	5 (3.5-7.2)	5.6 (4-7.8)	4 (3.2-5.1)	4.2 (3.4-5.3)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	1.2 (0.6-2.5)	1.7 (0.9-3.2)	*	*	0.9 (0.4-2.1)	1.6 (0.9-3.1)	1 (0.9-2)	2.1 (1.5-2.9)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	2.4 (1.5-4)	4 (2.7-5.9)	*	*	2.2 (1.2-3.7)	4 (2.6-5.9)	3 (2.3-3.9)	2.9 (2.2-3.9)
Psychoanaleptics (N06)	7.5 (5.6-9.9)	6.4 (4.7-8.7)	*	*	7.2 (5.3-9.7)	6.1 (4.4-8.4)	8 (6.5-9)	5.6 (4.6-6.8)

¹Matched controls had an estimated pregnancy start within +/- 14 days from pregnancy start for pregnant women with COVID-19 and were in the same age category. They were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they have a pseudo date of COVID-19 and pseudo trimester of infection, but no severity of infection.

Table 89 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (UIO, Trimester 1 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: UIO	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 1	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched comparator group ¹	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	3.9 (2.1-7.3)	2.6 (1.2-5.6)	7.7 (1.4-33.3)	0 (0-22.8)	3.7 (1.9-7.1)	2.8 (1.3-5.9)	2 (1.2-3.4)	1.6 (0.9-2.8)
Antibacterials (J01)	2.6 (1.2-5.6)	4.3 (2.4-7.8)	15.4 (4.3-42.2)	7.7 (1.4-33.3)	1.8 (0.7-4.6)	4.1 (2.2-7.7)	2 (1.3-3.6)	2.8 (1.8-4.3)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	1.7 (0.7-4.4)	1.7 (0.7-4.4)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	1.8 (0.7-4.6)	1.8 (0.7-4.6)	2 (1.3-3.6)	1.7 (1-3)
Cough and cold medications (R05)	0 (0-1.6)	2.2 (0.9-5)	0 (0-22.8)	7.7 (1.4-33.3)	0 (0-1.7)	1.8 (0.7-4.6)	0 (0-0.8)	0 (0-0.6)
Immunosuppressants (L04)	0 (0-1.6)	0.4 (0.1-2.4)	0 (0-22.8)	7.7 (1.4-33.3)	0 (0-1.7)	0 (0-1.7)	0 (0-0.8)	0 (0-0.6)

¹Matched comparator group had an estimated pregnancy start within +/- 14 days from pregnancy start for pregnant women with COVID-19 and were in the same age category. They were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they have a pseudo date of COVID-19 and pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.

Pregnancies with a COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis in Trimester 2

Table 90 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (ARS, Trimester 2 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: ARS	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 2	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched comparator group ¹	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Antibacterials (J01)	5.8 (3.6-9.2)	6.9 (4.4-10.5)	17.6 (6.2-41)	17.6 (6.2-41)	5 (2.9-8.4)	6.2 (3.8-9.8)	3.7 (2.6-5.2)	2.9 (2-4.3)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	4.3 (2.5-7.4)	16.6 (12.7-21.4)	5.9 (1-27)	47.1 (26.2-69)	4.2 (2.4-7.4)	14.6 (10.8-19.4)	3.2 (2.2-4.6)	4.2 (3-5.7)
Corticosteroids (H02)	1.4 (0.6-3.7)	5.4 (3.3-8.7)	0 (0-18.4)	23.5 (9.6-47.3)	1.5 (0.6-3.9)	4.2 (2.4-7.4)	0.9 (0.4-1.8)	1 (0.5-1.9)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	0.4 (0.1-2)	1.4 (0.6-3.7)	0 (0-18.4)	5.9 (1-27)	0.4 (0.1-2.1)	1.2 (0.4-3.3)	0.7 (0.3-1.6)	1.3 (0.8-2.4)

¹Matched comparator group had an estimated pregnancy start within +/- 14 days from pregnancy start for pregnant women with COVID-19 and were in the same age category. They were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they have a pseudo date of COVID-19 and pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.

Table 91 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (BPE, Trimester 2 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: BPE	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 2	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched comparator group ¹	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	35.9 (26.8-46.1)	38 (28.8-48.3)	35.9 (26.8-46.1)	38 (28.8-48.3)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Antibacterials (J01)	19.6 (12.7-28.8)	34.8 (25.8-44.9)	19.6 (12.7-28.8)	34.8 (25.8-44.9)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Antimycotics (J02)	1.1 (0.2-5.9)	4.3 (1.7-10.7)	1.1 (0.2-5.9)	4.3 (1.7-10.7)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Antiprotozoals (P01)	0 (0-4)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	0 (0-4)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	3.3 (1.1-9.2)	6.5 (3-13.5)	3.3 (1.1-9.2)	6.5 (3-13.5)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Corticosteroids (H02)	5.4 (2.3-12.1)	4.3 (1.7-10.7)	5.4 (2.3-12.1)	4.3 (1.7-10.7)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Cough and cold medications (R05)	5.4 (2.3-12.1)	4.3 (1.7-10.7)	5.4 (2.3-12.1)	4.3 (1.7-10.7)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	1.1 (0.2-5.9)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	1.1 (0.2-5.9)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Immune sera and globulins (J06)	1.1 (0.2-5.9)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	1.1 (0.2-5.9)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Nasal preparations (R01)	12 (6.8-20.2)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	12 (6.8-20.2)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	8.7 (4.5-16.2)	9.8 (5.2-17.6)	8.7 (4.5-16.2)	9.8 (5.2-17.6)	NA	NA	NA	NA

DAP: BPE	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 2	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched comparator group ¹	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
Psychoanaesthetics (N06)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	2.2 (0.6-7.6)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Psycholeptics (N05)	3.3 (1.1-9.2)	3.3 (1.1-9.2)	3.3 (1.1-9.2)	3.3 (1.1-9.2)	NA	NA	NA	NA

¹ BPE did not have access to COVID-19 surveillance data. Cases were identified based on admission to hospital with a COVID-19 diagnosis, hence it was not possible to create a cohort of pregnant women who did not have a diagnosis of COVID-19, given the likelihood of misclassification of COVID-19 status.

Table 92 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (FISABIO-HSRU, Trimester 2 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: FISABIO-HSRU	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 2	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched comparator group ¹	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	0.9 (0.5-1.8)	3 (2.1-4.4)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	1 (0.5-1.9)	3.1 (2.1-4.5)	1.2 (0.8-1.7)	1.2 (0.8-1.7)
Antibacterials (J01)	3.5 (2.5-5)	5.3 (4-7)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	3.3 (2.3-4.8)	5.4 (4-7.1)	2.8 (2.2-3.5)	2.8 (2.2-3.5)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	4.4 (3.3-6)	50.7 (47.4-54)	7.7 (1.4-33.3)	61.5 (35.5-82.3)	4.3 (3.1-5.9)	50.4 (47-53.8)	3.5 (2.9-4.3)	4.2 (3.5-5)
Immune sera and globulins (J06)	0.7 (0.3-1.5)	1.5 (0.9-2.6)	0 (0-22.8)	7.7 (1.4-33.3)	0.6 (0.3-1.4)	1.4 (0.8-2.5)	0.6 (0.4-1)	1.7 (1.2-2.2)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	1.2 (0.6-2.1)	2.8 (1.9-4.1)	0 (0-22.8)	0 (0-22.8)	1.2 (0.6-2.2)	2.9 (1.9-4.2)	1.1 (0.7-1.5)	1.1 (0.7-1.5)

Table 93 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (IACS, Trimester 2 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: IACS	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 2	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched comparator group ¹	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	11.6 (8.4-15.8)	10.5 (7.5-14.6)	22.2 (9-45.2)	16.7 (5.8-39.2)	10.9 (7.7-15.2)	10.1 (7-14.3)	3 (2-4.4)	3.5 (2.4-5)
Anti_inflammatory drugs (M01)	1.1 (0.4-3)	0.7 (0.2-2.5)	0 (0-17.6)	5.6 (1-25.8)	1.1 (0.4-3.3)	0.4 (0.1-2.1)	1.8 (1.1-3)	0.6 (0.3-1.5)
Antibacterials (J01)	5.6 (3.5-8.9)	5.3 (3.2-8.5)	22.2 (9-45.2)	0 (0-17.6)	4.5 (2.6-7.7)	5.6 (3.4-9.1)	4.1 (2.9-5.8)	4.1 (2.9-5.8)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	17.9 (13.9-22.8)	37.5 (32.1-43.3)	16.7 (5.8-39.2)	66.7 (43.7-83.7)	18 (13.8-23)	35.6 (30.1-41.5)	5.7 (4.3-7.5)	6.2 (4.7-8.1)

Corticoosteroids (H02)	0.4 (0.1-2)	0.7 (0.2-2.5)	0 (0-17.6)	5.6 (1-25.8)	0.4 (0.1-2.1)	0.4 (0.1-2.1)	0.5 (0.2-1.3)	0.4 (0.1-1.1)
Cough and cold medications (R05)	0.4 (0.1-2)	0.4 (0.1-2)	5.6 (1-25.8)	5.6 (1-25.8)	0 (0-1.4)	0 (0-1.4)	0.1 (0-0.7)	0 (0-0.5)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	1.1 (0.4-3)	3.9 (2.2-6.8)	0 (0-17.6)	11.1 (3.1-32.8)	1.1 (0.4-3.3)	3.4 (1.8-6.3)	0.8 (0.4-1.7)	0.8 (0.4-1.7)

¹Matched comparator group had an estimated pregnancy start within +/- 14 days from pregnancy start for pregnant women with COVID-19 and were in the same age category. They were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they have a pseudo date of COVID-19 and pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.

Table 94 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (SWANSEA, Trimester 2 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: SWANSEA	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 2 INFECTION	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched controls ¹	
	30 days pre-infection	30 days post-infection	30 days pre-infection	30 days post-infection	30 days pre-infection	30 days post-infection	30 days pre-infection ¹	30 days post-infection ¹
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	1.7 (1-3.1)	2.5 (1.5-4)	*	*	1.7 (0.9-3)	2.2 (1.3-3.7)	1.4 (1-2.1)	1.3 (0.9-1.9)
Antibacterials (J01)	6 (4.4-8.1)	6.1 (4.5-8.2)	*	*	5.7 (4.1-7.8)	6 (4.4-8.2)	4.3 (3.4-5.3)	3.6 (2.9-4.6)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	2.2 (1.3-3.6)	2.5 (1.5-4)	*	13.9 (6.1-28.7)	1.7 (0.9-3)	1.8 (1-3.2)	2.2 (1.7-3)	2.6 (1.9-3.4)
Corticosteroids (H02)	1.1 (0.5-2.2)	0.8 (0.3-1.8)	0 (0-9.6)	*	1.2 (0.6-2.4)	*	*	0.3 (0.1-0.6)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	1.9 (1.1-3.3)	2.2 (1.3-3.6)	*	*	1.3 (0.7-2.6)	1.7 (0.9-3)	1 (0.6-1.5)	1 (0.6-1.6)
Immunosuppressants (L04)	*	*	0 (0-9.6)	0 (0-9.6)	*	*	*	*
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	4.5 (3.2-6.5)	5.2 (3.7-7.2)	*	13.9 (6.1-28.7)	4.2 (2.8-6.1)	4.7 (3.2-6.7)	1.9 (1.4-2.6)	1.9 (1.4-2.6)
Psychoanaleptics (N06)	6.3 (4.6-8.4)	6.4 (4.8-8.6)	13.9 (6.1-28.7)	*	5.8 (4.2-8)	6.3 (4.6-8.6)	6.2 (5.2-7.4)	5.5 (4.5-6.6)

Table 95 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (UIO, Trimester 2 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: UIO	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 2	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched comparator group ¹	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	2.3 (1.2-4.2)	2.3 (1.2-4.2)	7.7 (2.7-20.3)	7.7 (2.7-20.3)	1.7 (0.8-3.6)	1.7 (0.8-3.6)	1.4 (0.9-2.3)	1.4 (0.9-2.3)
Antibacterials (J01)	4.3 (2.7-6.7)	4 (2.5-6.4)	2.6 (0.5-13.2)	10.3 (4.1-23.6)	4.5 (2.8-7.1)	3.3 (1.9-5.8)	2.7 (1.9-3.8)	2.3 (1.6-3.3)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	1.3 (0.5-2.9)	2.5 (1.4-4.6)	2.6 (0.5-13.2)	17.9 (9-32.7)	1.1 (0.4-2.8)	0.8 (0.3-2.4)	1.8 (1.2-2.7)	2 (1.4-3)
Cough and cold medications (R05)	0.3 (0-1.4)	3.3 (1.9-5.5)	0 (0-9)	5.1 (1.4-16.9)	0.3 (0-1.6)	3.1 (1.7-5.4)	0.2 (0-0.6)	0 (0-0.3)
Nasal preparations (R01)	1.3 (0.5-2.9)	2.8 (1.6-4.9)	5.1 (1.4-16.9)	5.1 (1.4-16.9)	0.8 (0.3-2.4)	2.5 (1.3-4.7)	1.2 (0.7-2)	2 (1.4-3)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	1 (0.4-2.6)	1.8 (0.9-3.6)	5.1 (1.4-16.9)	2.6 (0.5-13.2)	0.6 (0.2-2)	1.7 (0.8-3.6)	0.8 (0.5-1.5)	1.2 (0.7-2)
Psycholeptics (N05)	0.5 (0.1-1.8)	0.8 (0.3-2.2)	2.6 (0.5-13.2)	2.6 (0.5-13.2)	0.3 (0-1.6)	0.6 (0.2-2)	0.4 (0.2-1)	0.6 (0.3-1.2)

¹Matched comparator group had an estimated pregnancy start within +/- 14 days from pregnancy start for pregnant women with COVID-19 and were in the same age category. They were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they have a pseudo date of COVID-19 and pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.

Pregnancies with a COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis in Trimester 3

Table 96 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (ARS, Trimester 3 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: ARS	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 3	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched comparator group ¹	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Antibacterials (J01)	5.3 (3.7-7.6)	8.9 (6.7-11.6)	2.8 (1-8)	8.5 (4.5-15.4)	5.1 (3.1-8.2)	8.4 (5.8-12.2)	3.7 (2.9-4.8)	5.2 (4.2-6.5)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	3.7 (2.4-5.8)	29.5 (25.7-33.6)	7.5 (3.9-14.2)	50 (40.6-59.4)	2.7 (1.4-5.2)	21.3 (17-26.3)	6.4 (5.3-7.8)	8.7 (7.4-10.2)
Corticosteroids (H02)	2.8 (1.6-4.6)	3.9 (2.6-6)	2.8 (1-8)	9.4 (5.2-16.5)	2.4 (1.2-4.8)	2.4 (1.2-4.8)	0.9 (0.5-1.5)	0.9 (0.5-1.5)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	1.8 (0.9-3.3)	1.8 (0.9-3.3)	0.9 (0.2-5.2)	4.7 (2-10.6)	2 (0.9-4.4)	1 (0.3-2.9)	1.9 (1.3-2.7)	1.2 (0.7-1.9)

¹Matched comparator group had an estimated pregnancy start within +/- 14 days from pregnancy start for pregnant women with COVID-19 and were in the same age category. They were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they have a pseudo date of COVID-19 and pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.

Table 97 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (BPE, Trimester 3 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: BPE	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 3	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched comparator group ¹	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	15.3 (13.1-17.7)	71.6 (68.7-74.4)	21.9 (17-27.7)	59.8 (53.3-66)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Anti_inflammatory drugs (M01)	0.2 (0.1-0.7)	8.6 (7-10.5)	0 (0-1.7)	2.7 (1.2-5.7)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Antibacterials (J01)	6.6 (5.2-8.3)	17.8 (15.6-20.4)	7.6 (4.8-11.8)	23.7 (18.6-29.6)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	1.9 (1.2-2.9)	22.8 (20.3-25.5)	3.1 (1.5-6.3)	25.9 (20.6-32)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Corticosteroids (H02)	2.1 (1.3-3.2)	1.3 (0.8-2.3)	3.6 (1.8-6.9)	3.1 (1.5-6.3)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Cough and cold medications (R05)	1.8 (1.1-2.8)	0.5 (0.2-1.2)	4 (2.1-7.5)	1.8 (0.7-4.5)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	3.5 (2.5-4.9)	1.2 (0.7-2.1)	4.9 (2.8-8.6)	3.6 (1.8-6.9)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Nasal preparations (R01)	2 (1.3-3)	0.8 (0.4-1.6)	4.5 (2.4-8)	0.9 (0.2-3.2)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	1.6 (1-2.7)	2 (1.3-3)	3.1 (1.5-6.3)	2.2 (1-5.1)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Psycholeptics (N05)	1.3 (0.8-2.3)	1.4 (0.9-2.4)	1.8 (0.7-4.5)	2.7 (1.2-5.7)	NA	NA	NA	NA

¹ BPE did not have access to COVID-19 surveillance data. Cases were identified based on admission to hospital with a COVID-19 diagnosis, hence it was not possible to create a cohort of pregnant women who did not have a diagnosis of COVID-19, given the likelihood of misclassification of COVID-19 status.

Table 98 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (FISABIO-HSRU, Trimester 3 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: FISABIO-HSRU	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 3	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched comparator group ¹	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	1.6 (1-2.5)	3 (2.2-4.2)	1.2 (0.2-6.6)	2.4 (0.7-8.5)	2.1 (1.3-3.4)	3.3 (2.2-4.8)	1.5 (1.1-1.9)	1.7 (1.4-2.2)
Anti_inflammatory drugs (M01)	0.4 (0.2-1)	2.8 (2-3.9)	0 (0-4.5)	3.7 (1.3-10.2)	0.7 (0.3-1.5)	2 (1.2-3.2)	1.3 (1-1.7)	2.7 (2.2-3.3)
Antibacterials (J01)	4.5 (3.4-5.8)	5.3 (4.2-6.8)	7.3 (3.4-15.1)	8.5 (4.2-16.6)	4.2 (3-5.9)	5.3 (3.9-7.1)	3.4 (2.9-4.1)	3.6 (3-4.2)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	3.8 (2.9-5.1)	61.9 (59.1-64.6)	2.4 (0.7-8.5)	74.4 (64-82.6)	4.5 (3.2-6.2)	61.8 (58.3-65.2)	5.1 (4.5-5.9)	5.5 (4.8-6.3)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	2 (1.4-3)	0.9 (0.5-1.7)	4.9 (1.9-11.9)	0 (0-4.5)	1.5 (0.8-2.6)	1.2 (0.6-2.2)	0.9 (0.6-1.2)	0.6 (0.4-0.9)
Immune sera and globulins (J06)	1.5 (1-2.4)	0.3 (0.1-0.9)	0 (0-4.5)	0 (0-4.5)	2.4 (1.5-3.7)	0.5 (0.2-1.4)	1.3 (1-1.7)	0.4 (0.2-0.6)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	0.7 (0.3-1.3)	2.9 (2.1-4)	0 (0-4.5)	3.7 (1.3-10.2)	0.9 (0.4-1.9)	3.6 (2.5-5.1)	0.8 (0.5-1.1)	0.9 (0.6-1.2)

¹Matched comparator group had an estimated pregnancy start within +/- 14 days from pregnancy start for pregnant women with COVID-19 and were in the same age category. They were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they have a pseudo date of COVID-19 and pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.

Table 99 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (IACS, Trimester 3 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: IACS	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 3	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched comparator group ¹	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	8.9 (6.6-11.8)	14 (11.2-17.5)	12.2 (6.5-21.5)	18.9 (11.6-29.3)	11.3 (7.7-16.1)	13.1 (9.3-18.1)	3.3 (2.5-4.4)	4.4 (3.5-5.7)
Anti_inflammatory drugs (M01)	1.3 (0.6-2.8)	9.9 (7.5-13)	0 (0-4.9)	5.4 (2.1-13.1)	1.8 (0.7-4.5)	5.4 (3.1-9.2)	2.8 (2.1-3.8)	5.3 (4.2-6.6)
Antibacterials (J01)	5.2 (3.5-7.6)	8.4 (6.2-11.3)	4.1 (1.4-11.3)	9.5 (4.7-18.3)	5 (2.8-8.7)	6.8 (4.1-10.8)	4.1 (3.2-5.3)	5 (3.9-6.3)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	14.7 (11.8-18.2)	44.7 (40.2-49.3)	24.3 (16-35.2)	83.8 (73.8-90.5)	18.5 (13.9-24.1)	33.3 (27.5-39.8)	6.4 (5.2-7.8)	6.1 (5-7.6)
Corticosteroids (H02)	0.9 (0.3-2.2)	1.9 (1-3.7)	0 (0-4.9)	9.5 (4.7-18.3)	0.9 (0.2-3.2)	0.9 (0.2-3.2)	0.4 (0.2-1)	0.5 (0.3-1.1)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	1.7 (0.9-3.4)	0.9 (0.3-2.2)	1.4 (0.2-7.3)	2.7 (0.7-9.3)	1.4 (0.5-3.9)	0.9 (0.2-3.2)	1 (0.6-1.6)	1 (0.6-1.6)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	1.9 (1-3.7)	3 (1.8-5)	0 (0-4.9)	6.8 (2.9-14.9)	3.6 (1.8-6.9)	3.6 (1.8-6.9)	1 (0.6-1.6)	0.6 (0.3-1.2)
Psycholeptics (N05)	0.9 (0.3-2.2)	2.6 (1.5-4.5)	0 (0-4.9)	2.7 (0.7-9.3)	0.5 (0.1-2.5)	2.3 (1-5.2)	0.7 (0.4-1.4)	1.3 (0.8-2)

Table 100 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (SWANSEA, Trimester 3 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: SWANSEA	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 3 INFECTION	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched controls ¹	
	30 days pre-infection	30 days post-infection	30 days pre-infection	30 days post-infection	30 days pre-infection	30 days post-infection	30 days pre-infection ¹	30 days post-infection ¹
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	1.7 (0.9-2.9)	2.2 (1.4-3.5)	*	4.2 (2-8.9)	1.4 (0.7-2.9)	1.6 (0.8-3.2)	1.9 (1.4-2.5)	2.3 (1.8-3.1)
Antibacterials (J01)	3.4 (2.3-5)	8.1 (6.3-10.3)	4.2 (2-8.9)	10.6 (6.5-16.7)	2.9 (1.7-4.8)	7.4 (5.4-10)	3.9 (3.2-4.8)	6.2 (5.3-7.3)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	1.4 (0.7-2.5)	1.2 (0.7-2.3)	*	*	1.2 (0.6-2.7)	1.2 (0.6-2.7)	2 (1.5-2.7)	1.5 (1.1-2.1)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	1.8 (1-3)	2.1 (1.3-3.4)	*	*	1.4 (0.7-2.9)	2 (1.1-3.7)	1.8 (1.4-2.5)	1.6 (1.2-2.2)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	2.3 (1.5-3.7)	2.9 (1.9-4.4)	*	3.5 (1.5-8)	2.7 (1.6-4.5)	3.3 (2-5.3)	2.3 (1.8-3.1)	2.4 (1.9-3.2)
Psychoanaleptics (N06)	5 (3.6-6.8)	5 (3.6-6.8)	7 (3.9-12.5)	3.5 (1.5-8)	4.1 (2.7-6.2)	5.5 (3.8-7.9)	5.9 (5-6.9)	5.9 (5-6.9)

¹Matched controls had an estimated pregnancy start within +/- 14 days from pregnancy start for pregnant women with COVID-19 and were in the same age category. They were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they have a pseudo date of COVID-19 and pseudo trimester of infection, but no severity of infection.

Table 101 Prevalence of medication prescribed/dispensed in the 30 days pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis, to pregnant women, and matched pregnant women without a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis, by severity of COVID-19 disease (UIO, Trimester 3 COVID-19 disease)

DAP: UIO	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis						Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 ¹	
TRIMESTER 3	Total COVID-19 cases		Hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Non-hospitalized COVID-19 infection		Matched comparator group ¹	
	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-	30 days pre-	30 days post-
	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)	% (95% CI)
Analgesics (N02)	1.4 (0.6-2.9)	4.5 (2.9-6.9)	1.9 (0.5-6.7)	5.8 (2.7-12)	1.3 (0.5-3.4)	3 (1.6-5.6)	1.4 (0.9-2.1)	1.7 (1.1-2.5)
Anti_inflammatory drugs (M01)	0.2 (0-1.3)	1.8 (0.9-3.5)	1 (0.2-5.2)	3.8 (1.5-9.5)	0 (0-1.3)	0.7 (0.2-2.4)	0.3 (0.1-0.8)	1.1 (0.6-1.8)
Antibacterials (J01)	3.4 (2.1-5.5)	7.2 (5.2-10)	5.8 (2.7-12)	10.6 (6-18)	2.7 (1.4-5.2)	5.3 (3.3-8.5)	2.8 (2-3.8)	4.1 (3.1-5.3)
Antithrombotic agents (B01)	0.9 (0.4-2.3)	5.9 (4-8.5)	2.9 (1-8.1)	15.4 (9.7-23.5)	0.3 (0.1-1.9)	2.3 (1.1-4.7)	1.4 (0.9-2.2)	1.9 (1.3-2.8)
Cough and cold medications (R05)	0.7 (0.2-2)	2.7 (1.6-4.7)	1.9 (0.5-6.7)	5.8 (2.7-12)	0.3 (0.1-1.9)	2 (0.9-4.3)	0.2 (0-0.5)	0.2 (0-0.5)
Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	3.4 (2.1-5.5)	2 (1.1-3.8)	1.9 (0.5-6.7)	0 (0-3.6)	4.3 (2.5-7.2)	2.7 (1.4-5.2)	1.1 (0.7-1.9)	1.1 (0.6-1.8)
Medicines for obstructive airway disease (R03)	0.2 (0-1.3)	1.6 (0.8-3.2)	1 (0.2-5.2)	4.8 (2.1-10.8)	0 (0-1.3)	0.7 (0.2-2.4)	0.9 (0.5-1.6)	1.1 (0.6-1.8)

¹Matched comparator group had an estimated pregnancy start within +/- 14 days from pregnancy start for pregnant women with COVID-19 and were in the same age category. They were assigned their matched partner's COVID-19 date. Hence they have a pseudo date of COVID-19 and pseudo trimester of pregnancy, but no severity of infection.

Annex 9. Baseline characteristics of the matched cohort of pregnant and non-pregnant women with COVID-19

Non-pregnant women had COVID-19 diagnosis in the same calendar week as the COVID-19 diagnosis in pregnant women with COVID-19, and had the same age category. They were assigned the start date of pregnancy of their matched pregnant partner, hence had a 'pseudo' trimester of pregnancy when infection occurred to enable comparison.

If the COVID-19 test/positive diagnosis was +/- 2 days of delivery date these episodes were not classed as hospitalized/non-hospitalized but were included in the count of total cases.

Table 102 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (ARS, trimester 1)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
ARS								
Trimester 1	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies	207	<10	181		NA	NA	NA	
Number of unique women	207	<10	181		603	12	591	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	8.7	7.9	8.4		NA	NA	NA	
Age, Median	32	28	32		33	38	33	
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>								
Cancer	<10	<10	<10	0.86	<10	<10	<10	0.84
Cardiovascular disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.22	37(6.1%)	<10	34(5.8%)	0.80
Diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.08	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.10
HIV	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.08	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Use of immunosuppressants	25(12.4%)	0(0%)	21(11.9%)	-0.37	84(13.9%)	<10	81(13.7%)	0.33
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	<10	0(0%)	2.05
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Mental disorders	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.22	55(9.1%)	<10	51(8.6%)	0.86
Severe obesity	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.08	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.06
Chronic lung disease	10(5%)	0(0%)	<10	-0.24	35(5.8%)	<10	31(5.2%)	1.20
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Any of the above	43(21.4%)	<10	37(20.9%)	-0.16	173(28.7%)	<10	165(27.9%)	0.86
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>								
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.22	NA	NA	NA	
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>								
Gestational diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.08	NA	NA	NA	
Pre-eclampsia	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		NA	NA	NA	
Stillbirth/spont abortion	11(5.5%)	0(0%)	10(5.6%)	-0.25	NA	NA	NA	
Any of the above	12(6%)	0(0%)	11(6.2%)	-0.26	NA	NA	NA	

Table 103 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (BPE, trimester 1)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19 ¹	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19 ¹	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
BPE								
Trimester 1	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies	<10	<10	no records		NA	NA	no records	
Number of unique women	<10	<10	no records		12	12	no records	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	13.3	13.3	no records		NA	NA	no records	
Age, Median	30	30	no records		33.5	33.5	no records	
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>								
Cancer	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		0(0%)	0(0%)	no records	
Cardiovascular disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		0(0%)	0(0%)	no records	
Diabetes	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		0(0%)	0(0%)	no records	
HIV	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		0(0%)	0(0%)	no records	
Use of immunosuppressants	<10	<10	no records		<10	<10	no records	
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		0(0%)	0(0%)	no records	
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		0(0%)	0(0%)	no records	
Mental disorders	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		<10	<10	no records	
Severe obesity	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		<10	<10	no records	
Chronic lung disease	<10	<10	no records		<10	<10	no records	
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		0(0%)	0(0%)	no records	
Any of the above	<10	<10	no records		10(83.3%)	10(83.3%)	no records	
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>								
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy ²	NA	NA	no records		NA	NA	no records	
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>								
Gestational diabetes	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		NA	NA	no records	
Pre-eclampsia	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		NA	NA	no records	
Stillbirth/spont abortion	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		NA	NA	no records	
Any of the above	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		NA	NA	no records	

¹In BPE COVID-19 cases were identified based on admission to hospital with a COVID-19 diagnosis. Hence there are no cases classed as non-hospitalized. ²BPE did not have access to vaccination records.

Table 104 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (FISABIO-HSRU, trimester 1)

FISABIO-HSRU	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
Trimester 1	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies	941	<10	915		NA	NA	NA	
Number of unique women	940	<10	914		2820	38	2782	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	7.1	10.1	7		NA	NA	NA	
Age, Median	32	26.5	32		32	35	32	
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>								
Cancer	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	23(0.8%)	<10	22(0.8%)	0.20
Cardiovascular disease	55(5.9%)	0(0%)	54(5.9%)	-0.25	117(4.1%)	11(28.9%)	106(3.8%)	1.26
Diabetes	18(1.9%)	0(0%)	18(2%)	-0.14	25(0.9%)	0(0%)	25(0.9%)	-0.10
HIV	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Use of immunosuppressants	40(4.3%)	0(0%)	37(4%)	-0.21	88(3.1%)	<10	85(3.1%)	0.28
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	<10	<10	0.97
Chronic liver disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.05	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.05
Mental disorders	91(9.7%)	0(0%)	88(9.6%)	-0.33	226(8%)	<10	219(7.9%)	0.39
Severe obesity	20(2.1%)	0(0%)	20(2.2%)	-0.15	44(1.6%)	<10	40(1.4%)	0.73
Chronic lung disease	117(12.4%)	0(0%)	115(12.6%)	-0.38	289(10.2%)	<10	283(10.2%)	0.19
Sickle cell disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.06	<10	<10	<10	0.49
Any of the above	253(26.9%)	0(0%)	246(26.9%)	-0.61	657(23.3%)	20(52.6%)	637(22.9%)	0.70
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>								
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		NA	NA	NA	NA
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>								
Gestational diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	19(0.7%)	NA	NA	NA	
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	<10	NA	NA	NA	
Stillbirth/spont abortion	86(9.1%)	0(0%)	83(9.1%)	13(0.5%)	NA	NA	NA	
Any of the above	96(10.2%)	0(0%)	92(10.1%)	36(1.3%)	NA	NA	NA	

Table 105 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (IACS, trimester 1)

IACS	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
Trimester 1	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies	190	<10	177		NA	NA	NA	
Number of unique women	189	<10	176		545	17	528	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	7.1	6.6	7		NA	NA	NA	
Age, Median	33	31.5	33		32	34	31	
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>								
Cancer	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	<10	<10	0.71
Cardiovascular disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.14	13(2.4%)	<10	12(2.3%)	0.29
Diabetes	<10	<10	0(0%)	1.91	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.13
HIV	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Use of immunosuppressants	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.18	24(4.4%)	<10	22(4.2%)	0.45
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.04
Mental disorders	35(19%)	<10	32(18.6%)	0.25	80(14.7%)	<10	76(14.3%)	0.35
Severe obesity	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.08	<10	<10	<10	0.62
Chronic lung disease	13(7.1%)	0(0%)	13(7.6%)	-0.29	44(8.1%)	<10	42(7.9%)	0.20
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Any of the above	48(26.1%)	<10	45(26.2%)	0.05	142(26.1%)	<10	137(25.8%)	0.17
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>								
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		NA	NA	NA	
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>								
Gestational diabetes	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		NA	NA	NA	
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.11	NA	NA	NA	
Stillbirth/spont abortion	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.16	NA	NA	NA	
Any of the above	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.19	NA	NA	NA	

Table 106 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (UIO, trimester 1)

UIO	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
Trimester 1	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies	230	13	217		NA	NA	NA	
Number of unique women	230	13	217		690	37	653	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	8.2	8	8.3		NA	NA	NA	
Age, Median	30	32	30		31	30	31	
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>								
Cancer	<10	<10	<10	0.21	13(1.9%)	0(0%)	13(2%)	-0.15
Cardiovascular disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.20	<10	<10	<10	0.13
Diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.14	12(1.7%)	<10	11(1.7%)	0.08
HIV	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.06
Use of immunosuppressants	<10	<10	<10	0.21	22(3.2%)	<10	21(3.2%)	-0.03
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Chronic liver disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.06
Mental disorders	11(4.8%)	<10	<10	0.91	66(9.6%)	<10	60(9.2%)	0.24
Severe obesity	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.16	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.12
Chronic lung disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.20	31(4.5%)	<10	27(4.1%)	0.32
Sickle cell disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Any of the above	44(19.1%)	<10	40(18.4%)	0.31	129(18.7%)	<10	119(18.2%)	0.23
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>								
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	7(3%)	0(0%)	7(3.2%)	-0.19	NA	NA	NA	
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>								
Gestational diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	NA	NA	NA	
Pre-eclampsia	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		NA	NA	NA	
Stillbirth/spont abortion	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		NA	NA	NA	
Any of the above	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	NA	NA	NA	

Pregnancies with a COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis in Trimester 2

Table 107 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (ARS, trimester 2)

ARS	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
Trimester 1	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies	277	17	260		NA	NA	NA	
Number of unique women	276	17	259		819	13	806	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	21.7	24.4	21.6		NA	NA	NA	
Age, Median	32	34	32		32	36	32	
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>								
Cancer	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.11	<10	<10	<10	0.75
Cardiovascular disease	14(5.1%)	<10	12(4.7%)	0.32	33(4%)	<10	31(3.8%)	0.59
Diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.13	14(1.7%)	0(0%)	14(1.7%)	-0.13
HIV	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.06	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.05
Use of immunosuppressants	36(13.2%)	<10	34(13.3%)	-0.04	123(15%)	<10	119(14.8%)	0.45
Chronic kidney disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.06	<10	<10	0(0%)	2.20
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Mental disorders	12(4.4%)	0(0%)	12(4.7%)	-0.23	59(7.2%)	0(0%)	59(7.3%)	-0.28
Severe obesity	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.06	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.04
Chronic lung disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.20	54(6.6%)	<10	53(6.6%)	0.04
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Any of the above	62(22.7%)	<10	58(22.7%)	0.02	221(27%)	6(46.2%)	215(26.7%)	0.44
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>								
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	<10	0(0%)	2(0.8%)	-0.09	NA	NA	NA	
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>								
Gestational diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.13	NA	NA	NA	
Pre-eclampsia	<10	<10	<10	0.49	NA	NA	NA	
Stillbirth/spont abortion	17(6.2%)	0(0%)	17(6.6%)	-0.27	NA	NA	NA	
Any of the above	22(8.1%)	<10	21(8.2%)	-0.09	NA	NA	NA	

Table 108 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (BPE, trimester 2)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19 ¹	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19 ¹	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
BPE								
Trimester 2	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies	92	92	no records		NA	NA	no records	
Number of unique women	89	89	no records		170	170	no records	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	22.9	22.9	no records		NA	NA	no records	
Age, Median	29	29	no records		32	32	no records	
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>								
Cancer	<10	<10	no records		13(7.6%)	13(7.6%)	no records	
Cardiovascular disease	<10	<10	no records		15(8.8%)	15(8.8%)	no records	
Diabetes	<10	<10	no records		10(5.9%)	10(5.9%)	no records	
HIV	<10	<10	no records		0(0%)	0(0%)	no records	
Use of immunosuppressants	22(25.9%)	22(25.9%)	no records		52(30.6%)	52(30.6%)	no records	
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		<10	<10	no records	
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		<10	<10	no records	
Mental disorders	16(18.8%)	16(18.8%)	no records		43(25.3%)	43(25.3%)	no records	
Severe obesity	<10	<10	no records		10(5.9%)	10(5.9%)	no records	
Chronic lung disease	12(14.1%)	12(14.1%)	no records		46(27.1%)	46(27.1%)	no records	
Sickle cell disease	<10	<10	no records		<10	<10	no records	
Any of the above	40(47.1%)	40(47.1%)	no records		106(62.4%)	106(62.4%)	no records	
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>								
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy ²	NA	NA	no records		NA	NA	no records	
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>								
Gestational diabetes	<10	<10	no records		NA	NA	no records	
Pre-eclampsia	<10	<10	no records		NA	NA	no records	
Stillbirth/spont abortion	<10	<10	no records		NA	NA	no records	
Any of the above	<10	<10	no records		NA	NA	no records	

¹In BPE COVID-19 cases were identified based on admission to hospital with a COVID-19 diagnosis. Hence there are no cases classed as non-hospitalized. ²BPE did not have access to vaccination records.

Table 109 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (FISABIO-HSRU, trimester 2)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
FISABIO-HSRU								
Trimester 2	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies	856	13	839		NA	NA	NA	
Number of unique women	856	13	839		2568	30	2538	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	20.7	24	20.7		NA	NA	NA	
Age, Median	32	33	32		32	35.5	32	
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>								
Cancer	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.10	19(0.7%)	0(0%)	19(0.7%)	-0.09
Cardiovascular disease	48(5.6%)	<10	44(5.2%)	0.78	105(4.1%)	<10	104(4.1%)	-0.04
Diabetes	13(1.5%)	0(0%)	13(1.5%)	-0.13	30(1.2%)	<10	29(1.1%)	0.20
HIV	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.03	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.02
Use of immunosuppressants	24(2.8%)	0(0%)	24(2.9%)	-0.17	91(3.5%)	<10	88(3.5%)	0.35
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.03
Chronic liver disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.05	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.06
Mental disorders	56(6.5%)	<10	54(6.4%)	0.36	229(8.9%)	<10	226(8.9%)	0.04
Severe obesity	14(1.6%)	0(0%)	13(1.5%)	-0.13	46(1.8%)	<10	43(1.7%)	0.63
Chronic lung disease	88(10.3%)	<10	86(10.3%)	-0.08	272(10.6%)	<10	267(10.5%)	0.20
Sickle cell disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.03	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.05
Any of the above	185(21.6%)	<10	180(21.5%)	0.23	618(24.1%)	10(33.3%)	608(24%)	0.22
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>								
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		NA	NA	NA	
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>								
Gestational diabetes	13(1.5%)	1(7.7%)	12(1.4%)	0.51	NA	NA	NA	
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.06	NA	NA	NA	
Stillbirth/spont abortion	83(9.7%)	<10	82(9.8%)	-0.07	NA	NA	NA	

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
FISABIO-HSRU	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Trimester 2								
Any of the above	98(11.4%)	<10	96(11.4%)	0.12	NA	NA	NA	

Table 110 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (IACS, trimester 2)

IACS	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
Trimester 2	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies	266	17	249		NA	NA	NA	
Number of unique women	265	17	248		783	32	751	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	21.2	21.7	21.1		NA	NA	NA	
Age, Median	33	37	33		31	36	31	
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>								
Cancer	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	13(1.7%)	<10	12(1.6%)	0.22
Cardiovascular disease	15(5.7%)	0(0%)	15(6.1%)	-0.26	32(4.1%)	5(21.7%)	27(3.6%)	0.92
Diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.16	10(1.3%)	<10	<10	0.28
HIV	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Use of immunosuppressants	13(5%)	<10	12(4.9%)	0.06	34(4.3%)	<10	32(4.2%)	0.22
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	<10	<10	0.83
Mental disorders	31(11.9%)	<10	28(11.4%)	0.23	100(12.8%)	<10	93(12.2%)	0.54
Severe obesity	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	<10	<10	0.34
Chronic lung disease	26(10%)	<10	24(9.8%)	0.09	73(9.3%)	<10	68(8.9%)	0.44
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.04
Any of the above	68(26.1%)	<10	63(25.7%)	0.13	204(26.1%)	12(52.2%)	192(25.3%)	0.61
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>								
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		NA	NA	NA	
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>								
Gestational diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.18	NA	NA	NA	
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.11	NA	NA	NA	
Stillbirth/spont abortion	<10	<10	<10	0.16	NA	NA	NA	
Any of the above	18(6.9%)	<10	17(6.9%)	-0.03	NA	NA	NA	

Table 111 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (UIO, trimester 2)

UIO	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
Trimester 2	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies	398	39	359		NA	NA	NA	
Number of unique women	398	39	359		1194	59	1135	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	21.1	24.3	21		NA	NA	NA	
Age, Median	31	33	30		31	32	31	
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>								
Cancer	14(3.5%)	<10	13(3.6%)	-0.06	14(1.2%)	<10	13(1.1%)	0.05
Cardiovascular disease	11(2.8%)	0(0%)	11(3.1%)	-0.19	14(1.2%)	<10	12(1.1%)	0.22
Diabetes	<10	<10	<10	0.04	33(2.8%)	<10	30(2.6%)	0.15
HIV	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.03
Use of immunosuppressants	13(3.3%)	<10	11(3.1%)	0.12	40(3.4%)	<10	36(3.2%)	0.20
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	<10	<10	0.15
Mental disorders	27(6.8%)	<10	24(6.7%)	0.04	132(11.1%)	13(22%)	119(10.5%)	0.37
Severe obesity	<10	<10	<10	0.13	17(1.4%)	0(0%)	17(1.5%)	-0.13
Chronic lung disease	13(3.3%)	<10	11(3.1%)	0.12	77(6.4%)	<10	72(6.3%)	0.09
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Any of the above	70(17.6%)	<10	62(17.3%)	0.09	267(22.4%)	19(32.2%)	248(21.9%)	0.25
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>								
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	<10	<10	<10	0.02	NA	NA	NA	
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>								
Gestational diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.1	NA	NA	NA	
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.1	NA	NA	NA	
Stillbirth/spont abortion	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.1	NA	NA	NA	
Any of the above	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.1	NA	NA	NA	

Pregnancies with a COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis in Trimester 3

Table 112 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (ARS, trimester 3)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
ARS								
Trimester 3	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies	508	106	296		NA	NA	NA	
Number of unique women	508	106	296		1524	29	1495	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	36.6	37.6	33.8		NA	NA	NA	
Age, Median	31	32	31		32	35	32	
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>								
Cancer	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.10	20(1.3%)	0(0%)	20(1.3%)	-0.12
Cardiovascular disease	18(3.5%)	<10	10(3.4%)	0.02	52(3.4%)	0(0%)	52(3.5%)	-0.19
Diabetes	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	21(1.4%)	<10	20(1.3%)	0.18
HIV	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.04
Use of immunosuppressants	68(13.4%)	16(15.1%)	39(13.2%)	0.06	206(13.5%)	<10	202(13.5%)	0.01
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.05
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Mental disorders	16(3.1%)	<10	12(4.1%)	-0.12	85(5.6%)	<10	83(5.6%)	0.06
Severe obesity	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Chronic lung disease	26(5.1%)	<10	16(5.4%)	-0.07	89(5.8%)	<10	88(5.9%)	-0.10
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Any of the above	100(19.7%)	21(19.8%)	61(20.6%)	-0.02	376(24.7%)	7(24.1%)	369(24.7%)	-0.01
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>								
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	<10	<10	<10	-0.06	NA	NA	NA	
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>								

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
ARS								
Trimester 3	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Gestational diabetes	<10	<10	<10	0.02	NA	NA	NA	
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	NA	NA	NA	
Stillbirth/spont abortion	42(8.3%)	<10	26(8.8%)	-0.01	NA	NA	NA	
Any of the above	50(9.8%)	11(10.4%)	31(10.5%)	0.00	NA	NA	NA	

Table 113 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (BPE, trimester 3)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19 ¹	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19 ¹	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
BPE								
Trimester 3	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies	970	224	no records		NA	NA	no records	
Number of unique women	924	220	no records		1839	1839	no records	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	39.9	35.5	no records		NA	NA	no records	
Age, Median	30	30	no records		31	31	no records	
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>								
Cancer	29(3.1%)	<10	no records		106(5.8%)	106(5.8%)	no records	
Cardiovascular disease	34(3.7%)	13(6%)	no records		170(9.2%)	170(9.2%)	no records	
Diabetes	16(1.7%)	<10	no records		57(3.1%)	57(3.1%)	no records	
HIV	<10	<10	no records		<10	<10	no records	
Use of immunosuppressants	198(21.4%)	49(22.5%)	no records		531(28.9%)	531(28.9%)	no records	
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		<10	<10	no records	
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	no records		<10	<10	no records	
Mental disorders	122(13.2%)	39(17.9%)	no records		462(25.1%)	462(25.1%)	no records	
Severe obesity	11(1.2%)	<10	no records		67(3.6%)	67(3.6%)	no records	
Chronic lung disease	85(9.2%)	18(8.3%)	no records		302(16.4%)	302(16.4%)	no records	
Sickle cell disease	<10	<10	no records		13(0.7%)	13(0.7%)	no records	
Any of the above	363(39.2%)	99(45.4%)	no records		1001(54.4%)	1001(54.4%)	no records	

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
BPE	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19 ¹	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19 ¹	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
Trimester 3	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>								
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy ²	NA	NA	no records		NA	NA	no records	
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>								
Gestational diabetes	15(1.6%)	<10	no records		NA	NA	no records	
Pre-eclampsia	<10	<10	no records		NA	NA	no records	
Stillbirth/spont abortion	36(3.9%)	<10	no records		NA	NA	no records	
Any of the above	55(5.9%)	15(6.9%)	no records		NA	NA	no records	

¹In BPE COVID-19 cases were identified based on admission to hospital with a COVID-19 diagnosis. Hence there are no cases classed as non-hospitalized. ²BPE did not have access to vaccination records.

Table 114 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (FISABIO-HSRU, trimester 3)

	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
FISABIO-HSRU								
Trimester 3	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies	1181	82	756		NA	NA	NA	
Number of unique women	1181	82	756		3543	3543	3543	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	35.4	36.8	33.1		NA	NA	NA	
Age, Median	31	32	31		32	34	32	
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>								
Cancer	10(0.8%)	<10	<10	-0.10	35(1%)	0(0%)	35(1%)	-0.10
Cardiovascular disease	42(3.6%)	<10	29(3.8%)	0.05	166(4.7%)	<10	158(4.5%)	0.59
Diabetes	10(0.8%)	0(0%)	<10	-0.10	31(0.9%)	<10	29(0.8%)	0.37
HIV	<10	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.02
Use of immunosuppressants	31(2.6%)	<10	24(3.2%)	-0.04	145(4.1%)	5(10.6%)	140(4%)	0.33
Chronic kidney disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.04	<10	<10	<10	0.88
Chronic liver disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.04	16(0.5%)	<10	14(0.4%)	0.57
Mental disorders	80(6.8%)	<10	51(6.7%)	0.02	318(9%)	<10	313(9%)	0.06
Severe obesity	19(1.6%)	<10	13(1.7%)	-0.04	73(2.1%)	<10	68(1.9%)	0.61
Chronic lung disease	108(9.1%)	<10	74(9.8%)	-0.04	357(10.1%)	<10	350(10%)	0.16
Sickle cell disease	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.04	10(0.3%)	<10	<10	0.76
Any of the above	246(20.8%)	15(18.3%)	166(22%)	-0.09	868(24.5%)	19(40.4%)	849(24.3%)	0.38
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>								
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		NA	NA	NA	
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>								
Gestational diabetes	15(1.3%)	0(0%)	<10	-0.11	NA	NA	NA	
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07	NA	NA	NA	
Stillbirth/spont abortion	96(8.1%)	8(9.8%)	54(7.1%)	0.10	NA	NA	NA	
Any of the above	112(9.5%)	8(9.8%)	65(8.6%)	0.04	NA	NA	NA	

Table 115 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (IACS, trimester 3)

IACS	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
Trimester 3	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies	436	72	198		NA	NA	NA	
Number of unique women	431	71	187		1292	33	1259	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis)	37	36.9	33.3		NA	NA	NA	
Age, Median	31	31.5	32		32	34	32	
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>								
Cancer	<10	<10	<10	0.04	11(0.9%)	<10	10(0.8%)	0.19
Cardiovascular disease	21(4.9%)	<10	12(6.1%)	-0.07	41(3.2%)	<10	33(2.6%)	0.99
Diabetes	<10	<10	<10	0.11	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.08
HIV	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Use of immunosuppressants	19(4.4%)	<10	11(5.6%)	-0.12	56(4.3%)	<10	53(4.2%)	0.16
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.03
Mental disorders	47(10.9%)	<10	25(12.7%)	-0.17	197(15.2%)	<10	189(15.1%)	0.14
Severe obesity	<10	<10	<10	0.11	<10	<10	<10	0.22
Chronic lung disease	28(6.5%)	<10	18(9.1%)	-0.23	113(8.7%)	<10	108(8.6%)	0.14
Sickle cell disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.03
Any of the above	101(23.4%)	12(17.6%)	55(27.9%)	-0.24	347(26.9%)	17(42.5%)	330(26.4%)	0.36
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>								
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		NA	NA	NA	
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>								
Gestational diabetes	<10	<10	<10	-0.08	NA	NA	NA	
Pre-eclampsia	<10	<10	<10	-0.08	NA	NA	NA	
Stillbirth/spont abortion	14(3.1%)	<10	<10	-0.06	NA	NA	NA	
Any of the above	17(3.9%)	<10	10(5.1%)	-0.10	NA	NA	NA	

Table 116 Baseline characteristics of pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis and matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/ diagnosis (UIO, trimester 3)

UIO	Pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis				Matched non-pregnant women with a positive COVID-19 test/diagnosis			
	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)	Total COVID-19	Hospitalized COVID-19	Non-Hospitalized COVID-19	Standardized difference (hospitalized vs. non-hospitalized)
Trimester 3	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Number of pregnancies	443	104	301		NA	NA	NA	
Number of unique women	443	104	301		1329	36	1293	
Median gestational weeks at diagnosis	34.6	37.1	33.3		NA	NA	NA	
Age, Median	30	31	30		31	32	31	
<i>Co-morbid conditions</i>								
Cancer	15(3.4%)	<10	12(4%)	-0.11	21(1.6%)	<10	20(1.5%)	0.10
Cardiovascular disease	15(3.4%)	<10	10(3.3%)	0.03	20(1.5%)	<10	18(1.4%)	0.34
Diabetes	10(2.3%)	0(0%)	10(3.3%)	-0.21	19(1.4%)	<10	16(1.2%)	0.60
HIV	<10	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.05
Use of immunosuppressants	10(2.3%)	<10	<10	-0.05	45(3.4%)	<10	42(3.2%)	0.28
Chronic kidney disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.04
Chronic liver disease	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)		<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.07
Mental disorders	28(6.3%)	<10	17(5.6%)	0.12	130(9.8%)	<10	126(9.7%)	0.05
Severe obesity	<10	<10	<10	0.12	15(1.1%)	0(0%)	15(1.2%)	-0.11
Chronic lung disease	24(5.4%)	<10	19(6.3%)	-0.06	84(6.3%)	<10	80(6.2%)	0.20
Sickle cell disease	<10	0(0%)	0(0%)		0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Any of the above	87(19.6%)	21(20.2%)	59(19.6%)	0.01	271(20.4%)	10(27.8%)	261(20.2%)	0.19
<i>Maternal vaccination</i>								
Influenza vaccination during pregnancy	<10	<10	<10	0.13	NA	NA	NA	
<i>Obstetric risk, prior history</i>								
Gestational diabetes	<10	<10	<10	-0.03	NA	NA	NA	
Pre-eclampsia	<10	0(0%)	<10	-0.09	NA	NA	NA	
Stillbirth/spont abortion	<10	<10	<10	0.03	NA	NA	NA	
Any of the above	14(3.2%)	<10	<10	-0.02	NA	NA	NA	

